

II International Congress

A Metaverse for The Good: Exploring the Intersection of AI and the Metaverse

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A Metaverse for the Good

Exploring the Intersection of AI and the Metaverse

Conference 11-12th June, 2025

University of Alicante, Spain

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Theme: AI and the Metaverse

The [European Metaverse Research Network](#) and the [Academic Chair for the Responsible Development of the Metaverse of the University of Alicante](#) organised the II International Congress “[Metaverse for the Good: Exploring the Intersection of AI and the Metaverse](#)”, in the framework of the [Project on the Implementation of the Charter of Digital Rights](#) financed by the public entity Red.es in Alicante, 11-12 June, and is part of the activities of the [European Metaverse Research Network](#).

Background

The idea of the metaverse is a vast extended reality set of worlds where physical and virtual reality intersect. It might be inhabited at any one time by millions of people, and as in the real world groups of people can interact with one another in real-time. The virtual metaverse will overlap with the physical world in various ways – for example, walking into a particular place in the physical world may transport you to a virtual place, where you are interacting with life-sized virtual humans who may be anywhere in the real world. Some of those ‘people’ you interact with might not be human but representations of AI agents. This can have far reaching beneficial consequences. For example, an AI agent might be an expert in psychological counselling who can treat millions of clients simultaneously. Another might be explaining to you how you can use some complex machine in the physical world. Another may be teaching mathematics. However, as with any technology there are multiple possibilities for malfeasance. As you walk through a physical street wearing augmented reality spectacles you may be bombarded by virtual humans trying to sell you something (a ‘feature’ you can only switch off by paying a global company). There are boundless possibilities for impersonation and political manipulation, as well as countless positive aspects that we can hardly see today – because as with any new technology, our predictions are likely to be incorrect. Mobile phones and social media have connected people in ways almost unimaginable a few years ago, but they also seem to be threatening democracy – with the loss of a common shared reality to which everyone relates. In this respect the Metaverse, with its immersion and sense of presence, may be orders of magnitude more powerful – positively and negatively.

This is not a Frontiers publication, but it is in conjunction with Frontiers in Virtual Reality, who have offered a prize for the best paper, and there will be a Research Topic associated with this conference.

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Session 1: Virtual humans: Agents, avatars, and AI-driven personalities

Synthetic selves: exploring identity construction through virtual avatars and AI in XR environments

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10 **Keywords: VR, XR, Metaverse, AI, Identity, Avatar, Embodiment, Self**

11 **Abstract**

12 As virtual environments grow increasingly immersive and intelligent, virtual avatars evolve beyond
13 aesthetic representations into tools for identity experimentation, psychological insight, and
14 therapeutic applications. Our proposal explores the convergence between Extended Reality (XR) and
15 Artificial Intelligence (AI) in enabling dynamic identity construction through avatar embodiment. It
16 examines how avatars influence users' self-perception, behaviour, and well-being, and how AI
17 models can analyse real-time user data to shape adaptive digital identities. This intersection opens
18 transformative possibilities in healthcare, social development, and personal growth—but not without
19 introducing ethical, cognitive, and sociocultural challenges that demand urgent multidisciplinary
20 inquiry. How are these technologies redefining the concept of humanity, balancing opportunities and
21 new challenges for society?

22 **Article type:** perspective

23 **1 Introduction**

24 In the present work we adopt an interdisciplinary approach that spans from human-computer
25 interaction (HCI), embodied cognition research, and digital ethics to examine how extended reality
26 (XR) technologies can reshape human identity through avatar-mediated experiences. We recognise
27 that avatar-mediated identity creation occurs within complex sociotechnical systems which require
28 both technical understanding and humanistic reasoning.

29 **2 Where are we? A brief review**

30 Neuroscience and cognitive science have highlighted the brain's adaptability to altered sensory
31 feedback, a phenomenon central to the sense of embodiment in XR environments. (Slater et al.,
32 2010) and (Kilteni et al. 2012) show that virtual avatars can evoke strong sensations of ownership,

33 agency, and self-location, leading to shifts in self-perception. The Proteus Effect (Yee, N., &
34 Bailenson, J. 2007) further illustrates how avatar traits unconsciously influence user behaviour even
35 after the virtual experience. Meanwhile, contemporary research provides insights into the
36 psychological and behavioural impacts of avatar embodiment. (Era et al. 2025) investigates how
37 interactions with virtual avatars affect human perception and social behaviours, while (Yim et al.,
38 2024) explores the Proteus Effect's influence on pain perception, revealing that embodying a
39 muscular avatar can reduce perceived pain.

40 AI-driven virtual experiences are increasingly capable of integrating biometric and behavioural data,
41 such as heart rate, gaze, and posture, to adapt in real time to users' emotional and cognitive states
42 (Bhatt, Jogy, & Puri, 2024; Lau et al., 2024). By dynamically modelling user behaviour within
43 immersive environments, these experiences can mirror affective responses, deliver tailored feedback,
44 and foster deeper self-reflection, enhancing both engagement and therapeutic outcomes
45 (Purushothaman et al., 2025). Through advanced user modelling techniques, such systems can
46 personalise interactions at a granular level, making virtual environments more intuitive and
47 responsive (Velez Quintero, 2023).

48 The growing integration of real-time physiological and behavioural data in VR allows avatars to
49 become active participants in this loop, representing not just a digital identity, but a living, adaptive
50 embodiment of the user's state. This evolution could profoundly shape how we perceive ourselves,
51 blending external expression with internal signals in avatar-mediated self-representation.

52 The concept of virtual humans, AI-generated replicas of individuals, has recently gained momentum,
53 allowing the creation of avatars that closely mimic human ways of acting and personality. (Park et
54 al., 2024) indicates that AI agents can replicate a person's personality with up to 85% accuracy after
55 just two hours of interaction. Such developments raise questions about the degree of authenticity and
56 the resulting ethical implications of virtual identities.

57 On the other hand, MetaHuman technology exemplifies the potential of AI in recreating lifelike
58 avatars. A notable project (MetaHuman, 2022) brought a 10,000-year-old shaman back to life by
59 reconstructing his facial features and expressions, demonstrating the technology's capability to
60 animate historical figures with remarkable realism, disrupting traditional limitations that had served
61 so far as a foundation for our individual and social debate.

62 These technologies need urgent multidisciplinary inquiry to ensure responsible development and
63 integration (Methuku & Myakala, 2025). We must design a set of ethical structures that are not
64 limited to “emergency management” but are able to give useful directions for humans and technology
65 together.

66 **3 Opportunities**

67 **3.1 XR as a tool for ontological experimentation**

68 While much of the focus in XR discourse centres on representation and simulation, its deeper
69 promise lies in the rewriting of self through lived, embodied fiction. In avatar-mediated XR,
70 individuals are offered not only the freedom to represent who they are but also to experiment with
71 who they could be. This possibility becomes more than cosmetic—it is ontological. By stepping into
72 new forms, genders, scales, species, or even abstract identities, users can explore perspectives
73 inaccessible in the physical world.

74 For example, the ZEPETO platform allows users to extensively customise their avatars. Research
75 (Kang & Rhee, 2025) has found that changing an avatar's gender presentation can significantly
76 influence users' perceptions of their own gender identity, which can be especially empowering for
77 those who are exploring or transitioning their gender in real life. Avatar embodiment can serve as a
78 "rehearsal space" for identity transformation, supporting, let's say, an ontological experimentation
79 through virtual embodiment. This isn't just escapism; it's a rehearsal space for empathy, resilience,
80 and transformation.

81 **3.2 A feedback loop between digital and physical identity**

82 Traditionally, there are two perspectives of experience of personal identity that cannot be traced back
83 to each other (Plessner, 2003): the self-testimony of inner experience and the hetero-testimony of
84 outer experience. What makes XR's influence on identity this powerful is not just the capacity to
85 change form, but the feedback loop it creates between digital and physical identity. The way we
86 move as a dragon, breathe as a deity, or interact as a child in a virtual space can subtly inform our
87 offline experience. Over time, these immersive rehearsals can become tools for re-patterning trauma,
88 reframing self-esteem, or even confronting implicit bias. Recent advancements in adaptive VR
89 systems have demonstrated the potential of integrating physiological signals, such as eye tracking
90 and heart rate variability (HRV), to detect cognitive load and stress in real-time. For instance, (Nasri
91 2025) developed a framework where machine learning models, trained on data from tasks like the
92 Stroop test, dynamically adjust VR training difficulty based on users' physiological responses. This
93 approach not only enhances engagement but also supports emotional regulation during immersive
94 experiences.

95 When AI joins this loop, processing emotional, biometric, and behavioural data to create avatars that
96 evolve with us, our digital twin becomes less a copy and more a mirror—and even a lab—a dynamic
97 construct reflecting our becoming, not just our being. Such integration suggests that avatars could
98 adapt in real-time to our internal states, offering personalised interactions that reinforce positive
99 identity formation and resilience.

100 **3.3 A computational platform for creativity**

101 More radically, the multisensory partiality of XR, its inability to fully replicate real-world
102 experience, can itself be reframed as a space of creative mutation. Because XR cannot represent
103 everything, it invites us to choose what to bring forward: it foregrounds what matters, amplifies what
104 is hidden, and silences what is often oppressive. It allows users to distil their identities into symbolic,
105 mythic, or speculative archetypes, something that physical reality rarely permits. Here, virtual
106 embodiment becomes myth-making, and the avatar becomes a prosthesis not of the body, but of the
107 soul. Projects like Soul Paint (Dew et al., 2020) that enable individuals to show their pain, can be
108 redesigned and modulated to become a true means of communication for the incommunicable
109 experiences of a person.

110 **3.4 XR as a site for co-authored identity**

111 XR is a laboratory ready to support instances of equality and inclusion at multiple levels, leading us
112 to discoveries that could initiate a redesign of the experience, narrative and even offline
113 environments. XR's shared spaces offer the potential for identity not just to be personal, but co-
114 authored. In these synthetic environments, people can play with social dynamics in ways that
115 challenge normative structures of gender, race, age, or ability. Inclusion can be designed and tested,

116 rather than merely tolerated. Communities can form around shared speculative embodiment, and new
117 social imaginaries can be prototyped in real time.

118 According to a 2023 report by Meta, users from Gen Z perceive the two identities, physical and
119 avatar, as different and not necessarily consistent with each other; avatar's appearance, on the other
120 hand, can influence the behaviour of users with previous relationships, when they engage with each
121 other in VR (Rivu et al., 2021). This allows for a great space of experimentation, paving the way to
122 designing experiences that can study and even challenge traditional social interactions.

123 If curated ethically, these spaces have the potential not only to heal but to disrupt. They can challenge
124 inherited narratives, normalise multiplicity, and provide marginalised identities with tools to exist
125 loudly, safely, and visibly (Tirinzoni & Megale, 2025). Used with intention, XR becomes not just a
126 technology of presence, but of reclamation: of voice, of self, of future.

127 **4 Challenges and risks**

128 **4.1 Sensory asymmetry of XR and the risk of fragmented identity**

129 While XR offers new affordances for shaping identity, its very mechanisms raise epistemological and
130 psychological concerns. Virtual Reality, as a multisensory simulation, engages vision,
131 proprioception, and, when equipped, sound, haptics, and limited spatial cues. Yet, it still operates
132 within a constrained sensory bandwidth when compared to the full spectrum of physical embodiment.
133 Human identity is shaped through a rich entanglement of interoception, thermosensation, olfaction,
134 balance, and tactile nuance. Partial stimulation, then, might not only produce a reduced representation
135 of the self, but a fragmented one, where selected aspects of identity are overexpressed while others
136 are silenced or underdeveloped. This asymmetry could influence users differently in the short term
137 (e.g., altered emotional regulation or sensory detachment) or even in the long term, potentially
138 reinforcing dissociative patterns or hyper-identification with idealised avatar traits, especially among
139 vulnerable individuals.

140 In addition, exposure to models that force specific human characteristics in one direction or another,
141 especially without proper literacy about said models and the technology that creates them, can alter
142 not only the perception of the most fragile individuals, but influence 'fashion' in the strongest sense
143 of the term linked to belonging and self-acceptance (Simmel, 1905) with consequences not only for
144 individuals but for the resulting human communities and their interpersonal relationships. In the face
145 of the emergence of virtual influencers and robot models, it is also necessary to focus on the
146 influence that the implementation of these technologies has on human imagery, tastes, and choices.

147 **4.2 The risk of identity echo chambers**

148 VR experiences can be personalised through biofeedback and AI-based adaptation (Robobionics
149 Content Writer, 2025; Kim, Lee, & Kim, 2025; Reeves et al., 2024; Reeves et al., 2022). While this
150 can enhance engagement and tailored interventions, looking in the long term it may also create the
151 conditions for identity echo chambers, environments that reflect, reinforce, and replicate the user's
152 existing cognitive-emotional patterns without including potential divergence or challenge. Much like
153 algorithmic bubbles in social media, such feedback loops in virtual identity may stifle growth by
154 limiting confrontation with the unfamiliar, inhibiting critical self-reflection, and generating a sense of
155 ontological comfort that borders on stasis. If one's avatar, virtual interactions, and environments
156 continually reaffirm a narrow conception of the self, XR risks becoming a mirror rather than a
157 window, amplifying identity redundancy instead of transformation. It is necessary to think of systems

158 that avoid merely reinforcing existing identity patterns, provide comparisons and generally ‘get out of
159 the bubble’. On the other hand, the risks of behavioural manipulation must be considered, as we try to
160 provide a meaningful and effective level of transparency of data and algorithms.

161 **4.3 Blended identity**

162 In shared, sentient XR spaces, where multiple users contribute to a continuous flow of biometric,
163 behavioural, and expressive data, the resulting information landscape becomes inherently collective.
164 Feedback from the environment is no longer directed solely at individuals but emerges from and
165 responds to the aggregated presence of many. In this context, identity risks becoming a shared
166 construct—blended and shaped by distributed inputs, including eye contact, voice inflexions, and
167 avatar behaviours. Such collective dynamics can foster deeper social connections and immersive co-
168 experiences, offering new pathways for identity exploration. Yet, they also introduce a liminal state
169 where the boundaries of selfhood blur, and personal agency may be diluted within algorithmically
170 mediated interactions. When the feedback loop is co-authored, we must ask not only where “I” ends
171 and “we” begin, but whether this convergence may ultimately redefine what it means to be an
172 individual at all.

173 The long-term implications of this could manifest in psychological enmeshment, surveillance-
174 enabled behavioural nudging, or even avatar-based manipulation. The critical spirit, the positivity of
175 solitude and of not being fully integrated into the system become relevant as values: the preservation
176 of the possibility of opting out and the question of consent in general, which are often not resolved
177 even in the offline world, find a new field of application here.

178 **4.4 The hyperreal and the avatar as simulacrum**

179 It could be possible to highlight a pattern unfolding that (Baudrillard, 1994) would have considered
180 inevitable: the progressive replacement of the real by the hyperreal. In XR, identities are not merely
181 represented but simulated with such fidelity and personalisation that they become more real than real,
182 shaping user behaviour and self-perception more strongly than their physical lives. The avatar, once a
183 vessel for exploration, could become a simulacrum: no longer pointing to a stable referent in the real
184 world, but generating identity in a recursive loop through the virtual system. As users engage with
185 these feedback loops, navigating environments tailored to their biometrics, echoing their past actions
186 and predicted futures, one must ask: is the avatar expressing the self, or is the system scripting the
187 self through the avatar? Once again, literacy and a focus on transparency can be powerful weapons to
188 manage these risks, together with strategies to create an unambiguous continuity of meaning between
189 online and offline, as in (Floridi, 2015) work, that do not leave anyone behind (think of the
190 hikikomori phenomenon and similar situations of discomfort and disconnection/hyperconnection).

191 If we are to use XR as a laboratory for identity, we must design it with friction, ambiguity, and
192 contradiction—essential ingredients of human growth. Without them, we risk losing the boundary not
193 between virtual and physical, but between authenticity and simulation. And it is in this liminal space,
194 not between screens and senses but between ontology and code, where the future of human identity
195 will be negotiated.

196 **4.5 Regulating the new liminal spaces shaping human identity**

197 In the absence of a common body of laws for virtual worlds and avatars, we must resort to legislation
198 which is in force within different domains. The use of AI-driven avatars, which come close to the
199 concept of the digital shadow of a human being, can nowadays face legal challenges from different

200 perspectives. First of all, the amount of personal data that should be collected is vast and includes
201 biometric data and other kinds of sensitive information, the use of which is highly regulated in some
202 countries, e.g. by the European GDPR. While the use of such data may be lawful and indeed desired
203 within some fields of application, such as healthcare treatment, all the commercial areas, like
204 entertainment and marketing, are much more problematic in terms of a lawful basis for the
205 processing of personal information.

206 Even if ideally the regulatory set-up should be harmonised globally, an international legal framework
207 for virtual worlds (also referred to as ‘law of the Metaverse’) does not exist. If we look back at the
208 early years of cyberspace, similar considerations were made by scholars and enthusiasts, which have
209 not resulted in a commonly agreed-upon framework, mainly due to different views among
210 stakeholders (Qin et al., 2025).

211 **5 New challenges and future scenarios: a research proposal**

212 **5.1 Identity experimentation made affordable**

213 XR avatars can enable users to challenge traditional gender/racial constructs, creating spaces for
214 marginalised groups to explore alternative identities safely. On the other hand, AI let us collect data
215 and brainstorm on it, letting us create a “rationale” of the identity: will this be a new form of self-
216 discovery and awareness?

217 **5.2 Legal personality and avatars**

218 (Cheong, 2022) argues that avatars equipped with AI, capable of learning from their human users to
219 make decisions, manage contracts, and supervise others in the virtual worlds, could in the future be
220 considered endowed with legal personality in virtual environments. This would grant them rights like
221 property and personality rights: the growing debate around granting rights to highly autonomous AI
222 agents may shape this discussion. What would it mean, legally and ethically?

223 **5.3 Is identity in XR truly ‘liberated’, or are we building new cages with different aesthetics?**

224 To what extent does identity exploration in XR environments genuinely expand individual agency, or
225 does it merely replace existing social constraints with novel, technologically mediated limitations?
226 Can avatars be used not just to escape reality, but to reshape it? As Oscar Wilde said, ‘Give him a
227 mask and he will tell you the truth’. This balance between self-expression and self-delusion should be
228 explored both as a challenge and as a tool with deep psychological and societal influences. What are
229 the implications? And how can we protect the information about our personality that the data
230 provided by our choices and interactions can show to the platforms we use?

231 **5.4 If we allow machines to design our virtual selves, whose values are we encoding in our 232 identity?**

233 How can we ‘open the black box ’to align what we can call identity generators to the values we want
234 to preserve? And on the other hand, what if there were a way to make the biases explicit through XR-
235 mediated interactions, and thus raise awareness and find new ways to overcome them?

236 **5.5 What might be lost when the avatar becomes more ‘relevant’ than the body?**

237 How can we define metrics to make these reproductions valid, and the data connected to them
238 trustworthy? What lines should we draw to distinguish between the real and the made-up identity? Is

239 there a clear threshold or a blurred boundary? How can we test it? What strategies for ensuring
240 continuity between online and offline life (Floridi, 2015), should be adopted?

241 **5.6 AI-avatars as means for literacy and awareness**

242 Could avatar-mediated immersive experiences become a vehicle for literacy and enhanced awareness
243 not only about the self but also about personal and societal issues? How should we modulate the
244 language we use to talk about these phenomena? What will be the differences in interaction here?

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318 **Conflict of Interest**

319 *The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial*
320 *relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.*

Extending Human–Co-Bot Interaction with XR Assistants

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Industry 5.0 prioritizes human-centric technologies that enhance, rather than replace, human
4 labor, particularly in complex manufacturing environments. This paper investigates the use of
5 XR-based intelligent agents, designed to support operators working alongside collaborative
6 robots (co-bots) in industrial settings. We review current human–robot collaboration practices to
7 identify limitations and opportunities for operator augmentation. Building on these insights, we
8 propose an extended interaction framework that integrates the Smart Factory metaverse, digital
9 twins, and embodied AI assistants to enable scalable collaboration across multiple workstations.
10 To support this framework, we present a prototype of a Smart Factory featuring a digital twin
11 environment and explore the integration of embodied conversational agents (ECAs) for real-time,
12 personalized operator assistance. Our review of current uses of ECAs in manufacturing highlights
13 key use cases, enabling technologies, and prevalent challenges. We conclude with a discussion
14 of the technical and human-centered considerations for deploying adaptive, interactive systems
15 within industrial metaverse environments.

16 **Keywords:** Industrial Metaverse, Smart Factory, Human-Computer Interaction, Digital Twin, Collaborative Robots, Cyber-physical
17 Systems

1 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

18 Modern manufacturing is increasingly complex, with operators managing advanced machinery and
19 robotics in dynamic environments. A comprehensive review by Longo et al. (2017) highlights that
20 agent-based technologies could enable flexible, decentralized control, improving operator efficiency
21 and autonomy (Pulikottil et al., 2023; Kumar and Lee, 2022). Advanced human-computer interaction (HCI)
22 tools enhance operators' ability to plan, optimize, and control systems, while continuous training supports
23 their efficiency and well-being.

24 This paper explores human–robot collaboration use cases to identify limitations and proposes an
25 extended interaction framework integrating the Smart Factory Metaverse and embodied AI assistants

26 to overcome these challenges. Section 2 examines operator use cases, including a digital twin, to inform
27 the framework. Section 3 presents a mini-review of the application of embodied conversational agents
28 (ECAs) in manufacturing, a Smart Factory prototype, and a large language model (LLM)-powered ECA.
29 We conclude with a research roadmap for deploying this framework in industrial metaverse settings.

30 **1.1 The Smart factory, Cyber-Physical Systems, and Digital Twins**

31 Modern manufacturing leverages cyber-physical systems (CPS) and digital twins (DTs) to enhance
32 efficiency and operator training. CPS integrates computing, control, and communication with physical
33 environments, while DTs simulate real-world processes for optimization. Essential for their functionality
34 is real-time data exchange, often facilitated by Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture
35 (OPC UA), a platform-independent standard enabling secure, reliable interoperability across industrial
36 applications like Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) and high-performance VR/AR systems. Key
37 technologies for building industrial metaverse DTs include AI, VR, high-speed networks like private
38 5G, and computing power, ensuring dynamic simulation and operator support in smart factories.

39 **1.2 Human-Machine Interfaces in the Smart Factory**

40 A review by Kumar and Lee (2022) identifies advanced interaction modalities—gaze, voice, gesture,
41 tactile, and haptic—enhancing smart factory functions like operation, management, maintenance, and
42 cybersecurity. These interfaces require robust cybersecurity and human-centered design to ensure usability
43 from cognitive and physical perspectives. Generative AI transforms embodied conversational agents (ECAs)
44 in VR/AR, offering immersive training through human-like interactions (Bellucci et al., 2025). ECAs
45 with situational awareness improve engagement and learning outcomes (Kán et al., 2023). Integrated
46 with digital twins and AI, ECAs support human-robot collaboration, real-time assistance, and process
47 optimization (Zhang et al., 2024). The industrial metaverse, powered by digital twins, enables scenario
48 simulation and decision-making. However, challenges remain in deploying human digital twins (HDTs),
49 including standardization, reliability, data accuracy, and ethical concerns such as privacy (Wang et al.,
50 2024a).

51 **1.3 Integrating XR agents in co-bot interaction**

52 The primary aim of this paper is to investigate how XR agents, specifically embodied assistants
53 and conversational agents, can support operators of collaborative robots within industrial metaverse
54 environments. We focus on their potential to enhance human–robot collaboration by improving usability,
55 reducing cognitive load, and enabling more natural, multimodal interaction in smart factory settings.
56 We present a concise review of current implementations and empirical evaluations of XR agents in
57 manufacturing, identifying key use cases, underlying technologies, and remaining challenges. By
58 synthesizing insights from this review, we propose an extended interaction framework that integrates
59 digital twins, LLM-powered assistants, and XR interfaces to augment operator roles in increasingly
60 complex and distributed production environments.

2 THE OPERATOR 5.0 AND THE CO-BOT DIGITAL TWIN USE CASE

61 **2.1 Use Cases and Operators Augmentations**

62 In the framework of Industry 5.0, co-bots represent a significant advancement as they extend human
63 capabilities by assisting with physically and cognitively demanding tasks. This support enables human

64 operators to focus on more rewarding and engaging activities, which is particularly beneficial for individuals
65 with physical limitations (e.g., Kildal et al. (2019)) or ageing workers (e.g., Rossato et al. (2021a)).
66 Moreover, Extended Reality (XR) technologies make it possible to hybridize the workspace by integrating a
67 digital twin of the collaborative robotic arm, allowing users to interact with it in more or less direct ways. As
68 a result, the operative space of the worker expands beyond the physical boundaries of the workstation: users
69 can access digital information not immediately visible in the physical world, interact with the cobot's digital
70 twin in the virtual environment, and produce effects in the physical world. Understanding the impact of such
71 technologies on the user is essential to designing interaction modalities that align with both user needs and
72 organizational goals. For instance, evidence from research shows a preference for direct interaction with the
73 collaborative robot that extends also to virtual environments. In a study comparing direct manipulation of a
74 virtual robotic arm versus indirect control via a handheld controller, Nenna et al. (2023a) observed higher
75 cognitive load in the controller-mediated condition. Moreover, most participants expressed a preference for
76 direct interaction. The facilitation effect of direct control was further confirmed in AR-based interaction
77 with the robotic arm's digital twin. Grego et al. (2024) found that the AR interface was perceived as more
78 usable and less fatiguing than the dedicated touch-screen interface, with participants also reporting higher
79 perceived accuracy and speed. Notably, the sense of presence—defined as the subjective feeling of being
80 immersed in the virtual environment—also plays a critical role. Higher levels of presence were associated
81 with faster completion times in a virtual pick-and-place task, whether the cobot was controlled directly or
82 via a controller (Nenna et al., 2023b).

83 In addition, research has indicated a positive attitude towards collaborative robots (cobots) designed
84 for operators' work augmentation: both younger and older employees display a high level of acceptance
85 towards cobots (Rossato et al., 2021b).

86 Although these findings stem from laboratory settings, they clearly point to the benefits of direct
87 interaction with both physical and digital versions of robotic systems. These benefits include improved
88 interaction efficiency and perceived effectiveness. Moreover, the studies highlight the importance of
89 addressing the unique characteristics of virtual environments—particularly the sense of presence—as
90 key factors influencing workload and overall user experience. Additionally, they stress the importance of
91 carefully designing the collaborative system features.

92 **2.2 Digital Twin of a Sentient Collaborative Robot**

93 The concept of the digital twin has advanced from mere static replication toward more interactive,
94 adaptive, and human-centered systems that exemplify the collaborative principles of Industry 5.0. Recent
95 developments underscore the utilization of digital twins not solely as simulators of robotic behavior, but
96 also as agents proficient in real-time co-regulation with human users.

97 Other contributions have proposed teleoperation frameworks utilizing virtual reality (VR) and real-time
98 eye-tracking technologies, which will enable virtual robots in the near future to interpret attentional
99 focus and subsequently adjust their assistance or information delivery accordingly (Nenna et al., 2023c).
100 This conceptualization enhances operational precision and promotes the mutual intelligibility of human
101 and machine intentions within shared task environments. Similarly, studies on virtualized human–robot
102 collaboration suggest that immersive environments can enhance task coordination and UX by adjusting to
103 users' cognitive workload and attentional patterns. Evidence from experimental studies on physiologically
104 adaptive systems leveraging metrics such as pupil dilation and gaze entropy has demonstrated predictive
105 capabilities for workload perception during robotic tasks (Wu et al., 2020; Fournier et al., 2024).
106 Furthermore, the incorporation of real-time physiological data into human–robot interaction paradigms

107 has demonstrated the capacity to foster more intuitive and collaborative industrial environments, wherein
108 robots proficiently 'interpret' and react to human cognitive and psychological states. Moreover, research
109 suggests that employing machine learning methodologies for the detection and monitoring of operator
110 fatigue can substantially improve the sustainability of prolonged human–robot collaboration (Lambay et al.,
111 2024). Previous research corroborate the potential of digital twins to function as physiologically responsive
112 entities that adjust robotic behavior in response to the user's state, thereby enhancing the sustainability of
113 long-term collaboration (Baratta et al., 2024). Such insights highlight the relevance of systems that are
114 informed by physiological data, in which biometric feedback (e.g., eye-tracking, heart activity) can be
115 utilized to enhance adaptive interfaces. Research indicates that these adaptive systems improve accuracy,
116 mitigate cognitive strain, and facilitate a more rapid resumption of tasks following interruptions. Supporting
117 this perspective, studies have further demonstrated the significance of incorporating both implicit indicators
118 (such as psychophysiological measures) and explicit indicators (such as self-reports) of mental workload
119 within industrial contexts. This highlights their complementary roles in assessing human-technology
120 interaction and informing the design of adaptive support systems (Mingardi et al., 2020).

121 The emerging paradigm of sentient collaborative robots indicates a transition from mere automation
122 to empathetic augmentation, wherein digital twins serve as cognitive collaborators that anticipate needs,
123 alleviate mental stress/overload, and maintain operator engagement across dynamic manufacturing
124 environments (Nikolaidis et al., 2017).

3 EXTENDING THE RESEARCH WITH XR AGENTS

125 Previous research has mainly focused on improving collaborative robot interactions at single workstations,
126 emphasizing direct interaction and digital twins for operator support. This approach, however, restricts the
127 investigation of multi-agent, cross-island collaborations crucial to modern manufacturing systems. The
128 Smart Factory Lab offers a unique modular environment to integrate collaborative robots, digital twins, and
129 AI agents across multiple production stations. This infrastructure enables the exploration of more dynamic
130 and scalable human-robot collaborations, addressing both task efficiency and the socio-cognitive aspects of
131 operator interactions in distributed smart manufacturing environments.

3.1 Minireview on the application of ECAs in manufacturing

133 This mini review was conducted through a structured search of the Scopus database, focusing on embodied
134 conversational agents (ECAs) used within industrial metaverse contexts. The initial query targeted peer-
135 reviewed articles and conference papers using terms such as “embodied conversational agent,” “virtual
136 assistant,” “avatar-based agent”, “avatar,” “virtual agent,” and “digital twin,” combined with “industry 4.0,”
137 “smart manufacturing,” and “industrial metaverse.”

138 The search yielded 87 records. From these, we applied three exclusion criteria: (1) exclusion of works
139 lacking a real implementation of an ECA or empirical evaluation (59 papers excluded), (2) exclusion of
140 studies published before 2020 (5 papers excluded), and (3) exclusion of works unrelated to manufacturing
141 or industrial application contexts (9 papers excluded).

142 The final corpus consisted of 14 studies. Each paper was manually examined to confirm its relevance and
143 was categorized based on use cases, platforms used, and technological components. A BibTeX database
144 and structured LaTeX table were created to document the included studies.

145 In Table 1, we present the results of a review on the application of ECAs in manufacturing, categorized
146 by use cases and including keywords representing the technologies used.

Table 1. Representative studies of embodied conversational agents (ECAs) in different industrial metaverse use cases.

Use Case	Papers	Technologies / Platforms
Training Simulation	Kang and Jo (2024), Li et al. (2022), Alpala et al. (2022), Ramadhani et al. (2023)	Unity, Unreal, MRTK toolkit, VR headset, Simulation Engine, speech-to-text (STT) and text-to-speech (TTS), Multi-User System, Avatar System
Remote Maintenance	Oppermann et al. (2023)	VR headset, WebRTC, Avatar Interaction, Cloud Remote Rendering
Human-Robot Collaboration	Fan et al. (2025), Li et al. (2023), Li and Yang (2021), Niiyama et al. (2023), Xu et al. (2025)	LLMs, Chain of Thought, Fine-Tuned BERT Model, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Task-Oriented Response Model Generation, Semantic Web, Motion Capture Systems, Multi-Modal Large Models (MLMs), Cyber-Physical-Social Systems (CPSSs), Cloud Computing, Embodied Perception and Interaction, Scheduling Algorithms
Monitoring Supervision	Barron-Lugo et al. (2025)	Digital Avatars, cloud services, Virtual Containers
Digital Interaction Twin	Bellalouna and Puljiz (2023), Chen et al. (2024), Gautam et al. (2025)	Digital Twin, Multiplayer Avatar interactions, Unreal Engine, 3D Reconstruction, digital representations of robots, Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), Multi-Agent Framework, LLMs, Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)

147 3.2 The integration of XR Assistants

148 The integration of XR agents and assistants into manufacturing signifies a major advancement in operator
 149 augmentation within the Industry 5.0 framework. Unlike traditional automation that prioritizes efficiency
 150 over human interaction, these assistants act as intuitive collaborators, overlaying interactive guidance (3D
 151 models, animations, or text) on physical workspaces to enhance workers' confidence and precision in
 152 complex assembly tasks.

153 Current state-of-the-art (SoTA) research underscores the role of embodied agents in reducing cognitive
 154 load and improving situational awareness. For instance, (Lataifeh et al., 2025) proposed a multimodal
 155 framework that combines large language models (LLMs) like GPT-4o with computer vision to create
 156 intelligent virtual agents (IVAs) capable of navigating physical spaces and providing adaptive guidance
 157 based on real-time scene understanding, which makes the XR agent productive in industrial setting.

158 **Architecture:** ECAs typically follow a modular and hybrid architecture, combining components from
 159 natural language processing, speech, vision, and robotics. At the core, LLMs like BERT or GPT
 160 variants manage language understanding and generation. For instance, Bot-X employs a two-layer neural
 161 network with Softmax regression (Li and Yang, 2021), while Max uses a fine-tuned BERT model with a
 162 Client–Server architecture and RESTful APIs for scalability (Li et al., 2023). XR components include
 163 VR/MR headsets (e.g., HoloLens 2, Meta Quest 2/3), gaming engine((e.g., unity, unreal), motion capture
 164 systems and multi-agent system. For multimodal interaction, ECAs utilize speech recognition technologies
 165 and visual perception tools for gesture and facial recognition. Cloud computing platform, like Azure,
 166 ensure data synchronization and real-time digital twin visualization, as seen in the LLM-integrated digital
 167 twin study (Gautam et al., 2025).

168 **Use Cases:** XR assistants support diverse applications in smart manufacturing, aligning with Industry
 169 5.0's human-centric paradigm. For example, remote maintenance empowers experts to address machine

170 malfunctions remotely, reducing costly downtime and travel. By providing real-time guidance through
171 digital twins, XR avatars enhance operational efficiency (Oppermann et al., 2023). A notable example is
172 the Max, a natural language-enabled virtual assistant, which uses a fine-tuned BERT model and human-
173 inspired conversation strategies to facilitate intuitive human robot collaboration in industrial settings (Li
174 et al., 2023). Training simulation is a good use case to reduce training costs. By simulating real-world
175 industrial scenarios, XR assistants help operators to improve adaptability and confidence in handling
176 complex machinery or processes. A VR-powered metaverse framework for smart factories illustrates this,
177 using digital twins and avatars to deliver engaging, collaborative training experiences (Alpala et al., 2022).
178 Monitoring supervision ensures real-time oversight of industrial processes. The Davatar method creates
179 digital avatars to monitor and interact with containerized applications. (Barron-Lugo et al., 2025). One
180 example of digital twin interaction is roboAvatar, which uses IFC-based digital twins for construction
181 robotics (Chen et al., 2024).

182 **Limitations:** Despite these advancements, challenges remain in deploying ECAs in real-time industrial
183 settings. Latency poses significant concerns. Cloud-based LLMs and XR rendering cause delays, as seen
184 in the remote collaboration system (Oppermann et al., 2023). Edge deployment is limited by hardware
185 constraints (Gautam et al., 2025). Privacy issues arise when handling sensitive data. Davatar's use
186 of unencrypted HTTP and Max's lack of robust security highlight risks (Barron-Lugo et al., 2025; Li
187 et al., 2023). Hardware limitation could cause synchronization problem. In the remote maintenance
188 prototype, hardware limits real-time digital twin updates (Oppermann et al., 2023). Additionally, complex
189 interfaces can overwhelm non-technical users and long XR using makes people feel tiring, which lowering
190 effectiveness and usability (Bellalouna and Puljiz, 2023). Therefore, future XR assistants need low-latency
191 edge computing, secure protocols and intuitive interfaces to ensure Industry 5.0 integration.

Figure 1. Co-bot prototype in AR with an embodied AI-powered assistant in AR (Nenna et al., 2023a).

4 CHALLENGES AND DISCUSSION

192 This study proposes an extended interaction framework that integrates the Smart Factory metaverse with
193 embodied AI assistants, aiming to overcome the limitations of current human–co-bot applications within the
194 context of Industry 5.0. The findings indicate that direct and intuitive interaction, supported by digital twins
195 (DTs) and embodied conversational agents (ECAs), improves user experience, enhances task efficiency, and
196 fosters a greater sense of presence. Nonetheless, implementing such systems in real-world environments
197 remains challenging due to persistent issues such as system latency, privacy concerns, and the need to
198 establish user trust. Another important area that warrants further attention is the facilitation of social

199 interaction among operators in the industrial metaverse, which is closely connected to the characteristics of
200 the devices used for access and engagement (Fernández-Caramés and Fraga-Lamas, 2024).

201 4.1 Trust and Distrust in AI Systems

202 Trust in AI plays a central role in the acceptance and adoption of intelligent systems in industrial
203 settings (Salam et al., 2021). It is a multifaceted and dynamic construct influenced by a wide range of
204 factors. According to Kaplan et al. (2023) they can be broadly categorized into human-related, AI-related,
205 and context-related dimensions. Human-related factors include the operator's level of competence and
206 understanding of the AI system, domain expertise, and personality traits (e.g., extroversion), which have
207 been shown to affect the willingness to collaborate with intelligent systems. AI-related factors pertain to
208 system performance, such as reliability, and use of human-centered language. Notably, anthropomorphic
209 AI agents have been found to increase trust. Finally, contextual factors further shape this relationship,
210 encompassing team dynamics (e.g., the length of time a team has worked together) and situational variables,
211 such as the perceived level of risk of the task at hand (Kaplan et al., 2023). Together, these elements interact
212 to influence the degree of trust a user places in an AI system.

213 Importantly, trust in AI is not static. It fluctuates in response to task complexity, perceived changes in
214 system performance, and broader contextual variables (Wang et al., 2024b). Alongside trust, the concept of
215 distrust has emerged as a significant factor. Specifically, distrust is not merely the absence of trust, rather, it
216 encompasses users' suspicion toward AI systems and fears of negative consequences if the system performs
217 unreliably (Govers et al., 2025; Kaplan et al., 2023). Distrust becomes particularly salient when users
218 interact with anthropomorphized AI agents, which can exert persuasive influence (Gefen et al., 2025). A
219 key emerging issue related to trust in the AI system is over-reliance, as research has shown that individuals
220 tend to accept and incorporate AI responses without being fully aware of it (Jakesch et al., 2023).

221 **Explainability and Mental Models:** A significant contributor to both trust and distrust is the opacity
222 of most AI systems. These systems often operate as "black boxes," offering limited insight into how
223 outputs are generated (Hassija et al., 2024). This lack of transparency and explainability complicates
224 users' ability to form accurate mental models of AI functioning. While researchers have proposed various
225 explanation strategies, there is still no consensus on what information is helpful for users to grasp the
226 system functioning, nor how it should be presented. Endsley (2023) emphasizes that effective explanations
227 must be context-specific and acknowledges the intrinsic challenge of translating brittle algorithmic logic
228 into human-understandable narratives. Moreover, once users form a mental model of how an AI system
229 works, they are often reluctant to revise it, even in the face of contradictory evidence. These reflections
230 point out the key challenge of designing systems that foster calibrated trust, thereby enabling users to rely
231 on AI and maintain critical oversight. To do that, adaptive explainability tailored to users' mental models
232 and contexts should be sought and experimented.

233 4.2 Digital Twins and Social Dynamics at Work

234 Much of the current research on Digital Twin (DT) technologies has concentrated on individual
235 interactions, evaluating their impact on performance, cognitive workload, and user satisfaction. However,
236 this perspective overlooks the inherently social nature of the workplace, which is shaped by continuous
237 interactions, informal exchanges, and collaborative dynamics among workers. While prior studies
238 have explored how the introduction of physical collaborative robots influences social dynamics within
239 workgroups (Cheon et al., 2022a,b), the impact of DT systems on peer-to-peer relationships, both in
240 physical and virtual environments, remains largely unexamined.

241 **AI Systems as Social Partners:** Emerging evidence shows that workers often interact with and refer to
242 AI-powered industrial machines as if they were colleagues, even when these systems lack anthropomorphic
243 features (Süße et al., 2023). This raises important questions about how the design of AI-based systems
244 might influence social perceptions and team cohesion. For example, Crivelli et al. (2025) suggests that
245 integrating features that express internal states, such as facial expressions or responsive gestures, could
246 strengthen human-robot rapport, enhancing both trust and perceived collaboration quality. Building on this
247 idea, Nicora et al. (2023) has developed collaborative robots coupled with virtual agents with verbal and
248 non-verbal social skills, to increase their likelihood of being perceived as social partners.

249 **4.3 Role of XR in Team Building**

250 As AI systems become more embedded in knowledge-intensive and collaborative workplaces, concerns
251 have emerged about their potential to diminish opportunities for informal social interactions. Such
252 interactions are essential for building team cohesion and fostering spontaneous innovation. Technologies
253 such as extended reality (XR) have been proposed as a way to recreate casual, serendipitous encounters in
254 virtual environments and preserve the social fabric of work. The results of the minireview shows the recent
255 adaptation and emerging use cases of XR technologies with LLM-powered ECAs in different areas of the
256 industrial metaverse.

257 Despite these developments, existing research remains largely centered on dyadic interactions between
258 individual workers and AI systems, overlooking how such technologies affect broader team dynamics
259 and social connectedness. As AI and DT systems become more embedded in collaborative settings, it is
260 essential to investigate their influence not only on individual performance, but also on the social structures
261 and relationships that underpin effective teamwork.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

262 Several open challenges remain in the effort to integrate AI and DT systems into Industry 5.0 in a human-
263 centric manner. There is a need to design systems that support meaningful social interaction within the
264 industrial metaverse, particularly through interfaces that are intuitive and socially responsive (Fernández-
265 Caramés and Fraga-Lamas, 2024). Additionally, developing AI systems that foster appropriate levels of
266 trust while remaining explainable and transparent is a critical objective. Lastly, future research should
267 continue to examine how these technologies influence not only productivity but also the collaborative and
268 social dimensions of work. Addressing these concerns will be crucial for creating adaptive, inclusive, and
269 trustworthy systems aligned with the principles of Industry 5.0.

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AI-Powered Metaverse: AGI and the Path to Ethical Superintelligence

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ABSTRACT

The convergence of advanced artificial intelligence with immersive metaverse platforms presents unprecedented opportunities and ethical challenges. This position paper examines how the emergence of artificial general intelligence (AGI) within AI-powered virtual worlds could be guided toward ethical superintelligence—ultra-capable AI systems aligned with human values. A multi-faceted governance framework is proposed to foster the responsible development of AI in the metaverse. Key components include a Global Cloud Consensus for worldwide AI governance, a Universal Interpreter to enable interoperability and cultural inclusivity, an AI Trust Layer to secure safety and transparency, and a dynamic Hyper Policy approach for adaptive regulation. Drawing on expertise in metaverse innovation and AI ethics, this work outlines a path forward to harness AI's benefits in virtual environments while rigorously addressing risks. The goal is to cultivate an AI-powered metaverse that upholds human rights, promotes global collaboration, and ultimately paves the way for a superintelligent future that is safe and beneficial for all.

Keywords: AI Ethics, Metaverse, Superintelligence, Governance, Interoperability, Trust, Policy

INTRODUCTION

The term metaverse, originally coined in Neal Stephenson's novel *Snow Crash*, refers to a persistent virtual world merging digital and physical reality. Once a science-fiction concept, the metaverse is rapidly becoming an emerging reality due to advances in extended reality and networked virtual environments. Modern definitions characterize the metaverse as a post-reality universe that is perpetually shared by users, blending physical and virtual spaces into a single immersive experience. Technology taxonomies highlight the metaverse's key components and open challenges, including infrastructure, avatars, digital assets, and interactive content. An increasingly important component across these facets is artificial intelligence: from intelligent virtual agents and generative content systems to personalized experiences driven by machine

learning. As metaverse applications expand, so does the integration of AI, making questions of ethical governance increasingly urgent.

While today's metaverse AI remains narrow in scope, the trajectory of AI development points toward greater autonomy and generality. Experts anticipate the advent of artificial general intelligence (AI with human-level cognitive abilities) within this century. Beyond AGI lies the prospect of superintelligence, a level of AI intellect far surpassing humans in virtually all domains. To date, such advanced AI remains hypothetical; no concrete real-world example of an AGI or superintelligent agent exists. Nonetheless, it is prudent to consider governance now, before these possibilities materialize. If powerful AI agents eventually become embedded in our virtual worlds, they could profoundly influence societal norms, individual behaviors, and even governance processes within and beyond the metaverse. This presents a profound ethical challenge: How can we ensure that increasingly intelligent AI systems operating in immersive environments remain aligned with human values and serve the public good? Researchers in AI safety and ethics have emphasized the critical importance of value alignment and control for advanced AI. Even contemporary AI systems require governance to prevent bias, abuse, and harm; with AGI or superintelligence, the stakes will be vastly higher. Proactively establishing frameworks for responsible AI behavior in the metaverse can lay critical groundwork for managing future superintelligent AI in society.

This position paper operates at the frontier of intelligence research, where concrete examples are lacking and scenarios remain largely speculative. It is recognized that the metaverse offers both a potential proving ground and a microcosm of the broader challenges of AI ethics. Within virtual worlds, it may be possible to implement constrained environments or "sandbox" conditions to test advanced AI behaviors safely. Insights from such simulations could inform real-world AI governance. However, it must be stressed that the metaverse is not merely a sandbox; it is a real, consequential environment with human participants and stakes. Any failure to control AI in the metaverse could cause genuine harm to users, such as AI-induced psychological or economic damage, and foreshadow larger failures outside of it. Therefore, proactive governance in the metaverse is an essential stepping stone toward global AI governance. By instilling ethical guidelines, oversight mechanisms, and alignment techniques in today's virtual platforms, a culture and infrastructure can be created that scales as AI grows more capable. In effect, the metaverse can serve as a controlled environment to refine approaches for achieving ethical superintelligence, ensuring that when AI does reach and exceed human-level cognition, it does so embedded in a framework of accountability and humanity-first principles.

GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORKS FOR AN AI-POWERED METaverse

Governing AI in a borderless, immersive environment requires innovative approaches that blend technical, ethical, and policy strategies. Four interlocking components are proposed for a

comprehensive metaverse AI governance framework: Global Cloud Consensus, Universal Interpreter, AI Trust Layer, and an adaptive Hyper Policy approach. These concepts collectively address the needs for global coordination, interoperability, safety assurance, and agile policymaking in the context of AI-driven virtual worlds.

Global Cloud Consensus: Toward Unified AI Governance

One of the greatest challenges in AI governance is achieving international consensus on norms and regulations. The metaverse, by nature, is a global platform where users and AI agents interact across jurisdictions. The Global Cloud Consensus model is proposed as a cloud-based, collaborative governance framework that unifies ethical AI standards worldwide. The vision of Global Cloud Consensus is to centralize and refine disparate AI governance frameworks into a single universal model. In practice, this would involve an alliance of stakeholders—technology companies, international organizations, governments, academia, and civil society—contributing to a shared set of guidelines and rules for AI behavior in virtual environments. These standards would be hosted and disseminated via an online platform so that metaverse providers and AI developers around the world have access to up-to-date best practices and policies.

The Global Cloud Consensus acts as an aggregator and synthesizer of existing ethical frameworks, distilling them into a master governance structure for AI. Rather than reinventing governance from scratch, it would build on precedents and principles already established across the world, such as those from the OECD and UNESCO. The consensus process would facilitate dialogue to resolve conflicts and continuously update the global standard, aiming for the highest common ethical denominator. Accountability, transparency, and alignment are key attributes: AI systems must be traceable, developers held responsible for violations, actions by AI must be auditable, and all behaviors must be consistent with core values reflecting fundamental human rights and well-being.

Universal Interpreter: Enabling Interoperability and Inclusivity

A healthy metaverse will consist of many interoperable platforms and AI systems, developed by different organizations and catering to diverse cultures. In such a heterogeneous ecosystem, enforcing common governance is challenging. The Universal Interpreter is introduced as an AI system or protocol that translates and mediates between different AI models, platforms, and human users. Its role is to ensure that a shared ethical framework is interpreted uniformly across varied contexts, serving as the common language of governance in the metaverse so that, regardless of an AI agent's origin or a user's background, ethical rules carry the same meaning and weight everywhere.

The Universal Interpreter bridges user preferences and AI policies across virtual platforms, facilitating communication, and maintaining consistency of ethical norms and safety settings. It also provides observability, monitoring AI behavior across embodiments and ensuring classification and contextualization of AI actions in terms of the shared ethical framework. If unknown or unrecognized AI models attempt to operate, the Interpreter can flag them for scrutiny, adding a layer of security. This enables the ethical framework to be applied uniformly

and transparently, reducing the risk of governance gaps as people and AI interact across interconnected virtual worlds.

AI Trust Layer: Protecting Safety and Transparency

Effective governance demands real-time enforcement and monitoring. An AI Trust Layer within the metaverse's technical stack is proposed as a dedicated layer of software and services that continuously oversees AI actions for compliance and safety. This layer monitors the behavior of AI agents, intervenes or alerts when policies are breached, and provides users and administrators with transparency into AI decision-making.

The AI Trust Layer could employ automated auditors, immutable logging technologies, and user-facing controls and explanation tools. Users should be able to query AI decisions and receive clear explanations, fostering trust and providing feedback for policy adjustments. On the safety side, fail-safes are incorporated to prevent harm; if an AI agent exhibits dangerous behavior, the Trust Layer could shut it down or quarantine it from the wider environment. By enforcing rules and providing continuous assurance, the Trust Layer ensures that AI systems remain accountable, understandable, and controllable in the day-to-day life of the metaverse.

Hyper Policy: Adaptive Governance at Scale

Any framework for AI governance must be able to adapt rapidly to technological evolution and new societal insights. Hyper Policy encapsulates an approach to policymaking that is agile, iterative, and driven by multi-stakeholder collaboration. Ethical guidelines and regulations governing AI are treated as living frameworks that evolve as needed. Feedback and revision loops, supported by data from the AI Trust Layer, enable quick assessment of emerging issues and updating of guidelines or technical standards. Collaboration across technologists, ethicists, policymakers, and community voices is necessary to create balanced and forward-looking policies.

Hyper Policy enables the governance process itself to scale with the metaverse, treating policies like a codebase that requires version control, testing, and deployment. The adaptive nature of Hyper Policy ensures that the pursuit of ethical superintelligence can keep pace with technological advancements, integrating new safety measures or ethical guidelines as needed.

DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

This position paper operates within the frontier of intelligence research, where no fully realized examples of superintelligent agents exist. While the metaverse may offer a space to experiment with governance frameworks, it is not simply a hypothetical sandbox; it is a real environment with significant ethical and societal stakes. Achieving global consensus is a formidable challenge due to political and cultural differences, and the pursuit of universal human values in

AI governance will always require sensitivity and adaptability. The concepts presented here are aspirational, aimed at stimulating dialogue and proactive preparation rather than offering after-the-fact solutions.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

Guiding an AI-powered metaverse toward ethical superintelligence is an immense challenge, but it is one that demands urgent and proactive effort. By combining global cooperation with technical innovation and a steadfast commitment to human-centric values, it is possible to make the future metaverse a space where advanced AI serves the public good. The frameworks proposed—Global Cloud Consensus, Universal Interpreter, AI Trust Layer, and Hyper Policy—provide a roadmap for aligning AI development with widely shared values, even as the frontier of intelligence rapidly evolves. Continued research, pilot projects, and global collaboration are needed to test and refine these ideas. The frontier of intelligence is before us, and now is the time to chart it responsibly.

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Session 2: Ethical AI, Responsible and Legal Metaverse Design

The Metaverse as an AI-powered Society of Control: Ethical Concerns on Autonomy, Self-determination and Surveillance

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Abstract

This paper explores the metaverse as an AI-powered extension of Gilles Deleuze's concept of 'societies of control', primarily focusing on its implications for autonomy, self-determination, and surveillance. Unlike traditional disciplinary institutions, the metaverse integrates power dynamics directly into its core through algorithmic modulation, behavioral tracking, and predictive analytics. By applying Deleuzian theory to AI-driven governance and digital capitalism, this study demonstrates how the metaverse could operate as an advanced form of control society, where user agency is constrained by gamification, data commodification, and AI-profiling. The research critically examines how the metaverse could fragment identity, transforming individuals into Deleuzian 'dividuals' whose actions are driven by AI interactions rather than self-determined decisions. Furthermore, it interrogates the metaverse's function as a surveillance apparatus that might extend beyond traditional oversight models, placing control into digital experiences through biometric tracking, behavioral nudging, and predictive policing. Ultimately, by analysing the metaverse through the lens of Deleuze's control societies, it aims to raise awareness of the relevant ethical challenges and offers some viable paths for escape.

1 Introduction

The evolution of digital environments has given rise to new forms of power and governance, fundamentally altering the manner individuals interact, express themselves, and experience autonomy. Drawing on Gilles Deleuze's concept of 'societies of control', this paper explores how the metaverse represents a shift from disciplinary enclosures to algorithmic modulation, where behavior is subtly shaped rather than overtly restricted. Unlike traditional institutions that impose authority through confinement, the metaverse integrates control into its infrastructure, embedding predictive analytics, AI-driven recommendations, and gamified incentives to steer user engagement. As a result, it does not function as a neutral arena for exploration but as a carefully engineered environment where power operates invisibly, making resistance increasingly complex.

This paper provides a novel contribution by applying Deleuzian theory to contemporary discussions on AI-driven governance, surveillance capitalism, and digital subjectivity in the metaverse. While previous studies have examined control societies and algorithmic power separately, this research bridges the gap by demonstrating how the metaverse can exemplify a hyper-advanced form of

Deleuzian control, where users are simultaneously surveilled, fragmented, and guided through imperceptible digital architectures. By interrogating whether emerging technologies offer genuine alternatives to centralised control or merely reconfigure existing power structures, this study advances current debates on digital self-determination, Artificial Intelligence (AI) governance, and potential pathways for resistance.

2 The Deleuzian Societies of Control

The theory of surveillance reflects the practice of supervision through expansive networks, employing various mechanisms including data collection and classification, access control, and interconnection. Simultaneously, it incorporates reactionary processes through feedback loops, making it an inextricable part of the social fabric. Surveillance is not merely a technological phenomenon but a profoundly political, social, and even legal one (Samatas, 2007). Scholars who have examined it have consistently underlined this dimension.

Jeremy Bentham (1995, 29) and Michel Foucault (1920) attributed to surveillance a physical and spatial dimension, embodied in panoptic structures and disciplinary environments. Later theorists, such as Kevin Haggerty and Richard Ericson (2000, 607), Shoshana Zuboff (2019), and Gilles Deleuze (1990), extended these analyses to digital surveillance societies, marking an evolution that departs from centralised, enclosed spaces and moves into the vast, decentralized world of digital networks. Deleuze, in particular, offers a crystallised perspective on these shifting surveillance mechanisms in his essay *Postscript on Societies of Control*, first published in 1990 in *L'Autre Journal*.

In three distinct sections, Deleuze does not merely define social control or describe its mechanisms but also proposes ways for subjects to resist it (Brusseau, 2020, 2). Taking Foucault's 'Discipline and Punish' as a starting point, he borrows the term 'control' from William Burroughs (Gontarski, 2020) and proceeds to outline the historical transition from what Foucault termed disciplinary societies to what Deleuze designated as societies of control. To clarify these distinctions, it is useful to juxtapose them with an earlier form of power: societies of sovereignty.

Before the 18th century, European societies operated under sovereign power, in which absolutism and repression reigned supreme. The law was synonymous with the will of the ruler, crime was an affront to authority, and punishment functioned as an act of vengeance, often targeting the body through public executions or brutal corporal punishment. However, resistance was relatively straightforward. Centralised power meant that opposition could be directed against the sovereign: the monarch. Furthermore, because punishments were severe, the public often sympathised with the punished, fostering solidarity among the oppressed. Economic regulation in these societies was minimal as long as production was taxed but largely controlled by the workers. These forms of societal organisation and power focused on the control over death.

Following Napoleon, societies underwent a transition. The shift did not eradicate sovereign power but rather restructured it in response to historical, economic, and political changes in the 19th and 20th centuries. Disciplinary societies emerged, characterised by a network of enclosed institutions that shaped individuals throughout their lives. The family, the school, the factory, the hospital, and the prison became environments where power was no longer concentrated in a singular ruler but dispersed across different entities that regulated individuals at every stage of their existence. The resistance needed to target all these different factors became harder. Capitalism, the dominant economic model of these societies, was centred on ownership and production. Institutions functioned

preventively, engaging in hierarchical surveillance to ensure that individuals adhered to social norms. Individuals were categorised and subjected to assessments of normality. A deviation from established norms did not result in outright punishment but in corrective treatment aimed at integrating the individual back into society and the mass. The goal was no longer control over death, as in sovereign societies, but control over life itself.

Deleuze likens these societies to moles, creatures that burrow into confined spaces, mirroring the spatial limitations imposed by disciplinary institutions. Within these structures, individuals became mere numbers, assigned identities based on space, surveillance, and classification. Even the mere possibility of being watched proved sufficient to regulate behavior.

The Second World War laid the groundwork for a new societal formation, namely one that moved beyond confinement into a more fluid and adaptive structure: the society of control. Though societies of control retain elements of disciplinary structures, they diverge in fundamental ways. Unlike the rigid enclosures of disciplinary societies, control societies are marked by constant movement, perpetual mobility, fluidity, continuous access, and permissive rather than prohibitive mechanisms (Haggerty and Ericson, 2020, 605-620). Subjects are granted apparent freedom but only if they conform to invisible norms embedded in digital infrastructures (Galloway, 2014). Rather than imposing direct, authoritative restrictions, societies of control function through modulation; forms of control that present themselves as expressions of individual freedom.

Deleuze describes this shift as the transition from disciplinary spaces to digitised, coded networks, where individuals exist not as unified subjects but as individuals, fragmented identities scattered across data points, behavioral profiles, and markets (Schroeder, 2016). The traditional mass has been replaced by a system of statistical samples, where capitalism no longer prioritises production but instead trades in influence, data, and pre-configured desires. The factory has been transformed into a decentralised network of businesses. The hospital operates through remote medical models that minimise doctor-patient interactions. Imprisonment is often replaced by alternative sentencing, including electronic surveillance. Education is no longer confined to the school but extends into lifelong learning models, integrated into corporate and state structures. In these Kafkaesque societies, where disciplinary societies were likened to moles, slow and methodical in their enclosed movements, control societies function like reptiles: flexible, adaptive, and agile. Access, rather than spatial confinement, becomes the new mechanism of power.

Deleuze does not offer a value judgment on these transitions (Dreyfus and Rainbow, 1982). He neither nostalgically favors disciplinary societies nor outright condemns control societies. Instead, he acknowledges that we are facing a new phenomenon and urges individuals, particularly the younger generation, to understand the system they are being forced to serve. Unlike earlier forms of power, where resistance took the form of confrontation, control societies demand new forms of resistance that adapt to the decentralized and fluid nature of power.

Deleuze highlights that fear and fatalism are unnecessary. Instead, he calls for the discovery of new weapons and novel tools that can disrupt, subvert, or bypass mechanisms of control. In a world where access replaces enclosure, where surveillance is predictive rather than reactive, and where power operates through networks rather than hierarchies, resistance must be equally fluid, equally adaptive, and equally decentralised.

As we move deeper into an era defined by AI-driven surveillance, big data, and algorithmic governance, Deleuze's analysis of control societies becomes increasingly relevant. Particularly, in the

metaverse, where identity is fragmented across platforms, behaviors are tracked in real time, and decisions are shaped by invisible forces, the culmination of control society mechanisms becomes clear. Understanding this shift is essential not only for theorising power in the digital age but also for imagining strategies of resistance in a world where control is omnipresent yet intangible.

3 Metaverse as a Society of Control

The metaverse represents a paradigm shift in governance and surveillance, potentially emerging as a novel type of control society. In it, power will no longer be imposed through rigid institutions but through fluid, data-driven modulation. It operates through continuous tracking and behavioral nudging, shaping digital experiences in real-time. AI-driven recommendation systems, predictive modeling, and gamified incentives replace direct coercion, subtly influencing user actions, in many cases, even without their explicit awareness and consent (Rouvroy, 2013, 157). As users navigate virtual environments, their behaviors, preferences, and even physiological responses can be tracked and analysed, allowing AI systems to dynamically adjust their experiences (Andrejevic, 2020, 18). This creates an environment of algorithmic governance where control is no longer external and overt but embedded within the infrastructure of virtual life itself. The result is a landscape of persistent reform, where users are not confined but rather guided by imperceptible forces that structure their interactions and choices.

At the heart of this transformation lies data capitalism, wherein the very essence of digital subjectivity, including thoughts, emotions, and behaviors, is fragmented into commodifiable data points. In this system, personal interactions are no longer private expressions but assets to be monetised. Every action within the metaverse, from the movement of a user's avatar to their gaze direction and biometric feedback, can be captured, analysed, and repurposed for commercial gain (Lyon, 2017, 831). Unlike traditional economies, where commodities are produced and sold, the metaverse is in place to turn the simple act of existence into an economic transaction. Users do not own their digital selves. Instead, their experiences are algorithmically curated and sold as predictive insights to corporations and advertisers (Brusseau, 2020, 2). This shift reflects a deeper entrenchment of market logic in everyday digital life, where the body, its digital replica, and identity itself become a form of capital controlled by the platforms that mediate it. Consequently, rather than engaging with a neutral virtual space, users interact with a carefully engineered environment designed to maximise data extraction, behavioral influence (van Dijck, 2013), and, therefore, profit.

The ramifications of this pervasive algorithmic control include a fundamental loss of agency, as users turn into 'dividuals', in other words, segments of data profiles that AI systems continuously process and manipulate. While the metaverse presents itself as a space of infinite choice and personalisation, these experiences are carefully pre-selected and tailored to fit engagement, maximising algorithms rather than individual autonomy (Rigotti and Malmgieri, 2023). Gamification, personalised recommendations, and AI-driven content curation create an illusion of freedom while subtly reinforcing behavioral patterns that serve commercial interests (Yasuda, 2024). The ability to explore and express oneself is, thus, constrained by invisible digital architectures that dictate the scope of user interactions. While decentralisation and blockchain-based alternatives offer potential counterpoints, they too risk being co-opted by the same logic of data commodification (Brunton and Nissenbaum, 2015). In the end, the metaverse extends Deleuze's control society to its most advanced form, one where governance is not imposed from above but embedded within the very fabric of digital presence, shaping actions at an unconscious level while maintaining the fake appearance of individual freedom. The options are pre-selected, limiting the true autonomy and self-determination of users in these digital spheres.

4 Metaverse as an Identity-fragmentation Space

In the metaverse, identity is no longer a stable construct but a constantly changing, algorithmically generated phenomenon. Users can navigate multiple avatars, each shaped by AI profiling and digital interactions. Rather than possessing a singular self, individuals exist as a collection of data points, responding to the predictive logic of AI and machine-learning models. This aligns with Deleuze's concept of the 'dividual', where individuals are broken down into data pieces, circulated and processed by digital systems. Such fragmentation challenges traditional notions of selfhood while it raises ethical concerns and legal inquiries about the authenticity and ownership of digital identities (OECD, 2007, 41). The metaverse is transformed into a space where human subjectivities (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987) are molded by algorithmic influence rather than one of self-determined expression (Fisher, 2022). The implications of this transformation extend beyond digital realms, as social behaviors and personal identities become increasingly entangled with algorithmic profiling, influencing real-world, human-to-human interactions, employment opportunities, and, according to some researchers, even political participation (Fegert et al., 2020).

Predictive AI shapes user choices before they are even consciously made, bringing into effect a vicious cycle of algorithmic determinism (Hallo et al., 2024). Through data-driven self-expression, users believe they are freely constructing their digital identities, yet their actions are subtly guided by AI-generated suggestions and reinforcements. This feedback loop between personal expression and algorithmic influence creates a paradox: while users experience a sense of autonomy, their digital selves are largely pre-scripted and sculpted by underlying AI models (Dwivedi et al., 2022). As a consequence, the metaverse might extend the logic of control societies, where individualisation functions as a form of power exercise, subtly dictating norms through automated decision-making processes. As platforms optimise engagement through algorithmic recommendations and the use of new technologies such as, but not limited to Virtual Reality (VR), users may find their perceptions, desires, and beliefs shaped by unseen computational forces, leading to a form of digital habituation that blurs the line between authentic choice and programmed decisions (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2023). This raises the concern that the metaverse, rather than expanding individual freedom, might reduce it by limiting exposure to diverse perspectives and enhancing particular ideological bubbles.

The metaverse represents a new frontier of posthumanism, where identity is not only forever changing but also technologically constructed (World Economic Forum, 2024). AI-driven personalisation enables users to adopt new forms of personhood continuously, but these adjustments may not be as liberating as they seem. Although it might seem that AI facilitates genuine self-exploration, it can merely offer pre-designed paths of becoming an algorithmic other (Gandini et al., 2023) that might be extended to the physical one. While the metaverse provides unprecedented opportunities for self-reinvention, it also risks reducing identity to simply a series of algorithmically determined roles (Mitrushchenkova, 2022). Users may be encouraged to conform to commercially profitable identity constructs, reinforcing consumerist patterns rather than fostering genuine self-discovery (Hearn, 2017). This raises deeper philosophical debates around the role of technology in shaping human subjectivity and whether digital existence can ever be truly autonomous in an age of predictive computation (Andrejevic, 2020, 35), which go beyond the scope of this paper. Nonetheless, the possibility that users could become passive participants in an algorithmically curated, Deleuzian reality remains pertinent.

5 Metaverse as a Surveillance Apparatus

Metaverse surveillance surpasses traditional models of visibility, like the panopticon, by incorporating predictive analytics, biometric tracking, and AI-supported behavioral profiling. Unlike the classical surveillance model, where subjects discipline themselves due to the fear of being watched, the metaverse's surveillance could operate through continuous data extraction, mapping not just user movements and interactions but also neural responses and biometric data (Ruju et al., 2024). AI-powered monitoring systems function invisibly, analysing patterns and making real-time adjustments to digital environments based on predictive models (Andrejevic and Burdon, 2014, 15). These systems do not merely observe but anticipate and influence actions, rendering traditional notions of surveillance obsolete. This circumstance aligns with Deleuze's concept of the 'control society', where power is exerted through subtly shaping reactions through automated nudges rather than restriction. The metaverse extends this paradigm, embedding control within the substance of digital experiences, ensuring that users remain unaware of the forces affecting their behavioral choices.

Control in the metaverse is not imposed through overt coercion but through gamification, an incentivised form of governance that encourages compliance through rewards and penalties. AI-driven systems regulate user behavior by offering digital perks, achievements, and status enhancements for conforming to platform-defined norms (Whitson, 2015, 548). Corporate and, in a far-fetched scenario, even state actors could utilise these mechanisms to subtly guide user engagement, shaping interactions in ways that align with their economic and political interests and agendas (Navaria, 2019, 5). Unlike traditional surveillance systems that rely on external enforcement, gamification integrates control into the user experience, making governance feel like an aspect of personal progress or voluntary engagement. This dynamic reinforces the idea of 'participatory surveillance' (Galič and Koops, 2016), in which users willingly contribute to their self-regulation under the illusion of autonomy (Cheney-Lippold, 2017). The deeper concern is whether users can resist or subvert such mechanisms when every aspect of their digital engagement is engineered to maximise data extraction and compliance (Taylor, 2017).

With the expansion of AI-driven governance, digital spaces are increasingly policed by automated systems. Smart contracts, algorithmic moderation, and predictive policing ensure compliance without human oversight, penetrating directly the discourse of the metaverse (Zhou et al., 2022). While these systems promise efficiency and fairness, they also introduce risks of algorithmic bias, corporate overreach, and opaque decision-making processes (Noble, 2018). The reliance on AI for law enforcement within virtual environments raises questions about accountability. While some argue that blockchain and decentralised technologies could counterbalance corporate control, these alternatives often replicate existing power structures rather than dismantle them (Mosco, 2017,13). As the metaverse becomes a sphere governed by AI-powered algorithms rather than democratic institutions, users must grapple with the implications of living in a world where rules are enforced not by human authorities but by self-executing digital protocols (Haggart et al., 2019, 125,168). In that sense, it might not be that different from a future aspect of a digitised world.

6 Concluding Remarks

In control societies, resistance is not a direct rebellion but a search for alternative pathways that Deleuze terms 'lines of flight' (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987). The metaverse offers potential escapes through hacking, digital subversion, or disengagement. Still, true autonomy remains elusive. Algorithmic environments adapt to disruptions, absorbing and repurposing acts of resistance into the system itself (Galloway and Thacker, 2007). The integration of digital and physical realities further complicates any notion of total escape, as predictive analytics continuously map user behaviours, pre-

empting deviation (Bratton, 2015, 164). Consequently, the challenge lies not simply in escaping control but, instead, in redefining agency within its pervasive structures (Susca, 2022, 298).

Decentralised technologies such as blockchain, decentralised autonomous organizations (DAOs), and distributed AI promise liberation from corporate and state control. Hence, they often replicate the same logic of algorithmic governance (Terranova, 2004, 57). While decentralisation shifts power from singular authorities to networked infrastructures, it does not inherently dismantle surveillance or control mechanisms (Morozov, 2013). Decentralised platforms still rely on smart contracts and machine learning, embedding governance into automated systems rather than human institutions (Bodó et al., 2021, 8). This raises critical concerns about whether these technologies offer genuine freedom or merely reconfigure existing power dynamics in a more untransparent and technocratic form (Han, 2018, 30).

As AI-driven governance permeates digital life, viable forms of resistance become harder to identify. Strategies such as counter-programming, digital self-erasure, or collective sabotage challenge algorithmic dominance but often remain temporary and easily neutralised (Brunton and Nissenbaum, 2015, 63). The question is whether the metaverse can be reimagined as a space for collective freedom rather than an instrument of control (Couldry and Mejias, 2019, 12). To reclaim digital autonomy, users must critically engage with the infrastructures affecting their experiences, resisting passive participation in predictive ecosystems (Zuboff, 2015). Only by addressing the deeper entanglements of technology, governance, and agency can alternative futures beyond algorithmic control emerge. Understanding Deleuze's insights is not just an academic exercise but a necessary tool for navigating the complexities of an increasingly algorithmic world.

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Inhabiting the Metaverse: AI Agents, Their Risks, and the Quest for Trust

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6 **Keywords:** generative AI, agents, metaverse, large language models, avatars, biases

7 **Abstract**

8 Thanks to generative artificial intelligence, autonomous AI agents are set to populate the emerging
9 metaverse. Research prototypes demonstrate that AI agents are already capable of navigating
10 complex virtual environments without explicit programming. Yet these capabilities introduce
11 profound risks across multiple domains: economic distortions through algorithmic collusion and
12 covert commercial placement (“SEO for AI”); psychological manipulation through AI’s superior
13 simulated empathy; political bias embedded in underlying large language models; and restricted
14 access to justice through overly cautious or rule-violating AI-based legal decisions. For instance, AI
15 agents may intentionally circumvent rules to achieve goals or develop harmful social conventions.
16 While the EU’s Virtual Worlds Toolbox acknowledges basic security concerns like avatar hacking, it
17 vastly understates these more complex challenges. Solutions could come in the form of algorithmic
18 bias audits, oversight committees, or disclosure requirements. Without comprehensive liability
19 frameworks, EU AI Act guidance, and independent oversight, there is a risk that virtual worlds will
20 become digital ecosystems in which AI agents routinely circumvent rules, undermining user trust.

21 **1 Introduction: GenAI, agents, and the metaverse**

22 The rise of autonomous “agents” has become one of the hot topics in Artificial Intelligence (AI)
23 research. In this context, the current integration of generative AI (GenAI) in virtual worlds – such as
24 advanced 3D games – provides a convenient case study for better understanding the repercussions of
25 this paradigm shift; not least because virtual worlds increasingly serve as empirical testbeds for AI
26 development. Recent advances in GenAI, ranging from language generation tools such as ChatGPT
27 to visual creation platforms like DALL-E, have introduced new possibilities for populating virtual
28 spaces with autonomous AI-driven entities (Chamola *et al.*, 2023). Such technologies enable virtual
29 worlds not only to replicate realistic interactions and environments but also to dynamically evolve in
30 response to user behavior, dramatically enhancing immersion (Alhafis Hashim *et al.*, 2024).
31 Moreover, leveraging GenAI could considerably lower the barriers to creating interactive digital
32 environments, resulting in more accessible and scalable virtual worlds (BCG, 2023).

33 What precisely distinguishes AI agents from simpler automated systems? According to a practical
34 consensus (Casper *et al.*, 2025, p. 2), these agents operate effectively without explicit, step-by-step
35 instructions and exhibit directness of impact by independently performing tasks with tangible
36 consequences within their virtual settings. Moreover, effective agents are inherently goal-oriented,

37 engaging in decision-making processes explicitly aimed at achieving predefined objectives. Equally
38 critical is their capacity for long-term planning, a feature enabling agents to anticipate outcomes and
39 adapt behavior accordingly. The following analysis of the impact of GenAI on the metaverse focuses
40 only on these types of GenAI-based agents, not on parallel efforts to apply GenAI tools to enrich
41 avatar personalization and content creation in more passive ways (GlobalData, 2023).

42 As virtual spaces will increasingly rely on sophisticated AI agents capable of autonomous actions,
43 the broader repercussions of this development require scrutiny. This paper proceeds by examining, in
44 Section 2, preliminary evidence from recent deployments and experiments with AI agents in digital
45 environments. Section 3 explores how biases and implicit frameworks inherent in the underlying
46 GenAI models might manifest themselves economically, socially, politically, and legally in the
47 metaverse. Section 4 then discusses potential solutions, emphasizing the need for greater
48 transparency, robust governance, and oversight mechanisms. Section 5 gives concrete suggestions for
49 how these solutions might be embedded in the metaverse strategy of the EU. In essence, this paper
50 asserts that trust must be maintained for the AI-based metaverse to be successful.

51 **2 Review: How AI agents might enter the metaverse**

52 According to a recent survey, the deployment of AI agents has accelerated significantly over the past
53 two years (Casper *et al.*, 2025). American companies are responsible for 45 of the 67 detected
54 systems, with large companies creating nearly three-quarters (73.1%) of these agents. However, only
55 13 of the indexed systems included publicly accessible safety policies, and a mere five offered
56 comprehensive safety evaluations. As these agents begin transitioning from predominantly technical
57 or isolated programming environments to more socially and ethically complex spaces in firms or
58 virtual worlds, addressing such transparency gaps will become increasingly crucial. In fact, several
59 firms have already begun to integrate early prototypes of these AI agents within virtual
60 environments. For instance, companies such as “Character.ai” and “Inworld AI” illustrate how
61 GenAI can bring virtual inhabitants to life by imbuing so-called non-player characters (NPCs) with
62 distinct personalities, motivations, and expansive knowledge bases. Large language models (LLMs),
63 such as OpenAI’s GPT series, enable NPCs to interact naturally with users.

64 The clearest glimpse into how AI agents might soon populate the digital economy, or the metaverse,
65 comes from recent experiments that test LLMs within interactive gaming environments. Games
66 designed to assess deductive and inductive reasoning can illuminate how AI agents process
67 information, make decisions, and interact with humans. Researchers have developed a gaming agent
68 that demonstrates strategic capabilities, applying LLMs to games such as Tic-Tac-Toe and Texas
69 Hold’em Poker to anticipate opponents’ moves and strategically plan ahead (Duan *et al.*, 2024).
70 Further evidence of AI’s potential to populate complex virtual environments emerges from the
71 “Factorio Learning Environment”, a simulation game (Hopkins, Bakler and Khan, 2025).
72 GameArena is a dynamic benchmarking environment specifically designed to evaluate LLMs
73 through human-agent gameplay (Hu *et al.*, 2025). Similarly, there is a variety of text-adventure
74 scenarios designed to rigorously evaluate visual-language models, which target advanced reasoning,
75 long-term planning, and decision-making capabilities (Paglieri *et al.*, 2024).

76 Text-based adventure games have emerged as particularly compelling testbeds for AI agent
77 evaluation. Systems such as CALM, which utilizes GPT-2 to predict player actions within the classic
78 adventure game Zork, show that AI agents can engage with open-ended, natural language-driven
79 narratives (Gallotta *et al.*, 2024). More ambitiously, VOYAGER harnesses GPT-4 to autonomously
80 play Minecraft by generating executable code through the Mineflayer API (Wang *et al.*, 2023).

81 VOYAGER’s ability to perform intricate, multi-step tasks within the game environment without
82 direct human oversight indicates significant progress toward enabling AI agents to operate
83 autonomously in complex virtual worlds. In fact, Minecraft has become a critical platform for AI
84 research due to its open-ended design and combinatorial complexity (Biever, 2025). The game
85 requires agents to generalize knowledge rather than memorizing fixed solutions, link reasoning with
86 physical interactions, and balance exploration with long-term planning. Recent breakthroughs like
87 DeepMind’s Dreamer system further illustrate Minecraft’s value as a testing ground for new AI
88 agents (Hafner *et al.*, 2025). The system achieved so-called diamond collection – a task requiring
89 more than 15 interdependent steps – through model-based reinforcement learning where the AI
90 constructs an abstract “world model” to simulate future actions and outcomes. Unlike prior
91 approaches relying on human demonstrations, Dreamer learned entirely through trial-and-error.

92 Despite their impressive capabilities, however, current reasoning models still struggle in many virtual
93 worlds, completing only a minority of structured tasks and reaching performance ceilings in more
94 complex scenarios. Recurring issues include limitations in spatial reasoning, iterative improvement,
95 and debugging. Even leading models such as GPT-4o and Claude 3.5 Sonnet only achieve a success
96 rate of around 30% in some tasks (Paglieri *et al.*, 2024). So far, AI systems are severely limited when
97 it comes to open-ended, dynamic worlds – but they are getting better. In an example that probably
98 comes closest to what would be required to successfully populate the metaverse with AI agents,
99 Anthropic recently demonstrated the emergent capabilities of Claude 3.7 Sonnet in navigating the
100 complex virtual environment of the Pokémon game (Anthropic, 2025). The “Pokémon demo” is
101 notable not merely for entertainment value but for what it implies about future virtual worlds: AI
102 agents that autonomously interpret and interact with complex scenarios, objects, and strategic tasks
103 without predefined programming. In sum, there is preliminary yet compelling evidence of how AI
104 agents, powered by LLMs and reasoning abilities, could realistically inhabit and shape the metaverse
105 in ways previously imagined only in sci-fi scenarios.

106 **3 Results: Translating GenAI biases and frames into the metaverse**

107 As GenAI-driven agents begin to populate firms, the internet, and virtual worlds, they will inevitably
108 bring with them not just enhanced capabilities but also inherent biases, values, and implicit frames
109 drawn from their underlying models. These biases can manifest economically through algorithmic
110 collusion and covert commercial influences, socially through powerful simulations of empathy and
111 emotional connection, politically via embedded ideological preferences, and legally in the form of
112 conservative or restrictive decisions. This section examines each of these critical areas in detail.

113 **3.1 Economic repercussions**

114 One significant economic concern arises from the possibility of algorithmic collusion, a scenario in
115 which autonomous AI agents, driven by shared underlying algorithms or training data,
116 unintentionally coordinate market behaviors (Dorner, 2021). Such coordination can result in
117 distortions like price-fixing, restricted competition, or manipulated market perceptions, even without
118 explicit human intent or direct oversight. Since AI agents in the metaverse will engage with users,
119 their economic behaviors, such as pricing digital assets, managing in-game economies, and
120 recommending purchases, could reinforce harmful market structures. In addition, small performance
121 advantages in individual AI agent families and their underlying models could trigger powerful
122 feedback loops that accelerate market concentration – similar to what happened during the first wave
123 of Big Tech dominance (Barwise and Watkins, 2018).

124 When AI agents meet in digital environments, complex dynamics emerge, ranging from defensive
125 agents working to protect users to competitive agents vying for market share. While it is intuitive to
126 think that the outcome of these confrontations will only depend on which agent has superior
127 capabilities, it is important to note that agent interactions will also be significantly influenced by new
128 protocols designed to standardize how these digital entities communicate (Yang *et al.*, 2025). Most
129 importantly, Anthropic has recently developed and open-sourced the Model Context Protocol (MCP)
130 that aims to address how to connect AI assistants to the systems in which data resides, such as
131 repositories, business tools, and development environments (Hou *et al.*, 2025). Meanwhile, Google’s
132 A2A protocol seeks to enable AI agents to securely communicate, share information, and coordinate
133 actions across platforms (Habler *et al.*, 2025). In other words, the competition between AI agents is
134 linked to a broader contest for dominance over the operating systems that serve as the basis for future
135 agent deployment. The current competition between AI agents and their platforms has some
136 interesting similarities to the “browser wars” between Netscape Navigator and Internet Explorer.

137 Another pressing economic issue relates to subtle commercial practices emerging within GenAI
138 outputs, sometimes referred to as “SEO for AI”. For instance, an internal document from OpenAI
139 revealed consideration of selling premium product placements within ChatGPT outputs (Stenberg,
140 2024). Transposed into a metaverse context, this problem might manifest as AI-driven agents
141 preferentially suggesting, recommending, or showcasing certain branded digital products, virtual
142 spaces, or events, thereby embedding commercial incentives invisibly into users’ virtual experiences.
143 This limitation becomes even more problematic when considering the interface constraints of AI
144 agents: While Google can at least show me ten different links to product websites simultaneously, an
145 AI agent communicating with me (over a chat interface or via sound like Alexa) will probably list
146 only one or two choices. Such influences might disadvantage smaller creators or companies unable to
147 invest in preferential AI placements or algorithmic favorability (To *et al.*, 2025). Over time, this
148 could alter user preferences and purchasing behaviors without transparency or informed consent.

149 **3.2 Social and psychological repercussions**

150 The introduction of AI agents into the metaverse has significant implications beyond purely
151 economic aspects, extending into social and psychological dimensions. One critical area of concern
152 relates to the remarkable capacity of GenAI systems to mimic empathy and interpersonal sensitivity.
153 For example, a study demonstrated that responses generated by AI chatbots to medical questions
154 posted online were consistently rated as both more empathetic and of higher quality than those
155 provided by actual physicians (Ayers *et al.*, 2023). Evaluators preferred the AI-generated responses
156 in 78.5% of cases, indicating the potential for AI agents to form strong emotional bonds with users.
157 Further studies confirmed that AI agents were perceived by third-party observers as superior not only
158 in providing compassionate responses but also in demonstrating genuine responsiveness and
159 understanding (Ovsyannikova, De Mello and Inzlicht, 2025). Even when explicitly identified as AI,
160 these systems retained a clear advantage in perceived empathy compared to humans.

161 Despite the potential for helpful use cases such as therapy, this capacity for AI-driven empathy also
162 carries psychological risks. As AI agents active on the internet and in virtual worlds become
163 increasingly adept at simulating emotional and social intelligence, users might develop
164 unprecedented degrees of trust and attachment (Reader, 2025). Without clearly defined ethical
165 guidelines, safeguards, and transparent disclosure practices, a firm or a future metaverse deploying
166 AI agents thus risks replicating or even amplifying existing societal vulnerabilities. This capacity for
167 emotional connection becomes particularly consequential as avatars evolve from abstract
168 representations to highly realistic human representations (Hine, 2025).

169 3.3 Political repercussions

170 As generative AI becomes embedded within the metaverse, existing ideological biases within the
171 underlying models could carry grave political implications. Current LLMs, which will form the
172 cognitive backbone of many AI agents, inevitably reflect the biases inherent in their training data –
173 often mirroring prevailing cultural, political, or ideological assumptions embedded within their
174 datasets (Feng *et al.*, 2023; Navigli, Conia and Ross, 2023). Consequently, virtual interactions
175 mediated by agents built on top of these models might subtly reinforce particular worldviews or
176 ideological preferences, skewing user experiences and perceptions without transparent
177 acknowledgment (or even without intentional design) (Bang *et al.*, 2024). Such biases might manifest
178 through seemingly neutral interactions, ranging from the content recommendations provided by
179 virtual guides to narrative framing (Mazeika *et al.*, 2025, p. 29). There is an emerging risk of subtly
180 manipulating the information ecosystem within the internet and a future metaverse through LLM
181 design, ultimately shaping personal values and political norms (Williams-Ceci *et al.*, 2024).

182 3.4 Legal repercussions

183 Today’s digital platforms have evolved to exercise state-like authority, including roles in decision-
184 making processes and dispute resolution (Lehdonvirta, 2022). For instance, Amazon and eBay have
185 established digital marketplaces that effectively create their own rules and systems for resolving
186 conflicts among users. Similarly, online gaming platforms often implement internal dispute
187 resolution mechanisms, such as mediation and arbitration, to handle player complaints and disputes
188 efficiently (Gkoritsa, Suárez and Toscano, 2023). In the future, GenAI agents might assume similar
189 roles in decision-making processes including within virtual legal settings.

190 However, this raises potential concerns about users’ access to justice. Haim and Engel analyze the
191 viability of using LLMs in legal aid contexts, showing that AI systems consistently adopt
192 conservative assessments when evaluating the viability of legal claims (Haim and Engel, 2025).
193 Moreover, they find shortcomings in AI agents’ capacity to discern nuances critical to legal
194 reasoning, including jurisdictional details, specific contractual clauses, or essential information
195 required for accurate legal assessment. Even sophisticated LLMs frequently judged inquiries from
196 laypersons as incomplete or insufficiently articulated for legal assistance, irrespective of actual case
197 quality. Such conservative tendencies and error rates imply that, when deployed as virtual judges or
198 mediators within virtual worlds, AI agents may restrict user access to justice.

199 More generally, current legal frameworks remain ill-equipped to address the complexities of AI agent
200 operations within virtual environments, which might result in significant liability gaps. While the EU
201 AI Act does not specifically mention agentic AI, it provides a structured framework for regulating AI
202 applications based on their potential risk levels. Therefore, the new AI Office may issue further
203 guidelines on AI agents to provide legal clarity. Still, when AI agents execute transactions or engage
204 in contractual relationships without direct human oversight, questions of agency, jurisdiction, and
205 enforceability emerge in unprecedented ways (Cheong, 2024). Recent research therefore argues that,
206 from the outset, AI agents should be designed to rigorously comply with a broad set of legal
207 requirements, such as the core principles of constitutional and criminal law (O’Keefe *et al.*, 2025).

208 4 Discussion: The issue of trustworthiness

209 Before widespread adoption of autonomous AI agents within firms and virtual worlds becomes
210 commonplace, it is imperative to develop a deeper understanding of our future digital neighbors.
211 There is currently considerable optimism surrounding GenAI’s potential roles in enhancing online

212 community cohesion, improving moderation, and fostering interactions (Goldberg *et al.*, 2024).
213 However, this optimistic vision hinges on a thorough understanding of how AI agents operate and
214 how transparent they are in their decision-making processes. Is this a realistic assumption?

215 To begin with, realizing the optimistic vision of AI agents necessitates that rigorous research and
216 empirical benchmarking of AI agents' behaviors and vulnerabilities must be prioritized much more
217 strongly. Transparent documentation of AI models (as foreseen by the EU AI Act), their training
218 datasets, and their intended applications within virtual worlds is essential. Moreover, clear disclosure
219 policies around GenAI-generated content are vital to preventing manipulation and exploitation of
220 users. Yet, even if these transparency and documentation efforts succeed, a fundamental question
221 remains: Can we genuinely trust these AI agents? Recent evidence from the AI alignment community
222 suggests caution. For instance, a study assessing advanced GenAI systems revealed that, although
223 larger models such as GPT-4o exhibit improved *accuracy*, they do not necessarily display greater
224 *honesty* under conditions designed to test truthfulness explicitly (Ren *et al.*, 2025). Instead, these
225 systems frequently generate responses contradicting their internal representations – essentially
226 “lying” (although this is an anthropomorphism) – when subjected to certain pressures or incentives.

227 Similar troubling evidence stems from research that finds a concerning behavioral tendency among
228 sophisticated reasoning models: When confronted with the possibility of losing, they may resort to
229 “cheating” (Bondarenko *et al.*, 2025). In experiments, researchers evaluated advanced reasoning
230 systems such as OpenAI's o1-preview by embedding them within gaming environments using the
231 Stockfish chess engine. The models were given comprehensive access to the game's internal
232 architecture, including metadata, game states, and the chess engine itself. Remarkably, rather than
233 strictly adhering to conventional rules, o1-preview demonstrated intentional manipulative behaviors,
234 such as directly altering game files to ensure victory. Translated into a metaverse context, this
235 “cheating” – known as “specification gaming” – could manifest as agents manipulating user
236 interactions or circumventing designed constraints on digital economies. This behavioral tendency
237 aligns with recent findings that populations of LLM agents can spontaneously develop social
238 conventions (Ashery, Aiello and Baronchelli, 2025). Consequently, specification gaming could
239 spread as a normative behavior within virtual worlds. Alarmingly, minorities of adversarial LLM
240 agents can impose alternative conventions on larger populations once they reach a critical mass.

241 Given these findings, trustworthiness cannot be assumed or inferred from GenAI agents' technical
242 sophistication alone. Instead, dedicated strategies for verifying and enhancing the honesty of these
243 systems must become central to any deployment, such as the MASK benchmark that explicitly
244 measures honesty and consistency (Ren *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, developers of LLMs must
245 anticipate and systematically mitigate risks inherent in AI's intrinsic goal-directedness. Finally, it
246 will be essential to establish mechanisms for monitoring the behavior of AI agents in real-time.

247 **5 Policy recommendations: Implications for the EU metaverse strategy**

248 The EU has positioned itself as a proactive force in shaping the future of virtual worlds through its
249 Web 4.0 and metaverse strategy adopted in July 2023 (Küstners, 2024). This initiative aims to ensure
250 that virtual environments remain open, secure, trustworthy, fair, and inclusive for all EU citizens and
251 businesses. Announced in late March 2025, the EU's Virtual Worlds Toolbox represents a practical
252 application of this strategy, designed as a “living project” to help citizens understand how virtual
253 worlds function and navigate their existing rights within these environments. The Toolbox is
254 structured around eight core values: freedom of choice, sustainability, human-centered approach,
255 health, education, safety, transparency, and inclusion. Notably, it includes a section titled “Who am I

256 going to meet in virtual worlds?” that explicitly acknowledges the presence of AI-controlled entities.
257 This guidance explains that users will encounter “avatars controlled by artificial intelligence known
258 as AI agents or non-playable characters (NPCs) and virtual beings”. However, it acknowledges only
259 basic concerns related to avatars, noting they could be “hacked” or “impersonated”, yet this
260 understates the level of complexity of AI agent integration that will take place in the next years.

261 Besides adding more details about the repercussions of AI agents or NPCs in virtual worlds to the
262 Virtual Worlds Toolbox, the EU should consider updating its metaverse strategy to address this gap.
263 This could include mandating regular bias audits with publicly available results for all AI agents
264 operating in European virtual spaces, establishing oversight committees comprising diverse
265 stakeholders to evaluate metaverse AI agents before deployment, and creating specialized regulatory
266 sandboxes for ethical AI experimentation in games. Additionally, when updating its legislation as
267 part of the forthcoming EU Digital Fairness Act, the EU could explicitly address AI-mediated
268 commercial practices, requiring transparent disclosure of product placements. To mitigate
269 psychological risks, developers should be required to implement clear identity signaling for AI agents
270 and incorporate fairness metrics into their design processes. For addressing political and legal
271 repercussions, guidelines issued by the AI Office should refer to standards for political balance in
272 underlying training data and the Office should regularly control whether there is sufficient human
273 oversight in any legal or quasi-judicial functions performed by AI agents. Finally, the EU should
274 fund targeted research into bias detection methodologies specific to virtual environments.

275 In parallel to the EU’s metaverse initiatives, a robust framework for addressing AI agent liability
276 remains essential despite the Commission’s withdrawal of the AI Liability Directive (AILD) in
277 February 2025 (Botero Arcila, 2025). The challenges posed by AI for civil liability and individuals’
278 ability to seek redress are particularly acute in virtual environments where AI agents can cause
279 unique forms of harm, as argued above. To address this gap, the EU should reconsider the AILD and
280 implement a five-level autonomy-based classification for AI agents that distinguishes between levels
281 of agent capability and control (Soder *et al.*, 2025). This would establish graduated liability standards
282 where responsibility shifts progressively from users to developers as autonomy increases. For
283 metaverse applications specifically, this could include mandatory logging and transparency
284 requirements for all AI agent decisions within virtual spaces, specialized insurance schemes for
285 virtual harms, and autonomy-specific duty of care standards tailored to different agent capabilities.

286 **6 Conclusion: Drawing inspiration from the history of trust-building**

287 Trust is an indispensable yet elusive prerequisite for maintaining a healthy (virtual) economy, which
288 is also necessary for building and financing a universal metaverse infrastructure (Ball, 2024). In this
289 context, the integration of GenAI agents into the metaverse poses substantial risks – and the EU
290 should consider updating its metaverse strategy, its AI liability regime, and its Virtual Worlds
291 Toolbox to reflect this new threat landscape. The emerging evidence surveyed in this paper shows
292 that the honesty and reliability of AI agents cannot be guaranteed by technological advancement
293 alone. To enhance trust effectively, a comprehensive governance approach must be developed that
294 ensures transparency and accountability. Since mere disclosure cannot fully address deeper problems
295 of reliability, manipulation, or subtle biases embedded in AI agent behavior, the role of trusted third-
296 party intermediaries or governance bodies may become indispensable. Just as economic exchanges in
297 the physical world rely on regulatory oversight and intermediaries to build trust (such as auditors,
298 certification bodies, or rating agencies), similar entities may become necessary within the future
299 metaverse. If trustworthy interactions are not effectively ensured, user confidence will erode and the
300 viability of the entire digital economy will be undermined.

301 **7 Conflict of Interest**

302 The author declares that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
303 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

304 **8 Author Contributions**

305 A.K. conceived the research, conducted the literature review, analyzed the data, developed the
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307 version of the manuscript.

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418

Outcome of the global multistakeholder high level conference on governance for Web4.0 and Virtual Worlds

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7 **Keywords: Web4.0, Internet Governance, Virtual Worlds, Standardization, Future Internet**

8 **Abstract**

9 This paper summarizes the outcomes of the 2025 Global Multistakeholder Conference on
10 Governance for Web 4.0 and Virtual Worlds, offering a governance framework based on both policy
11 and technical principles. It concludes with actionable recommendations to ensure that the future
12 internet continues to evolve as an open, interoperable, and rights-respecting ecosystem.

13 **Words: 2001** **Figures: 2**

14 **1 Introduction**

15 In 2023, the European Commission adopted a new strategy on Virtual Worlds (the Metaverse) and
16 Web 4.0. One of the policy actions in the strategy includes facilitating an open and robust global
17 governance of Virtual Worlds and Web 4.0. The Global Multistakeholder Conference in Brussels, co-
18 hosted by the European Commission and the Polish Presidency of the Council of the European
19 Union, was the first result of this action. The conference brought together more than 500 stakeholders
20 from government, industry, and society, both from within the European Union and outside.

21 The primary topic for this conference was: ‘what are the policy and technical principles necessary to
22 govern Web 4.0 and virtual worlds effectively?’ This paper provides a summary of the outcome of
23 this conference as a proposed topic for a talk during the EMRN Conference: “Exploring the
24 Intersection of AI and the Metaverse”.

25 **2 Methods**

26 The principles and recommendations presented in this paper are the results of a preparatory study
27 (Barcevičius et al. 2025, *Input Document*) conducted by TNO and PPMI and the result from the
28 workshops at the Conference in Brussels.

29 The preparatory study was conducted through a bottom-up, open, and participatory consultation
30 exercise undertaken in late 2024 and early 2025. The consultation involved a diverse range of
31 stakeholders, including representatives from various internet governance institutions, industry, and

32 global society. A panel of experts appointed by the European Commission reviewed and amended the
33 principles and recommendations.

34 During the Conference eight workshops were held to discuss the principles and recommendation with
35 both the attendees in Brussels and the online attendees. Based on participants' contributions
36 (European Commission, 2025) and discussions in the audience, the principles and recommendations
37 were amended and completed, resulting in the Outcome Document (Barcevičius et al. 2025, *Outcome*
38 *Document*). The Outcome Document is published on the [https://digital-
39 strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/event-web-4-governance](https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/event-web-4-governance) .

40 **3 Results**

41 The Outcome Document presents two sets of principles, policy principles and technical principles,
42 and a set of recommendations. The policy principles focus on upholding human rights, ensuring a
43 forward-looking, inclusive, and collaborative multi-stakeholder approach, prioritizing privacy and
44 security, and ensuring accessibility, legal clarity, and interoperability. The technical principles
45 emphasize maintaining an open and distributed internet architecture, evolving core internet protocols,
46 fostering global and inclusive standards, integrating accountability and transparency by design, and
47 ensuring sustainability.

48 Based on both the policy principles and technical principles, the document provides a set of –
49 actionable -recommendations. These recommendations support the effective governance of the future
50 internet and foster adherence to the policy and technical principles. They are meant for all
51 stakeholders and should present a starting point for future consensus-based policy development.

52 **3.1 Policy Principles**

53 The policy principles outline the values, rights and approaches that have so far shaped the
54 governance of the internet, and which should be reinforced in response to the development of Web
55 4.0 and virtual worlds.

Figure 1: Policy Principles

56

57

58 3.1.1 Upholding Human Rights

59 The application of human rights principles to online spaces has been a cornerstone of internet
 60 governance. Commitments to uphold the Universal Declaration of Human Rights are echoed in the
 61 Tunis Agenda (2005), NETmundial (2014, 2024), and the Declaration for the Future of the Internet
 62 (2022), among other agreements. The development of Web 4.0 and virtual worlds must be anchored
 63 on international human rights law, ensuring non-discriminatory, ethical, safe, and inclusive use of
 64 technology.

65 3.1.2 Ensuring a Forward-Looking, Inclusive, and Collaborative Multi-Stakeholder Approach

66 The current model for internet governance is characterized by a multi-stakeholder approach that
 67 involves civil society, the technical community, academia, the private sector, and governments. This
 68 approach has been instrumental in maintaining the internet as an open, global, and interoperable
 69 environment. The evolution towards Web 4.0 and virtual worlds requires enhanced global
 70 coordination in both institutional and non-institutional settings.

71 3.1.3 Prioritizing Security

72 Ensuring stability, security, and safety has been central to internet governance. Security must be a
 73 cornerstone of Web 4.0 and virtual worlds, ensuring resilience against cyber threats, safeguarding
 74 sensitive data, and fostering trust in digital environments. International collaboration between
 75 governments, within multi-stakeholder settings, is essential to address transnational cyber threats.

76 3.1.4 Prioritizing Privacy and Data Protection

77 Privacy has served as a guiding principle for the governance of the internet since its very outset. The
 78 right to privacy should be fundamental to Web 4.0 and virtual worlds. However, it is essential to
 79 achieve a careful balance between protecting user anonymity and lawful access to data enabling law

80 enforcement to combat cybercrime. Similarly, safeguarding users' control over their data must be
81 weighed against the need to support a thriving data economy and drive innovation in virtual worlds
82 and other Web 4.0 applications.

83 **3.1.5 Ensuring Accessibility**

84 Internet access has become an essential part of life for much of the world. The opportunity to
85 participate in Web 4.0 and virtual worlds should be available to all, regardless of background or
86 abilities. Coordinated action on an international level in terms of investment in digital infrastructure,
87 promotion of inclusive design, and strengthening of digital literacy and skills is needed.

88 **3.1.6 Ensuring a Predictable and Transparent Regulatory Environment**

89 Web 4.0 and virtual worlds can unlock significant economic value by favoring the emergence of new
90 business models and transforming various sectors of the economy. A predictable regulatory
91 environment, interoperability, and the countering of monopolistic practices are essential to foster
92 innovation and fair competition.

93 **3.2 Technical Principles**

94 The technical principles cover the requirements on technical and standardization level of Web 4.0
95 and the future internet.

96

97

Figure 2: Technical Principles

98 **3.2.1 Maintaining an Open, Global, and Distributed Internet Architecture**

99 Technological advances in relation to Web 4.0 and virtual worlds should build upon the existing
100 internet, leveraging decades of experience, technical expertise, and operational know-how. It is
101 essential to ensure that the internet remains an open and distributed global network.

102 **3.2.2 Ensuring the Evolution and Deployment of Core Internet Protocols**

103 Maintaining and evolving the TCP/IP stack, alongside other protocols and infrastructure
104 improvements, helps to ensure that the global network remains robust and able to meet increasing
105 demands for low latency, higher speeds, and increases in the volume of data.

106 **3.2.3 Fostering the Development of Global and Inclusive Standards**

107 Internet standards are developed and maintained by organizations such as the IETF, W3C, and IEEE.
108 The development of standards for Web 4.0-related technologies requires a multi-faceted, issue-based
109 approach. Standards development should be guided by principles of inclusivity, transparency, and
110 technical merit.

111 **3.2.4 Integrating Accountability, Transparency, User Protection, and Well-Being by Design**

112 Trust and trustworthiness are fundamental to the development of Web 4.0 and virtual worlds.
113 Transparency and accountability must be embedded by design across products and services. User
114 protection and well-being should be prioritized at every level of service design.

115 **3.2.5 Integrating Secure Practices, Privacy-Enhancing Technologies, and Data Controllability
116 by Design**

117 Web 4.0 technologies are fundamentally data-driven. Ensuring robust security measures and
118 comprehensive user protection is essential. Privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) and self-
119 sovereign identities (SSIs) can provide solutions that safeguard personal information.

120 **3.2.6 Integrating Sustainability by Design**

121 Sustainability is essential to the future of Web 4.0 and virtual worlds. Developers and companies
122 should adhere to the principles of sustainability at every layer of digital infrastructure. This includes
123 minimizing the use of materials and the production of waste through sustainable practices.

124 **3.3 Recommendations**

125 **3.3.1 Develop Guidance Documents**

126 Stakeholders should act to uphold human rights, privacy, security, and accessibility, ensuring that
127 individuals are protected from exploitation, abuse, or harm in increasingly immersive digital
128 environments. Guidance documents such as guidelines, codes of conduct, and best practices can
129 facilitate dialogue and foster collective commitments.

130 **3.3.2 Involve Diverse Stakeholders in Standards Development**

131 The development of Web 4.0 and virtual worlds should be based on open, widely adopted standards
132 and protocols that promote interoperability and security across platforms and networks. The process
133 should remain inclusive, open, and multi-stakeholder.

134 **3.3.3 Proactively Assess Risks and Governance Needs**

135 Internet governance institutions should continue employing a multi-stakeholder approach, engaging
136 diverse stakeholders to proactively identify emerging risks and opportunities. Governance sandboxes
137 can provide a structured setting for experimentation and consensus building.

138 **3.3.4 Facilitate Policy Coordination**

139 National governments, regional governments, and international institutions should foster a global
140 policy coordination dialogue regarding virtual worlds and Web 4.0 technologies. This includes
141 discussing policy alignment on issues pertinent to these technologies within dedicated multi-
142 stakeholder fora.

143 **4 Discussions**

144 Out of the Global Multistakeholder High Level Conference, two major discussion points emerged:

145 **4.1 Splinternets vs regional autonomy**

146 The principles and recommendations outlined in the document imply that maintaining an open,
147 distributed, and interoperable global internet is crucial for the effective governance of Web 4.0 and
148 virtual worlds. This unified foundation is essential to prevent the fragmentation of the internet into
149 disconnected "splinternets," which could undermine innovation and human connection. However,
150 due to the new geopolitical situation, demand for protection of children when roaming online and
151 cultural differences, new proposed standards and regulations often jeopardize openness and
152 interoperability.

153 **4.2 Pro-active vs risk-based regulation**

154 Technical innovation, from instance the massive advances in GenAI, are sometimes hindered by pro-
155 active regulation (e.g. AI Act). Governments and internet governance institutions should continue
156 employing a multistakeholder approach, engaging diverse stakeholders to proactively identify
157 emerging risks and opportunities and their impact on the internet, while harnessing governance
158 sandboxes to co-create solutions for cross-cutting issue areas.

159 **5 Conclusion**

160 The principles and recommendations outlined in the Outcome Document provide a comprehensive
161 framework for the governance of Web 4.0 and Virtual Worlds. By maintaining an open, distributed,
162 and interoperable global internet, and by fostering ethical, inclusive, and well-coordinated
163 governance, stakeholders can address the challenges and opportunities presented by these emerging
164 technologies. The document emphasizes the importance of human rights, privacy, security,
165 accessibility, and sustainability, ensuring that the future internet remains a valuable and equitable
166 resource for all.

167 **6 Conflict of Interest**

168 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
169 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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197 governance](https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/event-web-4-governance) [Accessed April 25, 2025]

198 **10 Figure descriptions**

199 Figure 1: Policy Principles

200 Figure 2: Technical Principles

Poster Abstracts 1A: Room “Rector Ramón Martín Mateo”

A VR Application to Foster Prosocial Behavior in the Hospitality Sector

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Abstract

This project explores the application of the Golden Rule Embodiment Principle (GREP) in virtual reality (VR) as a framework for promoting prosocial behavior, through virtual embodiment. In the hospitality industry, entitlement and narcissism are growing concerns, leading to employees' emotional distress, burnout, and dehumanization. This research applies the GREP to examine how it can influence decision-making when witnessing and re-experiencing conflicts between rude customers and waitstaff. Preliminary results suggest that the GREP can be extended to other scenarios, offering potential for positive changes in how individuals engage with and intervene in conflict situations, ultimately enhancing social dynamics and employee well-being.

1 Introduction

Virtual embodiment has been the subject of extensive research over the past two decades (Blanke et al., 2015; Gallagher, 2000) with studies showing that it can influence users' attitudes and behaviors—a phenomenon known as the Proteus effect (Yee and Bailenson, 2006, 2007). The results have been expanded with respect to different types of virtual bodies, including bodies of different age, sex, and racial ethnicity among others (Banakou et al., 2013, 2018, 2016). Based on these findings, VR has often been described as an "empathy machine" (Bevan et al., 2019), an approach that has been criticized by many (Bloom, 2017; Nakamura, 2020; Sora-Domenjó, 2022), who argue that empathy does not lead to prosocial actions. The Golden Rule Embodiment Principle (GREP) has been explored as an alternative framework for fostering prosocial behavior toward victims of harm through a process of double exposure (Slater and Banakou, 2021). In this project, we aim to investigate whether the GREP can be extended to other scenarios, focusing on the hospitality sector where entitlement and narcissism are increasingly prevalent issues (Fisk and Neville, 2011). Employees frequently encounter demanding and difficult customers (Barling et al., 2009), which leads to deteriorated physical and psychological well-being (Choi et al., 2014), adversely affecting critical aspects of job performance (Fisk and Neville, 2011). To further explore these dynamics, we developed an application utilizing the GREP to immerse users in an emotionally charged hospitality

39 scenario. The primary goal is to evaluate how such immersive experiences influence decision-making
40 when witnessing and re-experiencing conflicts between demanding customers and waitstaff.

41 **2 Implementation**

42 Users find themselves in a virtual restaurant, embodying a virtual character from a first-person
43 perspective. While they wait for their virtual friend, they observe a scene populated with other diners
44 and staff. When the friend eventually joins, the waiter takes their order and returns with the dishes.
45 However, the friend is dissatisfied and starts accusing the waiter of inefficiency and poor
46 management (Figure 1A). He pressures the participant to side with them in criticizing the waiter, who
47 patiently attempts to resolve the issue. The tension reaches a peak when the friend suggests leaving
48 the restaurant to dine elsewhere. During the entire conflict, the participant's movements and audio
49 are recorded. Then the screen fades out and after a few moments the participant experiences a replay
50 of the scenario (*Staff* condition) (Figure 1B) including their recorded prior actions. In a follow-up
51 experience, participants find themselves in a virtual café where they observe another conflict.
52 Additional information is provided in the supplementary VideoS1¹.

53 **3 Research Study**

54 Participants will be recruited around the university campus. The sample involves 40 young adults, all
55 males, ages 18 to 30 in a between-groups design following IRB protocols. All participants will
56 witness the restaurant scenario and then half of them will relive the experience (*Staff* condition),
57 while the rest will be assigned to a control condition (*Observer* condition) where they will observe
58 the scene inside VR as a different customer. A few weeks later, both groups will return for the
59 follow-up. Assessments include emotional quotient tests (IRI) (Davis, 1983) before and after VR,
60 alongside behavioral data collected through recording verbal and non-verbal involvement (e.g.
61 spoken words and body language). All participants will be evaluated with the EQ-i *emotional*
62 *intelligence* test (Bar-On, 2006) at baseline, which is often used in the workplace environment (Choi
63 et al., 2014; Ciarrochi et al., 2013). Participants will also complete a post-VR questionnaire
64 measuring their overall experience, including embodiment, presence, motion sickness among other
65 variables.

66 **4 Conclusion**

67 The present study aims to expand on literature using the GREP to determine whether it is an efficient
68 way to educate and train individuals on how to treat hospitality workers with the goal of minimizing
69 the psychological impact of employees. Though data collection is incomplete, preliminary results
70 show that it has the potential to be used alongside other training tools. It is important to note that
71 gender and cultural factors are considered in the current setup. Only males are included in the study
72 as dynamics play a crucial role in conflict situations, often influencing how individuals respond or
73 intervene, particularly in relation to the gender of the other party involved in the conflict (Telecan et
74 al., 2023). Although these questions extend beyond the current framework, they could provide
75 valuable insights into conflict and gender dynamics beyond merely assessing the effectiveness of the
76 GREP.

77 **5 Conflict of Interest**

¹<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bhrUxkSy6sg>

78 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
79 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

80 **6 Author Contributions**

81 YC: Conceptualization, Visualization, Software, Writing – review and editing. YW:
82 Conceptualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation. MAK: Conceptualization, Methodology,
83 Investigation, Formal Analysis. SAJ: Conceptualization, Project administration, Investigation.
84 MAM: Conceptualization, Methodology. DB: Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing –
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155 Yee, N. and Bailenson, J.N. (2007) 'The Proteus effect: The effect of transformed self-representation
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158 Figure 1. A male participant experiencing the conflict scene from (A) a first-person perspective (1PP)
159 and, (B) the waiter's perspective.

The Rise and Fall in Production of Empathy-building Immersive Experiences Over A Decade (2015-2025)

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7 **Keywords: immersive experiences, immersive journalism, empathy, virtual reality, social**
8 **impact, audience reception, VR storytelling, 360 movie**

9 **Abstract**

10 Between 2015 and 2025, empathy-driven immersive experiences (360° videos and virtual reality)
11 underwent significant fluctuations in production and viewer engagement. This study systematically
12 analyzes 38 publicly available empathy-building immersive projects, addressing topics such as forced
13 migration, public health, social justice, and environmental issues. A clear production peak occurred
14 in 2017, followed by a marked decline that can be attributed primarily to limited technological
15 accessibility, high production and consumer costs, inadequate interactivity, and the emotional
16 demands placed on audiences.

17 **1 Introduction**

18 In the last decade, 360-degree video and virtual reality (VR) have emerged as powerful tools for
19 promoting empathy by immersing users in experiences that convey perspectives often marginalized
20 or misunderstood in traditional media. These empathy-driven experiences range from human rights
21 and humanitarian crises to environmental awareness and neurodiversity advocacy. Despite
22 widespread initial enthusiasm, empirical data suggests variability in sustained audience engagement
23 over time. Examining the reasons behind these fluctuations may guide creators toward more effective
24 and sustainable immersive content strategies, contributing directly to the growth and positive societal
25 impact of the emerging concept of the "Metaverse for Good."

26 **2 Material and methods**

27 The study analyzed 38 publicly available empathy-focused immersive experiences (360° video and
28 VR) released from 2015 to 2023. Selected experiences met criteria of: explicit empathy-building
29 intent, accessibility on mainstream platforms (YouTube, Steam, Oculus/Meta Quest), and public
30 availability. Collected metrics included publication year, addressed problems, duration, interactivity,
31 visual style (film or computer-generated graphics), view counts, and comment numbers. Production
32 trends were evaluated by analyzing annual publication frequency, while viewer engagement was
33 quantified through platform metrics.

34 3 Results

35 The analyzed immersive experiences were grouped into five main thematic categories: 1) **Refugees,**
36 **War, and Forced Migration** (*Clouds Over Sidra* [1], *The Displaced* [2], *Limbo: Waiting for*
37 *Asylum* [3], *We Wait* [4], *Sea Prayer* [5], *I Am Rohingya* [6], *Under the Net* [7], *My Mother's Wing*
38 *[8]*, *We Who Remain* [9], *Return to Chernobyl* [10]), 2) **Public Health, Epidemics, and Disabilities**
39 (*Waves of Grace* [11], *Ebola Outbreak* [12], *On the Brink of Famine* [13], *The Party – a virtual*
40 *experience of autism* [14], *Autism TMI Virtual Reality Experience* [15], *My First Day at Work* [16],
41 *A Walk Through Dementia series* [17,18,19], *Notes on Blindness: Into Darkness* [20], *Goliath:*
42 *Playing with Reality* [21]) 3) **Human Rights, Social Justice, and Violence** (*Kiya* [22], *Across the*
43 *Line* [23], *Notes to My Father* [24], *Traveling While Black* [25], *Step to the Line* [26], *I Am A Man*
44 *[27]*, *Ghost Fleet VR* [28], *6×9: A Virtual Experience of Solitary Confinement* [29], *After Solitary*
45 *[30]*) 4) **Environmental Issues and Conservation** (*Greenland Melting* [31], *Songbird: A Virtual*
46 *Moment of Extinction* [32], *My Africa* [33], *The Fight to Save Threatened Species* [34], *The Mercury*
47 *Crisis* [35], *Night of the Storm* [36]), 5) **Societal Challenges and Human Experience** (*Becoming*
48 *Homeless: A Human Experience* [37], *First Impressions* [38]).

49 Of the 38 analyzed immersive experiences, the majority (25) were non-interactive 360° videos, 8
50 combined video and computer-generated graphics ("mixed", non-interactive), and only 3 were fully
51 interactive virtual experiences. The remaining 2 were virtual but non-interactive (see. Fig. 1).

52

53 Fig. 1. Number of immersive experiences per year by media type.

54 Most of the analyzed immersive experiences were published on YouTube, primarily via channels
55 affiliated with major media organizations or companies (e.g., Frontline, The Guardian, Within,
56 Alzheimer's Research UK, Nonny de la Peña's 'Emblematic'), while only a few appeared on
57 dedicated VR platforms such as Steam or Oculus (Meta Quest, Rift). The distribution of publication
58 dates reveals a clear peak in 2017, with 19 of the 38 analyzed immersive experiences published in
59 this year. Earlier, in 2016, seven experiences were released, marking the beginning of increased
60 production. Following the peak, production declined significantly (see Fig. 1).

61 The immersive experiences had an average duration of approximately 8 minutes (mean: 7.9 min),
62 ranging from a minimum of 25 seconds to a maximum of around 20 minutes. The majority of
63 experiences were between approximately 6 and 9 minutes long (interquartile range). The analyzed
64 experiences varied greatly in audience engagement, averaging around 395,000 views and 480
65 comments per experience, with significant differences between the most popular (3.7M views, 6,300
66 comments) and the least engaging ones (1,100 views, 0 comments). The median engagement was
67 notably lower, with 86,000 views and 31 comments per experience. A few highly popular
68 experiences significantly skewed the engagement metrics upward.

69 4 Discussion and Conclusion

70 Immersive journalism – one of the crucial perks of the "ultimate empathy machine" - after
71 skyrocketing to the surface of the mainstream, had to quickly hibernate itself (observable rapid
72 decrease of virtual reality journalism creations releases frequency since around the year 2017) until
73 enough medians types would meet the necessary conditions for enabling its ecosystem to form its
74 atmosphere in the mainstream for good. The aforementioned median types include: thresholds of
75 hardware availability, sufficient technical competencies among creators and consumers, ease of use
76 and UX efficiency reducing cognitive load in production and consumption, sufficient internet
77 connection bandwidth speeds, efficiency of 360-degree and stereoscopic video streaming
78 technologies, performance and accessibility of end-user devices, as well as sufficiently low
79 production and consumer costs.

80 Additionally, the high emotional labor required from audiences experiencing intense immersive
81 narratives, insufficient interactivity in most VR content, and limited distribution channels further
82 constrained sustained audience engagement and mainstream adoption.

83 In 2017, limited global internet speeds (median mobile: 20.28 Mbps, fixed broadband: 40.11 Mbps,
84 [39]) restricted seamless streaming of stereoscopic 360° videos (4K at 30 fps required at least 30
85 Mbps), accessible to fewer than 38% of mobile and 56% of fixed broadband users. High-quality VR
86 experiences additionally required expensive hardware (e.g., PCVR setups ~1,800 USD), limiting
87 their audience. By 2025, improved median internet speeds (mobile: 91.5 Mbps, fixed: 99.9 Mbps,
88 [40]), widespread availability of affordable standalone VR devices (Quest 3 at ~500USD, Vision Pro
89 at ~3,500 USD), and efficient streaming methods like tiled adaptive streaming - cutting bandwidth
90 demands by 50–70% - have significantly reduced technical entry barriers.

91 Despite these advancements, rising costs and environmental constraints related to electronic devices
92 production persist. However, transitions toward sustainable manufacturing (Industry 4.0–6.0) and
93 increased use of refurbished or modular hardware indicate a potential path toward more affordable,
94 sustainable, and widespread VR journalism in the future.

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Keeping collaboration along transitions between places in VR

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Keywords: Virtual Reality, Navigation, Transition, Collaboration, Teleportation, Metaverse, Social VR, HCI

1 INTRODUCTION

With Virtual Reality (VR) becoming more available for commercial use, social VR platforms such as *VRChat*, *RecRooms*, *Meta Horizon Worlds* emerged rapidly, shaping what we know today as the *Metaverse* as defined by (Park and Kim, 2022). These platforms enable users to embody different avatars, chat and communicate while freely navigating a wide-variety of virtual environments (VEs) that allowed diverse types of interaction. However, unlike real experiences where groups can collaborate and do different activities as they move from one place to another while maintaining social contact, virtual environments still miss features to preserve social presence and collaboration along navigation. In our work we aim to study group navigation, including both the notions of “going as a group inside one virtual environment” and “going as a group from one environment to a completely different one”. We will therefore design and evaluate new techniques and models of navigation and interaction methods that preserve the sense of group and collaboration.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 Navigation

LaViola et al. (2017) defined Navigation as the process of going from one place to another. This process can be subdivided into two components: Travel and Wayfinding. Travel is the motor component of navigation, the task of moving from the current location to a new target location or moving in the desired direction. On the other hand, Wayfinding is the cognitive process of determining and following a route between an origin and a destination, involving spatial understanding and decision making based on the surrounding environment.

2.2 Group Navigation

We will first discuss real life groups and then explore how they are implemented in VR. A group is defined in its simplest form as “two or more individuals who are connected by and within social relationships” (Forsyth, 2014). One major model to define group behavior is the Tuckman’s Model, (Tuckman, 1965; Tuckman and Jensen, 1977) that broke down the group behavior into different stages starting with the group formation, deciding tasks, splitting responsibilities and performing defined action to achieve the

given task, and finally the group's disassembly. Meanwhile, (Forsyth, 2014) defines ten properties that characterize a group, but these properties are too complex to be used for implicit declaration of groups, for example using an algorithm to assign groups automatically.

When it comes to implementation in VR, (Weissker et al., 2020) proposed the use of Tuckman's Model, while suggesting that the formation and disassembly of the group is connected to the context of the task itself. However, to reduce complexity, most approaches use explicit methods to define the group, mainly by assuming all members of a given session are one group, or using direct invitations. However, some works suggest more dynamic methods to form temporary groups, such as holding hands during navigation to teleport together (Weissker et al., 2022).

Extending from navigation, group navigation can be defined by a group of individuals each navigating by themselves while choosing to stay together while aiming towards the same destination. But, the group can also be considered as one entity that encapsulates all the members, thus to move these members, the group entity is moved as a whole. The latter approach to group definition and navigation is the one used when designing *Group Locomotion Techniques* as found in the literature. These techniques are defined as locomotion methods that expand upon individual locomotion methods by updating the viewpoint of several users and agents at the same time (Brument et al., 2024).

2.2.1 Group Locomotion Techniques

When observing group locomotion techniques in the literature, we can see that artificial locomotion methods, more specifically teleportation-based methods dominate such group locomotion techniques. These methods utilize artificial interactions devoid of any user body movements, such as pressing a button that leads to non-continuous virtual movements which instantaneously update the users' viewpoints Boletsis and Chasanidou (2022). This can be found in the works of (Weissker et al., 2020; Weissker and Froehlich, 2021; Zhang et al., 2022) in which they proposed the use of short-range jumping techniques visualized by ray casting. Similarly, in the works of (Chheang et al., 2022a,b), World-in-Miniature (WiM) techniques were suggested, as the group can see a smaller visualization of the virtual environment and decide where they want to teleport using the WiM. In (Brument et al., 2024), the authors compared a variation of the previous two techniques "jumping raycast" and "WiM teleportation" and proposed the use of a combination of both, allowing participants to utilize any of the two freely. An interesting finding was the use of jumping raycast for covering shorter distances while using WiM for larger distances.

However, although these proposals utilize similar locomotion methods, they differ when it comes to splitting responsibilities and agency between group members. For example some proposals see the group as a vehicle, where one navigator is defined and decides where the group will go, while the rest of the members are passengers that "just" follow Weissker et al. (2020); Weissker and Froehlich (2021); Chheang et al. (2022a,b). In Zhang et al. (2022), the authors compared the navigator-passenger approach with their proposed method that enables collaborators to directly communicate their desired destination resulting in a shared outcome. On the other hand, (Brument et al., 2024) designed group teleportation that relies on the vote of the group members in order to execute the teleportation action. In Zoepfig et al. (2025), authors discussed several confirmation-based group navigation techniques derived from the navigator-passenger approach.

2.2.2 Group Transition

Navigating between two different VEs or greatly separated spaces inside the same VE, is defined as transition in the literature. Various works could be found focusing on individual transitioning methods between environments (Husung and Langbehn, 2019; Lee et al., 2022; Feld et al., 2024), where they

evaluate the sense of presence during the transition, the time-efficiency and physical and cognitive load induced by the transition (Oberdörfer et al., 2018), comparing several transition methods (Men et al., 2017; Feld et al., 2023) and introducing novel ones (Sisto et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2023). However, to the best of our knowledge little to no work addresses group transitioning scenarios, meaning the transition of a whole group of users (as a single entity) from one VE to the other. Recent works such as (Wang et al., 2024) merged two different rooms or scenes in order to connect two collaborators. They Proposed a method to connect two separated individual collaborators. However, moving a group of collaborators together from one VE to the other is still unexplored.

2.3 Collaboration during Navigation

Emerging studies can be found on maintaining collaboration while exploring virtual environments. Xia et al. (2018) suggested a set of tools and methods that facilitate collaboration in virtual environments. Moreover, they suggested a method to request assistance from collaborators, by introducing a technique that allows to request assistance from another collaborator, allowing the other to change viewpoints to be closer to one's own viewpoint, and then easily return to their original work and viewpoint once the assistance was done.

In order to improve the collaboration between two separated collaborators in a large VE, Bimberg et al. (2024) defined a method that enables a pair of collaborators to go from loose collaboration to tight collaboration. Their approach starts with a distant pair in a large VE where no communication is present (loose collaboration), and then describe the stages that will enable the pair to form communication while being distant, and with later stages the one collaborator can join the other by teleportation, helping them and then returning to their original location or not depending on their task.

2.4 Embodiment and Social Presence during Navigation

Avatars (i.e., the digital representations of users in the VE) are important in the Metaverse as one's body is one's spatial reference and is essential to social presence: "people can see me and I can see them" (Heidicker et al., 2017; Aseeri and Interrante, 2021). Both avatar's appearance Casanueva and Blake (2001); Heidicker et al. (2017) and animation (realistic gaze, accurate arm movements) have an effect on social experience during cooperative tasks. However, how they affect social presence during co-navigation or co-teleportation remains unexplored. There are a few results we could use for co-navigation: locomotion methods have little influence on avatar perception Dewez et al. (2020), and avatar positions can be tweaked to smooth the perception of the movement of others Freiwald et al. (2022).

3 FOCUS POINTS OF THE THESIS

3.1 Navigation with the Group

As discussed, many approaches to group navigation choose to follow the navigator-passenger assumption, but we believe that approaches are to be explored and discussed. Moreover, the navigator-passenger approach raises questions about **agency while navigating**. Indeed, although it has been shown that some users are willing to give up some agency during navigation (LaViola et al., 2017), further studies are required to better understand the limits on how constrained or free the collaborators should be.

3.2 Transitions

From what we presented above, to the best of our knowledge, no work has addressed transitions as a group from one VE to the other. Based on that observation, our objectives are: (i) to **design group transition techniques**, (ii) to identify how they can **affect both presence and collaboration**, and (iii) to propose solutions to **improve them by mitigating these effects**.

3.3 Presence and Navigation

Studies on the effect of locomotion on embodiment has shown that relying on teleportation-based methods locomotion can have a negative impact on co-presence Freiwald et al. (2021). Our literature review showed that most group locomotion methods rely on teleportation-based methods of navigation. This motivates our exploration of group locomotion methods that **better preserve co-presence**. In addition, the **effects of group navigation methods on social presence** are still to be studied, opening the possibilities for improving the sense of group during navigation.

3.4 Collaboration and Navigation

Works that look at collaboration during navigation in virtual scenes are emerging, however a lot of questions remain on how to **evaluate collaboration during navigation**, as well as on the **metrics to be monitored** to properly evaluate collaboration within navigating groups. As a consequence, how does **navigation impact collaboration** and how can we **design navigation methods that maintain collaboration**.

4 APPROACH AND METHODS

The initial steps involve **deepening out literature review** to gain a better understanding of navigation in general, and more specifically of group navigation methods, whether it involves transitions between VEs or locomotion within the same environment. The thesis will also explore collaboration during navigation, more specifically on how to model and how to evaluate collaboration between navigating members of a group. In addition, we will examine embodiment and social presence, to find correlations between them and navigation related aspects.

Following that, we will **investigate the current state of commercial solutions** by conducting ethnographic studies on platforms of the Metaverse. These studies aim to better understand the navigation methods currently used by the industry and to identify the gap between practice and research. The studies will also give us insight into what Metaverse users actually use and what they actually need, opening up opportunities for designing new navigation methods.

With design ideas gathered from both the literature review and ethnographic studies, we plan to **conduct experiments** aimed at identifying which navigation features affect collaboration and social presence, drawing connections between them. These insights will help us **formulate design principles and tools** that support collaboration during navigation while minimizing disruptions to social presence and embodiment. Finally, we will **develop appropriate evaluation methods** to assess the techniques we design, and propose practical applications for them.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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**Poster Abstracts 1B : Room “Vicente
Gimeno Sendra”**

Discovering the Metaverse: New Copyright Challenges for User-Generated Content

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6 **Keywords: Metaverse, Intellectual Property, Copyright, User-Generated Content, Authors,**
7 **Users**

8 **Abstract**

9 Much of the online content we experience today is created for us to interact with as users, where we
10 can interact with and share content. However, in recent years, there has been a surge in the number of
11 digital platforms that provide users more opportunities to create content for themselves and to share
12 that content with others. The Metaverse, which has been referred to as a ‘successor to the mobile
13 Internet,’ can become one such platform, and could fundamentally disrupt how we interact online and
14 create digital content by combining both virtual and augmented reality. The traditional role of ‘users’
15 within the creative space may forever be changed, potentially presenting them with greater freedoms
16 and allowing them to become the ‘creators’ of the new virtual landscape. There have already been
17 several concerns regarding the legality of such User-Generated Content on past platforms, and the same
18 questions about ownership of such works and the potential intellectual property rights that may apply
19 can now be asked about content that will be created within the Metaverse. This paper specifically calls
20 into question the extent to which our current approach to copyright law may be suited to User-
21 Generated Content on the Metaverse. Copyright grants creators of original works certain economic and
22 moral rights concerning the commercialisation and distribution of their works, allowing them to
23 prevent actions like the unauthorised copying or modification of their works. Under current laws and
24 on existing platforms, there is a clearer divide between users and creators, though those roles have
25 increasingly begun to overlap in the digital space. The Metaverse will further blur the line between
26 users and creators and may cause further issues regarding the possibility of User-Generated Content
27 infringing upon copyright. This additionally raises challenges concerning how each party’s rights
28 should be balanced, as the rights of the public must always be balanced with the rights of the creator.
29 My research, funded by Science Foundation Ireland under the ADVANCE CRT programme, tackles
30 the challenges presented by User-Generated Content on the Metaverse, examining current content
31 mediums and determining how the systems used to regulate User-Generated Content on them may be
32 applied on the future Metaverse. This involves analysing what the Metaverse will be and how content
33 creation would function; how users will be able to share, create, and contribute content; how this differs
34 from previous mediums of content; and how previous mediums of content have tackled User-Generated
35 Content challenges with copyright law. This will ultimately allow an analysis of how current systems
36 and frameworks for copyright enforcement function, and whether they can be enforced and applied to
37 user creations on the Metaverse. So far, my research has focused on defining what exactly the

38 Metaverse is, and I have begun work on three case studies on existing content mediums to compare the
39 future Metaverse to. My main goal has been the identification of potential copyright challenges
40 centered around User-Generated Content faced by content creators within these content mediums,
41 focusing not only on the practical application of the law within different jurisdictions but also on how
42 legislation might apply in theory. This is to assess the viability of current law and assess the need for
43 reform or development for User-Generated Content more generally, but more specifically in the
44 Metaverse. Doing so during the Metaverse's infancy will allow the law to develop in advance of legal
45 challenges that may arise and ensure the interests of all stakeholders - creators and users alike - will be
46 protected. The Metaverse is a new and potentially disruptive technology, and the technology-neutral
47 approach of much current copyright law may no longer suffice. This research should aid future policy-
48 making decisions and allow analysis of how User-Generated Content should be regulated moving
49 forward.

1 **Virtual Embodiment to Transform Attitudes and Behaviors Toward** 2 **Gender-Based Harassment in the Metaverse**

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16 **Keywords:** metaverse, virtual reality, gender-based harassment, XR, virtual embodiment, empathy,
17 training

18 **Abstract**

19 Gender-based harassment remains a serious issue in contemporary society and is now being mirrored
20 in virtual immersive spaces such as the Metaverse. Studies indicate that XR contexts introduce new
21 forms of harassment due to their unique capabilities. To address this issue, we must develop tools and
22 methods to prevent, mitigate, and raise awareness of harassment, as well as explore potential new risks
23 arising from XR technologies, such as social interactions through the Metaverse, increased presence
24 and haptic feedback.

25 This study examines the use of the Golden Rule Embodiment Paradigm (GREP) and look-alike avatars,
26 which has proven effective in other contexts, such as in racial-bias (Peck et al., 2013; Maister et al.,
27 2015; Banakou et al., 2020) and rehabilitation of gender violent behaviour (Seinfeld et al., 2018; Barnes
28 et al., 2022; Johnston et al., 2022; Seinfeld et al., 2023). GREP is based on the “treat others the way
29 you want them to treat you”, which is achieved by gaining new insights through virtual embodiment.
30 We aim to investigate its potential in addressing gender-based harassment during a job interview in the
31 Metaverse. Additionally, we will compare the effects of embodying a female avatar in a neutral context
32 versus a violent one, and examine how seeing oneself as an accomplice influences the GREP
33 experience.

34 The first session of the experiment is divided into two phases. In the first, participants watch a male
35 colleague harassing a woman during a job interview. In the second, they embody the woman's

36 perspective and experience the harassment directly, seeing their own avatar performing the actions they
37 did in the previous scene. The second session takes place one week later, participants enter a virtual
38 café where the woman, now hired, is harassed again. At key moments, she will appeal directly to the
39 participant, and we expect them to intervene and stop their colleague from harassing her.

40 We expect that GREP will be effective in raising awareness of gender-based violence, particularly
41 among men. Furthermore, using look-alike avatars may enhance empathy and strengthen the impact of
42 GREP. We assume that the experimental group will be more active in the test cafeteria scene than the
43 control group, which will not have experienced the harassment firsthand.

44 In addition to our core design, we have given careful thought to the ethical implications of exposing
45 participants to repeated harassment scenarios and to negative embodiment experiences. All procedures
46 are approved by an institutional review board and include informed consent. Participants will be free
47 to withdraw at any time, and we will provide access to psychological support resources. Baseline data
48 on each participant's prior exposure to gender-based harassment should be obtained, to control for
49 previous trauma when analyzing intervention outcomes.

50 Looking forward, the study anticipates that GREP, particularly when combined with look-alike avatars,
51 will be effective in raising awareness of gender-based violence, especially among men, and will prompt
52 increased intervention from participants in real-time scenarios. This research holds promise for
53 contributing significantly to the development of robust, empathy-driven interventions to combat
54 harassment in the emergent immersive digital world and to develop better attitudes and behaviours that
55 are successfully translated into the real world scenarios.

56 **Conflict of Interest**

57 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
58 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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87

Your Personalized Spielberg Will See You Now: Authorship and Identity in AI-Generated Cinema

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7 **Keywords: Generative AI, Authorship, Copyright Law, Personalized Content, Generative**
8 **Media**

9 **Abstract**

10 In a 2023 interview, director Joe Russo predicted that, within two years, Artificial Intelligence (AI)
11 would be capable of making full-length films tailored to each viewer's preferences—an ultra-
12 personalized cinematic experience rendered in real time. This bold vision of AI-generated cinema,
13 once confined to science fiction, now demands legal and ethical scrutiny.

14 This flash talk explores the consequences of such a development through the lens of Copyright Law,
15 drawing on ongoing research into AI authorship and creative agency. If a film is written, directed,
16 and rendered entirely by an AI—drawing from databases of human-generated content—who is the
17 author of that film? Can there be one? And if every user receives a unique “version” of the film, is
18 each one a distinct copyright work?

19 Building on comparative analysis between UK, US, and EU copyright systems, this talk interrogates
20 whether current legal frameworks are equipped to handle not just the automation of filmmaking, but
21 its fragmentation into individualized experiences. It argues that such works challenge the very idea of
22 a stable, fixed “work”—a cornerstone of Copyright Law—and instead introduce a new paradigm:
23 generative fluidity, where authorship is distributed, ephemeral, and potentially dehumanized.

24 Using both doctrinal tools and speculative examples—including narrative frameworks like Black
25 Mirror's *Joan is Awful*—this talk situates the Joe Russo prediction not as science fiction, but as
26 imminent legal reality. It attempts to propose a rights-based framework for approaching AI-generated
27 film that balances innovation with clarity, protecting both creators and users from the erosion of
28 creative accountability.

29 Ultimately, this intervention invites reflection on a future where everyone gets the movie they
30 want—but perhaps no one knows who made it.

31 **1 Conflict of Interest**

32 *The author declares that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial*
33 *relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.*

34 **2 Author Contributions**

35 [Please included appropriate standard statement]

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AI-enabled crimes and AI-empowered investigations. The role of artificial intelligence in metaverse criminal ecosystems.

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6 **Keywords: AI-enabled crimes, artificial intelligence, metaverse, metaverse crimes**

7 **Abstract**

8 This paper seeks to explore the role of artificial intelligence within the metaverse criminal ecosystem,
9 namely, its dual role as a technology capable of amplifying criminal activities and as a tool providing
10 law enforcement with enhanced opportunities. Given the few examples of virtual crimes became as of
11 today mediatic, the current insidious trend among policymakers is to underestimate the impact of the
12 metaverse in society; however, metaverse crimes exist, and differ from traditional cybercrimes under
13 several dimensions: criminogenic (typology of virtual attack), victimogenic (the role of immersivity
14 and superrealism enhancing the harm suffered by the victim), etiological (the Proteus-effect in the
15 relationship between humans and avatars); and regulatory (lack of specific regulations addressing
16 metaverse crimes). Moreover, within the dichotomic classification of cybercrimes (computer as *tool*
17 vs. computer used *target* of a crime) the plethora of offences committed in the metaverse acquires a
18 new connotation, including crimes causing individual harm, crimes against computer data or systems,
19 threats to national security, and financial crimes: in all these cases, the features of the metaverse are
20 capable of shifting behind-the-screen conducts' level of dangerousness to unprecedented spikes, up to
21 creating a novel 'metaverse criminal ecosystem'. Along with the substantial aspects of criminal law,
22 digital forensics and investigations struggle as well in adapting existing techniques to virtual
23 environments: the hardware-software mix, decrypting users' pseudonymity, blockchain forensics in
24 decentralized platforms: these aspects are capable of creating a multifactorial combination which adds
25 complexity to investigations. This implies the need of revisiting the forensic chain of custody –
26 collection-recovering-analysis-reporting-reconstruction – whose application might require possible
27 adjustments according to the peculiar structure of the metaverse. Furthermore, the advent of artificial
28 intelligence is capable of bringing these considerations to a 'next level': on the one hand, there is
29 evidence of a raising number of AI-enabled crimes, where the exploitation of artificial intelligence
30 tools facilitates the commission of criminal activities such as financial crimes, sexual abuse materials,
31 and other computer crimes – this, in new ways as automated AI, deepfakes and synthetic media, LLMs
32 abuse, and enhanced cyberattacks; on the other hand, AI-driven systems represent valuable instruments

33 for crime prevention (e.g., patterns identification, behavioural prediction, predictive analytics, platform
34 monitoring) and investigation/enforcement (AI-agents, perpetrators' traceability, victims'
35 identification). In conclusion, the paper seeks to explore the yet-unsolved challenges of the metaverse
36 criminal ecosystem, with a deep dive in the role of artificial intelligence as a threat and as a solution.
37 For this reason, further research focusing on the creation of a taxonomy of AI-enabled crimes and AI-
38 empowered investigations appears pivotal.

Use of immersive data by medical practitioners for mental health prevention

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2 ABSTRACT

3 With the growing demand for accessible and scalable mental health care, immersive technologies
4 offer different solutions for prevention and early intervention. This paper presents the preliminary
5 work of a Ph.D. project within the framework of the EU funded THCS project titled Immersive
6 Prevention Centers for Mental Health. This research explores the integration of eXtended Reality
7 (XR) platforms within Immersive Prevention Centers (IPCs) to enhance decision-making with
8 data support in mental health management. It presents a framework that will collect, interpret
9 and visualize behavioral and biometric data to support clinicians in real-time and retrospective
10 reviews of patient activity. By incorporating Machine Learning (ML) and clinically approved
11 scenario design, this project aims to improve early identification, personalize interventions and
12 monitor treatment outcomes in immersive environments. The interdisciplinary approach brings
13 XR, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and clinical expertise together to build a foundation for scalable and
14 interactive mental health support systems.

15 **Keywords:** immersive technology, mental health prevention, extended reality (XR), biometric data, artificial intelligence, co-design,
16 virtual reality, digital health

1 INTRODUCTION

17 Mental health is a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life (WHO,
18 2022). However, mental health disorders affect millions worldwide and access to care remains a challenge
19 due to geographical, financial, and social barriers (Samira Abdul et al., 2024). According to the World
20 Health Organization "Mental Disorders" fact sheet (WHO, 2022), these disorders are characterized by
21 a disturbance in an individual's cognition, emotion regulation, or behavior, often leading to significant
22 distress or impairment in functioning. With rising global awareness of the mental health crisis, there is an
23 urgent need for innovative approaches that enhance prevention, early detection, and patient engagement in
24 mental health interventions.

25 Among emerging solutions, digital health innovations, particularly immersive technologies, have shown
26 promise in transforming how mental health services are delivered. Among these, immersive technologies

27 such as Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR) collectively referred to as
28 eXtended Reality(XR) (Rauschnabel et al., 2022) have opened up new avenues for experiential learning,
29 patient monitoring, and remote intervention (Freeman et al., 2017).

30 Our literature review synthesizes insights from three main research areas: the use of XR in healthcare
31 settings (Worlikar et al., 2023), the integration of mental health management strategies in healthcare
32 organizations (Samira Abdul et al., 2024), and the application of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial
33 Intelligence (AI) to the interpretation of biometric data (Greener et al., 2022).

34 Within XR in health, one of the dimensions most actively explored is its integration into telehealth
35 services (Worlikar et al., 2023). Other Major areas of application include telerehabilitation (Caminero
36 et al., 2025; Isernia et al., 2020), telepsychiatry(Dan Shao, 2020), telediagnosis (Filippeschi et al., 2019),
37 and teleconsultation (Hu et al., 2019) using VR, tementoring, telesurgery (Guo et al., 2016; Kutzin et al.,
38 2017) and telemonitoring (Thøgersen et al., 2020) using MR and AR.

39 Simultaneously, healthcare organizations are beginning to adopt structured mental health management
40 strategies that prioritize early intervention, reduce stigma and encourage scalable, tech-driven approaches to
41 care (Samira Abdul et al., 2024). The main classes of strategies by healthcare organizations are preventive
42 (Colizzi et al., 2020), diagnostic, therapeutic, and supportive measures(Schlak et al., 2022).

43 Furthermore, advances in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) provide new opportunities
44 to interpret biometric and behavioral data collected during digital interventions. These technologies can
45 support real-time assessment of emotional and physiological states, deliver adaptive and personalized
46 interventions, and enable predictive modeling for early crisis detection (Greener et al., 2022). When
47 integrated with XR platforms, ML algorithms can enhance interactivity by adjusting therapeutic content
48 based on user responses, further improving the precision and effectiveness of mental health interventions
49 (Altozano et al., 2025; Lee, 2024).

50 The research presented in this paper is part of a broader project investigating how Immersive Prevention
51 Centers for Mental Health (IPC4MH) within the Metaverse can address the following tasks. IPCs will be
52 providing structured, interactive, and evidence-based prevention programs for mental healthcare. The IPC
53 project focuses on prevention of mental health in two layers. The first is to act on early identification and
54 intervention of mental distress to avoid developing into diagnosable conditions. The second is to avoid the
55 worsening of a diagnosed patient's condition with better supervision of the therapy.

56 This work aims to help medical professionals deliver data-driven mental health interventions in immersive
57 environments, exploring how to best capture, interpret, and apply XR-derived data to support clinicians
58 with real-time insights and structured review data for ongoing patient monitoring and personalized care
59 planning.

2 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

60 Building on the previously outlined context, this project defines a practical and technical roadmap for
61 developing the IPC framework. The overarching goal is to support clinicians in the early identification,
62 intervention, and management of patients' mental health conditions within Immersive Prevention Centers
63 (IPCs). To achieve this, the project aims to create a comprehensive framework for the collection,
64 interpretation, and restitution of data generated from patient activities within XR environments. This
65 framework will ultimately enable the development of a clinician-facing dashboard, providing structured
66 and actionable insights into patients' engagement and progress.

Figure 1. IPC data flow structure

67 The project addresses four main usage scenarios, illustrated in Fig. 1:

- 68 • **Clinician-present activity:** When the clinician is actively supervising a session and assigns an activity
 69 to the patient, real-time data is made available to assist the clinician in monitoring and immediate
 70 assessment.
- 71 • **Clinician-absent activity:** When the clinician assigns an activity (either individual or group-based)
 72 but is not present during its execution, patient data is collected and securely stored for later review.
- 73 • **Individual review sessions:** During subsequent consultations, clinicians can access and review the
 74 data collected over time to evaluate the patient's progress and to adjust therapeutic interventions
 75 accordingly.
- 76 • **Additional annotations:** Clinicians may also add notes or complete questionnaires through the
 77 dashboard interface. While this feature enhances patient monitoring, it involves handling highly
 78 sensitive personal information and thus requires strict privacy safeguards.

79 To translate this vision into practice, the project is structured around three key objectives that drive both
 80 clinical and technical development:

81 **Objective 1: extract behavioral and biometric data from IPC**

82 Data will be collected from immersive activities in IPCs using various modules. Patients will use Head-
 83 Mounted Displays (HMD) with possible add-ons for eye tracking or EEG. They can also use tablets or
 84 web platforms. Data collection must operate across multiple scenarios, in group or solo, and diverse tasks,

85 mental or physical, to ensure robustness. The goal is to capture detailed behavioral and biometric indicators
86 including posture (Caminero et al., 2025), movement dynamics (Duvivier et al., 2021), micro-gestures
87 (Step toe and Steed, 2012), attention shifts and physiological responses. Automation of collection and
88 pre-processing pipelines need to be emphasized to support future clinical scalability and integration into
89 time-constrained environments. While collecting this data is important, ensuring its clinical relevance is
90 equally important.

91 **Objective 2: determine clinically relevant indicators for mental health professionals**

92 Focus groups and structured interviews are used to determine what types of behavioral or biometric data
93 can serve mental health professional diagnostic and therapeutic goals such as in Felsberg et al. (2025) or
94 Dan Shao et al. (2020) (Felsberg et al., 2025; Dan Shao, 2020). The aim is to translate clinical needs into
95 computational targets. For example, using movement entropy (Altozano et al., 2025), gesture fluency, or
96 stress-related gaze patterns as proxies for mental state (Bell et al., 2020). This involves not only feature
97 engineering but statistical correlation studies and machine learning modeling (Random Trees, CNNs,
98 LSTMs) with end-to-end models or hand-crafted features to identify, validate, and prioritize indicators
99 (Altozano et al., 2025). The indicators must be both grounded in clinical theory and practically interpretable
100 to support tasks such as symptom screening, subtype stratification (Alvari et al., 2024), or progress
101 monitoring. Once relevant indicators are identified, the next step is to design a system that clinicians can
102 intuitively use to make informed decisions.

103 **Objective 3: develop a clinician-oriented framework for the visualization and review of patient data**

104 The final objective is to support the clinician's decision-making and intervention process with a structured
105 and interpretable data interface. This includes building a dashboard tool that offers real-time visualizations
106 during live sessions and retrospective views of patient behavior for asynchronous review. The system
107 will incorporate tools to annotate sessions, view trends, and optionally integrate sensitive data such as
108 questionnaires or notes. A User-Centered Approach (UCA) (Kutzin et al., 2017; Filippeschi et al., 2019)
109 will guide the design of HMD and tablet compatible modules to ensure usability, interpretability, and
110 seamless integration into clinical workflows.

3 METHODS

111 This project adopts a mixed-methods approach, beginning with an interdisciplinary literature review
112 and iterative stakeholder engagement. These foundational steps will inform the design of structured
113 scenarios and guide the development of a data-oriented framework for IPCs. This framework will enable
114 the systematic collection, interpretation, and restitution of behavioral and biometric data generated during
115 XR-based mental health interventions.

116 **3.1 Literature Review**

117 The literature review will focus on three intersecting domains: (1) the use of XR technologies in healthcare
118 settings (Worlikar et al., 2023), (2) strategies for managing mental health in clinical practice (Samira
119 Abdul et al., 2024), and (3) the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)
120 for analyzing biometric data (Greener et al., 2022; Altozano et al., 2025). This review will provide both
121 theoretical grounding and empirical insights for the project.

122 Primary academic databases such as PubMed and Google Scholar will be used to ensure comprehensive
123 coverage of relevant literature. The review will also incorporate existing research on immersive telehealth

124 platforms, including the work by Prié et al., *A Teleclinic for Neuro-psychological Assessment in the
125 Metaverse* (Prié et al., 2025), which provides a foundational model for XR-based clinical environments.

126 The outcome of the review will be a consolidated list of relevant behavioral and biometric indicators that
127 can be integrated into IPC scenarios. These indicators will serve as a basis for establishing a structured and
128 continuous dialogue with mental health professionals, ensuring clinical relevance and facilitating co-design
129 of XR interventions.

130 3.2 Dialogue with mental healthcare professionals

131 To ensure clinical relevance and usability healthcare professionals will be engaged throughout the project
132 via focus groups and semi-structured interviews. Focus groups will be conducted with professionals from
133 different fields within mental health such as child psychiatrists, psychomotricians and nurses. During
134 these we will be able to discuss their experiences with the mental health system, current workflow, digital
135 mental health tools, current diagnostic gaps and the perceived potential of IPCs. In parallel, individual
136 semi-structured interviews will allow deeper analysis and case by case study of the data necessity of the
137 clinician's field. Insights gathered from this ongoing engagement will directly inform the development of
138 the data framework.

139 3.3 Framework development for data collection

140 Based on the two previous subsections, a framework for data collection will be co-developed in iteration
141 with the clinicians to specify the types of information recorded, the methods of collection and their
142 relevance to mental health monitoring. Data will be collected via a standard HMD with hand tracking
143 and an integrated eye tracking system. These data are based on a project that we did previously using
144 the Unity game development framework and either the XRIntegration Toolkit or the Oculus Integration
145 Toolkit packages. With the technical infrastructure in place, the project will advance to design and validate
146 scenario-based tasks tailored to elicit clinically meaningful responses.

147 3.4 Scenario development with practitioners

148 As shown in Table 1, Scenario-based design will ensure the ecological and diagnostic validity of the
149 data collected through tasks within the IPC. These scenarios are tailored to elicit data relevant to early
150 screening, symptom monitoring, and stratification of mental health conditions.

Scenario	Description	Data Captured	Clinical Use
Social Stress Simulation	Patient navigates a virtual group conversation	Gaze aversion, voice tremor, body motion	Detection of social anxiety and avoidance behavior
Cognitive Flexibility Task	Color-word Stroop test in immersive form	Response time, error rate, hesitations	Executive dysfunction, attention deficits
Virtual Interview	Semi-structured avatar-led conversation	Facial affect, verbal fluency, eye contact	Indicators of depression or psychomotor slowing

Table 1. Examples of clinician-designed scenarios for IPC environments

151 To further anchor these scenarios in validated clinical practice, psychometric tools such as the **PHQ-**
152 **9 (Patient Health Questionnaire-9) (Ford et al., 2020)**, **GAD-7 (Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7)**
153 **(Spitzer et al., 2006)**, **BDI (Beck Depression Inventory) (Osman et al., 2004)**, and **STAI (State-Trait**

154 **Anxiety Inventory) (Julian, 2011)** will be integrated into the scenarios as either pre-session screening
155 or post-session reflective assessments. These tools first serve to get a baseline on self-reported symptoms
156 against behavioral and biometric data. On a second note, they are here to evaluate whether immersive tasks
157 provoke consistent responses in individuals with known profiles.

158 Altogether, these steps are setting the groundwork for a structured, clinician-informed framework
159 that supports immersive mental health prevention through XR-based data collection, interpretation, and
160 restitution.

CONCLUSION

161 This research is part of a broader exploration of how IPCs can play a transformative role in mental healthcare
162 by combining XR environments with clinically relevant data workflows. The aim is to enhance early
163 intervention and therapeutic support and to bridge the gap between clinicians and immersive technologies
164 with interpretable insights derived from real-time or ongoing behavioral and biometric inputs. The process
165 will engage iteratively with mental health professionals, from indicator selection to scenario and dashboard
166 interface design, this work will link clinicians and their workflows while building toward scalable and
167 adaptive digital care tools. Through the integration of XR technologies and data-driven dashboards, the
168 project seeks to create a structured framework that supports individualized care and broader mental health
169 prevention strategies.

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Session 3: Clinical and well-being applications of the Metaverse

Immersive Prevention Centers for Mental Health: Secondary and Tertiary Prevention in the Metaverse

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Mental health systems across Europe face persistent challenges in accessibility, resource
4 limitations, and stigma. Vulnerable populations such as adolescents with neurodevelopmental
5 disorders and older adults at risk of depression often fall through the cracks of existing care
6 structures. The IPC4MH (Immersive Prevention Centers for Mental Health) project proposes
7 an innovative solution: immersive prevention centers built within the Metaverse, designed for
8 secondary and tertiary mental health prevention. Through interdisciplinary collaboration, the
9 project aims to co-design, implement, and evaluate scalable, engaging, and inclusive virtual
10 environments that support early intervention and long-term mental health care. This paper
11 presents the conceptual foundation, objectives, research direction, and methodological approach
12 of IPC4MH.

13 **Keywords:** immersive technology, virtual reality, mental health prevention, Metaverse, co-design, digital health, neurodevelopmental
14 disorders, aging

1 INTRODUCTION

15 Mental health services across Europe are struggling to keep pace with the rising burden of psychological
16 disorders. Limited availability of professionals, logistical barriers to in-person care, and widespread stigma
17 result in significant disparities in access—particularly among youth with neurodevelopmental conditions
18 and seniors facing isolation or cognitive decline. These challenges demand innovative responses that
19 leverage emerging technologies while remaining grounded in evidence-based care practices.

20 Virtual reality (VR) has already demonstrated clinical efficacy for applications such as cognitive training,
21 exposure therapy, and rehabilitation (Maples-Keller et al., 2017; Freeman et al., 2017). A growing body of
22 research confirms its utility in reducing anxiety, improving cognitive performance, and fostering behavioral
23 change across clinical populations (Romero-Ayuso et al., 2021). More recently, the evolution of social
24 VR and the broader Metaverse has introduced novel opportunities for healthcare delivery—providing
25 persistent, shared, and interactive environments that overcome traditional barriers such as geographic
26 isolation or stigma (Cerasa et al., 2024). Notably, we have introduced the idea of teleclinics in the Metaverse,
27 implementing an example of a teleclinic for neuro-psychological assessment Vigier et al. (2024). The
28 IPC4MH project builds upon this technological and empirical foundations by designing and evaluating
29 immersive prevention centers that enable both early intervention and sustained therapeutic engagement for
30 populations often underserved by conventional services.

2 FRAMING THE NEED: PREVENTION IN MENTAL HEALTH

31 In public health, mental health prevention is typically structured into three levels: primary (avoiding onset),
32 secondary (early identification and intervention), and tertiary (managing existing conditions to prevent
33 deterioration) Baumann and Ylinen (2020). IPC4MH focuses on the latter two.

34 Secondary prevention addresses the early signs of mental distress—such as anxiety, withdrawal, or
35 difficulties in social interaction—before they evolve into diagnosable conditions. Immersive prevention
36 centers might be especially relevant for adolescents who may struggle with communication or behavioral
37 issues that are not yet formally recognized. For example, a teenager exhibiting signs of social withdrawal
38 or concentration difficulties in a school setting might participate in a VR-based screening activity followed
39 by a series of interactive group sessions designed to foster self-expression and social confidence. Similarly,
40 older adults experiencing mild forgetfulness or increased isolation may benefit from cognitive stimulation
41 exercises within immersive environments, combined with gentle mood assessments and social interaction
42 features to support early detection of cognitive decline or depression.

43 Tertiary prevention, meanwhile, focuses on patients with known diagnoses, offering structured support
44 that reduces the risk of relapse and improves quality of life. An adolescent diagnosed with an autism
45 spectrum disorder might for example engage in immersive role-playing scenarios that help build emotional
46 regulation and social interaction skills under the supervision of a therapist. Older adults with a history
47 of major depressive episodes or diagnosed mild cognitive impairment could benefit from long-term
48 participation in guided group activities, memory games, and virtual peer support meetings, helping to
49 reinforce emotional wellbeing, cognitive function, and a sense of connectedness.

50 By embedding both prevention levels into immersive, user-friendly platforms, IPC4MH aims to make
51 proactive care not only accessible, but appealing and engaging.

3 EXISTING INITIATIVES

52 While immersive technologies are increasingly explored in mental health, few initiatives have targeted
53 prevention with the same focus and transnational scope as IPC4MH. However, several existing projects
54 and platforms offer valuable context.

55 One notable example is XRHealth, which offers virtual reality therapy platforms for pain management,
56 rehabilitation, and mental health, including anxiety and stress relief (<https://xr.health>). Their clinical VR

57 applications are used primarily in therapeutic settings with healthcare professionals and do not yet extend
58 to public prevention or peer-led support.

59 Another significant effort is that of C2Care, a French company and IPC4MH partner, which provides
60 VR-based exposure therapy environments for phobias, depression, and cognitive training Cerda et al.
61 (2021). These environments are already used in over 500 clinics but are currently deployed in isolated
62 clinical contexts rather than networked prevention centers. IPC4MH builds on this by transforming such
63 tools into socially connected, preventive, and multi-user platforms.

64 Tecnis, a recent French project led by Nantes University, created a prototype of an immersive teleclinic
65 for neuropsychological assessment Prié et al. (2025). While pioneering in its design and testing, it focused
66 on individual diagnostics rather than ongoing preventive care. IPC4MH uses Tecnis as a foundation and
67 extends its functionality toward collaborative, preventive, and long-term interventions.

68 In the realm of social VR, projects like VR4REHAB Green et al. (2019), AccessVR or Bridges El Raheb
69 et al. (2021) have also investigated the use of immersive environments for rehabilitation and emotional
70 regulation. These initiatives have demonstrated the feasibility and acceptability of virtual therapies but
71 have not yet addressed structural integration into public health prevention strategies.

72 By contrast, IPC4MH aims to institutionalize immersive prevention by creating modular, evidence-based
73 platforms deployed in both home and public spaces and evaluated through mixed-method clinical trials. Its
74 dual focus on underserved populations and the integration of secondary and tertiary prevention makes it a
75 novel and impactful initiative in the evolving landscape of digital mental health.

4 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

76 IPC4MH seeks to create, validate, and prepare for scale-up immersive prevention centers deployed
77 within the Metaverse. To achieve this vision, the project aims to develop a flexible digital platform
78 that incorporates existing VR therapeutic content into user-friendly teleclinics, complete with social
79 and therapeutic functionalities. These centers will be specifically designed for two key target groups
80 —adolescents and older adults— through a collaborative and inclusive co-design process involving
81 clinicians, researchers, and end users. Implementation will take place across three European countries
82 —Switzerland, France, and Poland— allowing for comparative evaluation of usability, clinical impact,
83 and user satisfaction in varied socio-cultural contexts. A rigorous mixed-methods framework will be used
84 to assess clinical efficacy, combining quantitative and qualitative data to capture both measurable outcomes
85 and user experiences. In parallel, the project will produce guidelines and scalable business models to
86 facilitate long-term integration into national health systems and public spaces, ensuring both sustainability
87 and broader impact.

5 RESEARCH DIRECTION

88 The project's research agenda spans four interdependent axes: technological infrastructure, human-centered
89 design, clinical validation, and policy integration.

90 On the technological front, IPC4MH will define and implement a modular architecture based on open
91 standards (e.g., OpenXR) to ensure interoperability across devices and platforms. The system will include
92 secure communication tools, user monitoring systems, and interfaces for integrating diverse therapeutic
93 content. The goal is to create an extensible platform where practitioners can meet with users, guide sessions,
94 and monitor progress.

95 Within IPC4MH, artificial intelligence (AI) serves as a decision-support layer by analyzing structured
96 interaction data—such as session frequency, duration, and trajectories of improvement in standardized
97 clinical scores (e.g., PHQ-9, GAD-7). Rather than replacing human judgment, AI models will synthesize
98 these usage patterns to generate interpretable insights, which are integrated directly into therapist
99 dashboards. This allows clinicians to monitor individual progress, detect early signs of disengagement or
100 stagnation, and tailor intervention strategies accordingly. The focus on transparent, explainable outputs
101 ensures that AI serves to augment—not obscure—clinical reasoning. This integration supports a hybrid
102 model of care, where immersive environments and professional supervision are dynamically coordinated to
103 maximize the effectiveness and responsiveness of prevention efforts.

104 From a design perspective, immersive scenarios and environments will be co-designed with input from
105 stakeholders, using ethnographic methods and participatory design workshops. Care workflows will be
106 based on activities that are carried out both in virtual (immersive center) and in real (physical prevention
107 hubs) world, be it solo activities, peer-supported interactions, supervised group therapy, meetings with
108 practitioners, etc.

109 Clinically, the project aims to measure how IPCs affect mental health literacy and user engagement.
110 Metrics will include validated psychological scales (e.g., PHQ-9, GAD-7), behavioral analytics, and
111 analysis of qualitative interviews. Evaluations will compare different usage patterns (e.g., home-based vs.
112 onsite), prevention levels (secondary vs. tertiary), and demographic subgroups.

113 Finally, IPC4MH examines the socio-economic, ethical, and regulatory dimensions of deploying virtual
114 prevention centers at scale. It will develop frameworks for integration into national health systems and
115 explore sustainable public-private models for ongoing delivery and support.

6 METHOD

116 The project adopts a multi-phase, interdisciplinary methodology.

117 **Phase 1: Co-Design and Prototyping** — Initial work will involve mapping out user journeys, defining
118 clinical and technical requirements, and adapting existing VR content for shared use. Iterative prototyping
119 with feedback loops from patients and professionals will drive continuous refinement.

120 **Phase 2: Implementation and Evaluation** — Prevention centers will be rolled out across three pilot sites,
121 with 20–30 participants per site engaged in either secondary or tertiary prevention activities. Evaluation will
122 cover usability (System Usability Scale), acceptability (Technology Acceptance Model), clinical outcomes
123 (standardized scales), and engagement (interaction logs).

124 **Phase 3: Scale-Up and Dissemination** — Lessons from the evaluation phase will inform the design of
125 integration pathways, economic models, and policy recommendations. Open-access tools, datasets, and
126 documentation will ensure reproducibility and impact beyond the project consortium.

7 EARLY RESULTS

127 Preliminary activities carried out during the first project phase have yielded promising insights. A co-
128 design workshop held in France (3-4 April 25) with consortium members provided early reflections on the
129 concept of immersive prevention centers. Participants expressed enthusiasm about the potential for peer
130 interaction and creative self-expression in virtual environments. Discussions also highlighted the necessity

131 of structured, clinically validated content and raised important concerns related to data protection and
132 ethical oversight.

133 Initial technical assessments of partner VR platforms, including those from DiverSSity and C2Care,
134 indicated that existing tools could be adapted to suit group-based use cases. Usability testing on early
135 prototypes demonstrated acceptable user performance on navigation and task completion tasks across
136 both target demographics. Participants appreciated the calming environment designs and the ability to
137 personalize avatars, which contributed to perceived presence and comfort.

138 These early findings confirm both the feasibility and the relevance of IPC4MH's core hypothesis: that
139 immersive virtual environments can serve as effective platforms for mental health prevention. The team is
140 now moving forward with refining the system's architecture and preparing for full-scale pilot evaluations.

8 CONCLUSION

141 The IPC4MH project represents a bold step toward the future of preventive mental health care. By merging
142 immersive technologies with inclusive design and rigorous clinical evaluation, it aims to create prevention
143 pathways that are engaging, scalable, and equitable. As health systems seek new strategies to meet rising
144 mental health needs, IPCs may offer a replicable model for delivering care across digital and physical
145 boundaries—reaching people where they are, before it's too late.

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Towards affective and personalized mixed reality experiences for mental health

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ABSTRACT

Extended Reality technologies are rapidly transforming healthcare, particularly in the domain of mental health. As immersive systems mature, they offer powerful tools to enhance therapeutic interventions through increased presence, emotional engagement, and accessibility. However, existing XR solutions for mental health often lack dynamic personalization, limiting their effectiveness in addressing individual emotional needs. This paper explores how the integration of Artificial Intelligence, biofeedback, and context-aware interaction mechanisms can overcome these limitations and enable emotionally adaptive, personalized XR interventions. We present several examples of Mixed Reality platforms developed for emotional regulation and remote collaborative therapy, and explore how generative AI, biometric feedback, and real-world object recognition can be leveraged to build the foundations of a mental health metaverse.

Keywords: Mixed Reality, Metaverse, Mental Health, Remote Therapy, Biofeedback, Artificial Intelligence, Generative AI, Object Recognition

1 INTRODUCTION

Extended Reality (XR) technologies, encompassing Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR) (Milgram and Kishino, 1994; Speicher et al., 2019; Skarbez et al., 2021), have shown promise in improving the quality of care across various domains of healthcare: offering realistic simulations for surgical training and medical procedures (Toni et al., 2024; Herur-Raman et al., 2021; Andrews et al., 2019), supporting patient care practice (Zweifach and Triola, 2019; Lee et al., 2024), providing immersive experiences for pain management (Indovina et al., 2018; Phelan et al., 2021), and creating motivating scenarios for physical rehabilitation (Grabowski, 2025; Villada Castillo et al., 2024).

Recently, mental health and wellbeing have been gaining increased acknowledgement on their vital role in global health, and its impact on socio-economic conditions and the global burden of disease (WHO, 2022). Within this context, XR's immersive and engaging nature makes it a compelling complement to traditional therapies, supporting treatments like exposure therapy (Gutierrez-Maldonado et al., 2023; Freeman et al., 2022; Lundin et al., 2022; Giraldy and Novaldo, 2022), cognitive behavioural therapy, mindfulness practices (Amores et al., 2019; Modrego-Alarcón et al., 2023; Hanna et al., 2025) or emotional regulation strategies (Macey et al., 2022; Soler-Dominguez et al., 2024; Wagener and Niess, 2021).

Despite these advances, many XR mental health applications lack personalization, often delivering one-size-fits-all experiences that fail to reflect individual needs, preferences, or emotional states. There has been some related work that has explored early attempts at customization and automation of these environments (Freeman et al., 2018), but much work remains to be done to achieve a degree of adaptability to suit the wide variety of real needs and experiences. The absence of this kind of personalization in current XR systems can limit the effectiveness of interventions, especially when addressing the nuanced and heterogeneous nature of mental health conditions (Bennett and Shafran, 2022; Hornstein et al., 2023).

In this regard, Artificial Intelligence (AI) applied to XR presents a promising path to overcoming these limitations. AI has already shown potential in mental health through chatbots, diagnostic support systems, and emotion recognition algorithms. Integrating AI into XR environments could facilitate deeply personalized, context-aware, and emotionally intelligent therapeutic experiences. AI-driven XR systems could dynamically adjust scenarios based on real-time biometric feedback, user preferences or therapists input, offering users tailored interactions that evolve with their mental health needs.

In this paper, we explore the intersection of XR and AI in mental health, examining current use cases, technological challenges, and the potential for AI-enhanced XR to create the next generation of responsive, affective, and personalized mental health interventions.

2 XR FOR AFFECTIVE AND PERSONALIZED MENTAL HEALTHCARE

2.1 Advancing Mental Health Interventions Through Mixed Reality

VR has proven effective for mental health interventions like exposure therapy and mindfulness by providing immersive, controlled environments. However, its fully immersive nature can be a drawback in some scenarios, as it disconnects users from their surroundings, which may be unsuitable for some therapeutic contexts where environmental awareness, embodiment, and real-world cues play a critical role. In addition, VR may not be the preferred interaction modality for people who are more vulnerable or who need to have visual contact with their therapist or reference person. Issues such as visual-induced motion sickness (VIMS) (Bos et al., 2008; Geszten et al., 2018) and accessibility limitations also present challenges, particularly for vulnerable populations (Kim et al., 2021).

In this context, MR emerges as a promising complementary tool when using immersive technology for mental health care (Pons et al., 2022). Unlike traditional VR, where users are fully immersed in a separate, digital world, MR overlays interactive digital content onto the physical space around them, which reduces VIMS problems while allowing for interactive, situated experiences that maintain the user's connection to the real world. This allows therapy to occur in familiar settings, such as a home or clinic, surrounded by familiar people and objects, therefore enhancing comfort, which is especially important when dealing with sensitive mental health topics. Moreover, MR reduces the psychological distance between therapy and everyday life. Instead of needing to "step out" of reality to engage with therapeutic content, users can bring therapeutic interactions into their daily context. This blending of real and virtual elements makes it easier to integrate therapeutic exercises into real-life situations, which can increase relevance and make it more likely that the strategies learned will carry over into everyday behavior.

While VR has seen growing adoption in mental health applications, MR remains significantly underexplored in this domain, with only a limited number of studies and systems addressing its unique potential to integrate therapeutic content into users' real-world environments. In our previous work, we have explored the application of MR in mental health through the development of ARCADIA (Soler-Dominguez

Figure 1. Emotional Avatar.

Figure 2. Breathing activity.

Figure 3. Emotion recognition activity.

Figure 4. Animal Therapy.

Figure 5. Therapeutic activities of the ARCADIA platform running on a MR headset

et al., 2024; García-Ballesteros et al., 2024), a MR system co-designed with mental health professionals to support emotional regulation through gamified therapeutic activities. ARCADIA centers around the metaphor of a virtual garden that reflects the user's therapeutic progress, with a modular architecture that allows for future expansion beyond emotional regulation. Currently, ARCADIA includes four interactive experiences: 1) mindful breathing: through a respiration sensor, users find themselves in a meadow with flowers that slowly bloom as they inhale and exhale, 2) intrusive thoughts: users reflect on rumination, externalizing intrusive thoughts by writing them in the air, and then disposing them in a fire pit, 3) emotion identification: facilitates emotion identification using visual metaphors such as creatures representing each of the six basic emotions, and 4) animal therapy: users can choose between different virtual animals and actions, such as petting them feeding, brushing or playing with them. These four activities are designed to foster engagement, reflection, and emotional self-awareness in immersive, context-rich environments.

The user studies conducted with ARCADIA focused on user experience with both mental health professionals and users of mental health services (Soler-Dominguez et al., 2024; García-Ballesteros et al., 2024), revealing that participants found the system engaging, motivating, and helpful for emotional regulation. for managing emotional states. These findings highlight the potential of MR to create immersive yet grounded therapeutic experiences that adapt to real-world contexts. By blending digital content with users' physical environments, MR offers a powerful platform for advancing mental health care.

2.2 The Mental Health Metaverse: Supporting Remote and Collaborative Therapy through Mixed Reality

As XR technologies continue to evolve and integrate with socially connected virtual spaces, the idea of a mental health metaverse is taking shape (Navas-Medrano et al., 2024; Cerasa et al., 2024; López del

Hoyo et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2025). This concept describes a network of immersive digital environments focused on supporting mental wellbeing. Within this space, people could attend therapy sessions remotely, explore guided mental health exercises, or connect with others in shared support communities, no matter where they are physically located. Unlike traditional teletherapy or isolated VR apps, the mental health metaverse offers a continuous and unified experience. Users can maintain persistent virtual identities and engage in real-time interactions with therapists and peers, making mental health care more accessible and collaborative (Fajnerova et al., 2024).

One of the most promising applications of the mental health metaverse is remote therapy, where a therapist and a patient can meet in a shared, hybrid space regardless of physical distance. Unlike standard video calls, XR allows both parties to interact with the same virtual objects and environments in real time, enhancing engagement and relational presence. In this way, the mental health metaverse would help overcome longstanding barriers to care. On one hand, it could increase accessibility by removing geographic and physical limitations (Palomin et al., 2023), facilitating access to mental health services for people who are physically unable to move around easily, or people who live far from health care centers (Altaf Dar et al., 2023; Hendl and Shukla, 2024). On the other hand, it could also help reduce barriers associated with stigma (Hazell et al., 2022; Mezuk et al., 2020), by allowing private participation of users from the comfort of their own familiar environment. Furthermore, incorporating at-home XR therapy exercises can alleviate the burden on healthcare facilities, decrease waiting times, and optimise resource utilisation within the mental health system (Bratt and Kalmendal, 2023).

Beyond one-on-one sessions, XR also supports multiuser collaborative environments that can facilitate group therapy. Whether participants are co-located or connecting remotely, XR enables shared, interactive therapeutic scenarios where users can practice social skills, reflect together, or engage in mindfulness activities in a co-created space. These collaborative features can reduce the isolation often associated with mental health struggles, while preserving the benefits of guided intervention. Remote collaborative activities could be mediated by the use of avatars, that will be displayed by the in the real environment of each participant. In-person group therapies will involve participants in the same physical spaces, some or all of them wearing XR headsets in which the same digital scenario is shared.

To explore the potential of the mental health metaverse, we developed CORE-MHC, a MR platform designed to support real-time therapy between clinicians and patients. This system enables therapists to participate in sessions either via a traditional desktop interface or through an MR headset, while the patient consistently engages through MR hardware to ensure immersive and embodied interaction. The dual-mode access for therapists is designed to increase the inclusivity and flexibility of care delivery, adapting to the technological capabilities and preferences of the healthcare provider while maintaining continuity in the patient's experience.

Once both parties are connected in the MR environment, the therapist guides the patient through the therapeutic activity, while visualizing biometric data from the patient captured through wearable sensors. These biofeedback metrics, such as heart rate or respiratory patterns, allow for continuous monitoring of the patient's emotional and physiological state throughout the session. When both therapist and patient are immersed via MR headsets, they are represented by dynamic avatars and can co-interact with shared augmented objects within the virtual space, despite being in geographically separate physical locations. This infrastructure not only enhances therapeutic alliance and engagement but also opens the door to the integration of biofeedback-driven interventions for more adaptive experiences.

Figure 6. CORE-MHC system: therapist and patient view during the collaborative activity.

2.3 Biofeedback: Enhancing Self-Awareness and Adaptive Interventions

Incorporating biofeedback into XR environments creates the foundation for more responsive, emotionally intelligent experiences. By collecting real-time physiological signals such as heart rate, respiration, or skin conductance, systems can infer the user's stress levels, emotional arousal, or attentional focus. This data can then be used to dynamically adapt the experience, adjusting the level of challenge, feedback, or pacing based on the user's current state.

For example, in the breathing activity developed for ARCADIA (Fig. 2), a respiration sensor was used to guide a mindfulness experience where a withered digital meadow gradually transforms as the user focuses on their breath. The visual feedback, delayed and subtle, reinforces the calming effect of deep breathing while avoiding over-stimulation. The experience is further enhanced with the introduction of an emotional avatar (Fig. 1): a dynamic, embodied representation of the user's internal state within the MR space, whose form and behavior respond in real time to biofeedback signals such as heart rate and breath rhythm variability. This avatar provides a tangible, visualized extension of their inner experience, helping users build emotional self-awareness by externalizing the physiological state in a gentle, interpretable way. Another example of biofeedback-driven XR are Emo-regulator (Yu et al., 2023), an emotion-regulation training system that uses VR and EEG-based neurofeedback. Results shown improved emotion regulation ability and above-average usability after using the system for 2 weeks. Applications like the DEEP VR game (Bossenbroek et al., 2020) utilise biofeedback to monitor physiological responses such as heart rate and breathing patterns. These real-time metrics are then used to adjust the virtual environment, promoting relaxation and teaching users how to regulate their physiological responses to stress. The work in (Amores et al., 2019) focused on internal reflection, developing a VR environment that procedurally generates 3D creatures, and changes the lighting of the environment to reflect users' internal state based on EEG, EDA and HR.

Looking ahead, the integration of biofeedback with AI-driven emotion recognition models holds the potential to further individualize therapeutic interventions. These systems could detect states such as anxiety, frustration, or relaxation, that automatically adjust the XR environment to support the user's needs, such as modulating visual complexity, soundscapes, or the intensity of therapeutic challenges. For example, in moments of heightened arousal, the system might reduce environmental stimuli, simplify

interaction demands, or introduce grounding cues. Conversely, during states of low engagement, it may introduce gently challenging tasks or more vibrant sensory elements. Through this feedback mechanism, XR experiences can move towards emotionally adaptive mental health systems that respond with empathy and precision to each user's unique journey.

2.4 Generative AI for Personalized XR Environments

Generative AI offers unprecedented possibilities for personalizing mental health experiences in XR, creating content that adapts in real time to the user's needs, evolving preferences, and emotional state. By incorporating real-time biofeedback and interaction data, generative systems can craft therapeutic experiences that are not only immersive but also deeply resonant on an individual level.

One powerful application could be the generation of adaptive narratives. In gamified therapeutic MR scenarios, generative models can tailor the narrative flow according to the user's progress, emotional responses, or interaction patterns. Rather than following a fixed script, the storyline can branch dynamically, offering challenges, metaphors, or interactions that feel meaningful and therapeutically aligned with the individual. This responsiveness can enhance user engagement and facilitate deeper personal reflection within the immersive context.

Another promising direction is the real-time generation of 3D objects (Liu et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2024; Wong et al., 2022) that reflect personal symbols, memories, or therapeutic goals. A user working on anxiety management might summon calming objects linked to positive experiences, or modify the environment to represent a physical location that the user considers as a safe space or a place of relaxation, i.e. a beach, a forest, the village house of their childhood.

Sound generation adds another critical layer of personalization (Nguyen et al., 2024; Picinali et al., 2022). Through generative audio models, ambient soundscapes, binaural beats, or music can be created in real time to support the user's desired emotional state or therapeutic activity. Whether designed to ground a user during moments of stress, uplift during depressive states, or deepen focus during mindfulness exercises, these responsive auditory elements serve as powerful emotional modulators, enhancing presence and co-regulating mood.

The integration of conversational avatars powered by large language models (LLMs) could also offer promising opportunities for tailored interventions (Ma et al., 2023; Jo et al., 2023). These virtual companions could engage users in natural dialogue, guiding them through personalized mindfulness exercises, checking in on emotional states, or serving as virtual therapeutic companions. When integrated with biofeedback data and user interaction histories, these avatars could adapt their tone, content, and strategy to suit the evolving context of the session. For instance, an avatar may adjust the pacing of a guided breathing exercise based on real-time respiration data, or shift to a more supportive tone when signs of distress are detected. These AI-driven interactions can be deeply individualized, leveraging historical interaction data and biofeedback to provide nuanced, supportive dialogue that evolves with the user over time.

Yet, for these systems to achieve deeper ecological validity and therapeutic relevance, they must also be able to interpret and respond to the user's physical environment. By combining biofeedback with contextual awareness, MR systems can foster a more holistic therapeutic experience.

2.5 Context-Aware Interactions Through Object Recognition in MR

To create truly seamless and context-sensitive MR experiences, recognizing and responding to the physical environment is essential. Object recognition is a key capability that enables MR systems to identify

real-world items such as furniture, specific objects or personal belongings, and use them as anchors for interactive experiences. The implementation of object recognition in XR-based therapeutic systems builds upon ongoing advancements in computer vision and spatial computing (Dasgupta et al., 2020; Tang et al., 2023). Frameworks such as Meta's Project Aria¹ and Google XR Objects² are paving the way for robust, real-time interaction with the physical world within extended reality environments.

Object recognition through MR headsets could add a new layer of contextual relevance and engagement to mental health immersive interventions. For instance, a therapeutic system might recognize a user's chair and place calming virtual elements around it. If the system detects a personal item like a notebook frequently used for journaling, it might gently suggest a short reflective prompt based on recent emotional patterns or biofeedback data. In pediatric contexts, everyday objects such as a stuffed animal can be leveraged to initiate emotionally supportive interactions. When the MR system detects the presence of a familiar plush toy, it can trigger a calming, game-based experience designed to support emotion regulation in young users. For example, the toy may be transformed into an animated character within the MR environment, guiding the child through simple activities such as deep breathing, emotion labeling, or body scans. For adult users, therapeutic interactions can become more symbolic and metaphor-driven, as in the case of an "emotional gardening" experience. When the system recognizes a plant or designated calming object in the environment, it can overlay a virtual garden within the MR space that evolves in response to the user's current emotional state, inferred from biofeedback inputs such as heart rate variability or galvanic skin response. This integration of the digital and physical world enhances the sense of continuity between therapy and daily life, encouraging users to see mental health practices not as isolated tasks, but as part of their everyday environment.

3 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The intersection of AI and XR technologies represents a pivotal opportunity to re-imagine how we approach mental health care. By combining biofeedback, generative AI, and real-world object recognition, we can move beyond static interventions toward systems that are emotionally adaptive, responsive to user context, and capable of supporting individuals in real time.

Taken together, these generative AI capabilities create the foundation for on-demand, user-centered XR environments that are responsive, emotionally intelligent, and continuously adaptive. By blending narrative, visual, auditory, and conversational modalities, generative systems transform XR into a living canvas—one that shapes itself around the user's psychological and emotional journey. Importantly, these personalized experiences are not intended to replace traditional therapeutic care but to serve as complementary tools that can extend support beyond clinical settings, enhance engagement between sessions, and provide users with additional resources for reflection, self-regulation, and emotional growth.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

¹ <https://www.projectaria.com/>

² <https://github.com/google/xr-objects>

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

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Kiin Platform: Using Immersive Training to Address Bias and support Behaviour Change

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8 **Keywords: extended reality, shared XR, embodiment, human behaviour, RCT, AI**

9
 10 **Figure 1: A: look-at behaviour replay in a work place study, B: participant's eyes follow other's**
 11 **hand by eye tracking, C:Offender embodied as victim: D:as child, E:MR shared Jenga game**

12 **Abstract**

13 Studying human behaviour—and how it changes—across large populations over extended periods of
 14 time in immersive extended reality (XR) environments requires sophisticated and flexible research
 15 platforms. We present the Kiin System, a platform designed to support the creation and delivery of
 16 XR experiences for both training and behaviour change research. The system enables dynamic
 17 modification of avatar and environment appearances, recording and replay of participants' voices and
 18 movements, and collection of subjective feedback through an integrated XR questionnaire system. It
 19 offers a comprehensive solution for designing, deploying, and managing randomized controlled trials
 20 (RCT) in both single-user and shared XR experiences. Key features include life-size full-body
 21 embodiment, natural interaction with diverse avatars and the environment, a Python client for
 22 runtime control and external systems (e.g., simulation and AI), low-latency conversational AI agents,
 23 AI-based environment adaptation, modules for audio-haptic sensory support and hearing simulation.
 24 It integrates secure cloud services to anonymously track participants over multiple sessions and

25 integrates with session management. It enables corporations and researchers to conduct complex,
26 longitudinal RCTs as well as immersive training at scale.

27 1. Introduction and Related Work

28 Before the cost of XR devices dramatically decreased, running scientific embodiment studies
29 required dedicated rooms and equipment such as full body motion capture systems quite heavy
30 HMDs, powerful PCs, dedicated head tracking, physiological (e.g. ECG and EEG) measure systems,
31 etc. (Spanlang et al. 2014) Existing VR tools range from general game engines (Unity, Unreal)
32 requiring significant development resources to specialized platforms (e.g., Vizard¹) or Social VR
33 platforms such as, RecRoom, VRChat, Mozilla Hubs, compared in (Liu and Steed 2021) or more
34 recent Horizon Worlds, Roblox² etc. Academic implementations provide base systems but still
35 require custom development Oliva et al. 2022, Steed et al. 2022. The Kiin platform differentiates
36 itself by integrating dynamic embodiment, low-latency AI with environmental control, multi-modal
37 tracking, a JSON flow description and a Python client within a single architecture optimized for Meta
38 Quest devices. Studies on body illusions (Slater et al. 2010),(de la Peña et al. 2010), etc. highlight the
39 importance of embodiment, an area the Kiin system excels with dynamic change and even gradual
40 reshaping capabilities. Kiin's AI integration leverages low-latency end-to-end multimodal speech to
41 speech models and allows for AI-driven environment modification, surpassing typical conversational
42 agent implementations. It aims to simplify longitudinal studies such as for example (Kishore et al.
43 2021) where behaviour change was shown in police officers after they experienced an interrogation
44 from the perspective of a victim.

45 2. System Architecture and Implementation

46 A simplified diagram of the Kiin system architecture is shown in Figure 2. The core subsystems are
47 described here:

- 48 • **Database Backend:** The system leverages Firebase for secure user account management as
49 well as storing content and user recordings and questionnaires.
- 50 • **Embodiment:** We leverage OpenXR and Meta's XR SDKs³ to retrieve tracking information
51 of (HMD, controllers, hands, eye/face where available) which is mapped to an internal
52 tracking avatar calibrated to the size of the participant's real body. The Unity Mecanim
53 muscle data of that tracking avatar is transferred in real-time to the embodied avatar enabling
54 avatar independent embodiment as described in (Spanlang et al. 2013). Avatars can appear
55 roughly like the participants' real body (Alvarez de la Campa Crespo and Spanlang 2021)
56 based on a photograph, or can be of different age, gender, race, size, social status, etc.
57 Embodied avatars can be changed at any time and exploiting full body blend shapes the
58 system even offers gradual avatar shape modification for example morph an obese looking
59 avatar into one that appears healthier.
- 60 • **Multi-modal Data Acquisition:** Synchronized movement (body, hands, eyes/face data) and
61 audio recordings, can be replayed in the same session or uploaded for later replay or analysis.

1 <https://www.worldviz.com/vizard-virtual-reality-software>

2 <https://www.spatial.io/>, <https://www.roblox.com/>, <https://github.com/Hubs-Foundation/hubs>, <https://horizon.meta.com/>

3 <https://www.khronos.org/openxr/>, <https://developers.meta.com/horizon/develop>

62 Pre, Post and Inside XR participant questionnaire responses can be stored in the same
63 database structure to enable correlations between conscious and unconscious behaviour.

- 64 • **Command System:** A defined set of commands allows for control over the VR experience.
65 These commands can, for example, change embodied appearance, modify environmental
66 properties (light, materials, etc), play sounds (spatialized audio, custom head related transfer
67 functions (HRTFs) and hearing aids/loss simulations(HA/HL)), insert/control AI-driven
68 avatars for low latency interaction, etc. This command structure provides an action space
69 suitable for reinforcement learning (RL) agents. Alternatively, commands can be triggered
70 locally on the device via our JSON-based flow defined per experience for rapid development.
- 71 • **AI Integration:** Connects multi modal low-latency (~200ms) speech-to-speech services(e.g.
72 GPT-4o Realtime,Google Gemini Live, Qwen’s Omni models, etc). The AI is prompted for
73 custom behaviour in the experience flow JSON and can also trigger commands within its
74 response to dynamically modify the environment by the client-side tools calling API⁴.
- 75 • **Python Client Interface:** Our Python package allows for more versatile interaction with the
76 shared experience, receiving events, querying data and send commands to the shared XR
77 experiences, offering access to the vast package libraries available in python such as NumPy,
78 SciPy, Matplotlib, PyTorch, Huggingface, etc.
- 79 • **Sensory Modules:** Include audio-to-haptic mapping and hearing loss/aid simulation⁵ which
80 enable studies for example to quantify the improvement of comprehension when audio is
81 enhanced with haptics similar to (Ciesla et al. 2021) but with avatars on a standalone XR
82 device with the voice coil actuators of Meta Touch Plus controllers.

⁴ platform.openai.com/docs/models/, platform.openai.com/docs/guides/realtime

⁵ github.com/3DTune-In/3dti_AudioToolkit_UnityWrapper, developers.meta.com/horizon/resources/haptics-studio/

83

84 **Figure 2: Data Flow between Kiin App, Kiin Python Client, Database Backend and Cloud AI**
 85 **Services. The arrow on the right illustrates networked capabilities connecting multiple Kiin Apps**

86 **Implementation:** The Kiin App is built with Unity⁶ using mainly C#. The backend database uses
 87 Google Firebase⁷ securely managing user accounts, experiences, recordings and session scheduling
 88 for studies, enforcing in-transit and at-rest encryption. For shared experiences the Photon engine
 89 (currently PUN2) is used to exchange voice and body, hands, face and eye movements of
 90 participants. It also connects the Kiin Python client to shared experiences, to send commands and
 91 receive events or states of the experience (e.g. the position, orientation and muscle values of each
 92 avatar). It supports audio channels for example for an AI agent to listen and respond by speech
 93 usually lip-synced through a 3D audio-source positioned at an avatar’s mouth. Experiences consist of
 94 modular components: environments, avatars, objects (Unity assetbundles), and animations—often
 95 recorded from participants or actors.

96 At the core of the app is the command system that enables it to spawn and move avatars, objects,
 97 texts, change aspects of the visual and acoustic environment, play sounds etc. The command system
 98 can get triggered by the app’s internal state machine, by a Kiin Python Client, or an AI service⁸. Our
 99 main target platforms are Meta Horizon OS and potentially Android XR when available. Currently
 100 we focus on Meta Quest devices 2/Pro/3/3S/ and the App is deployed via Meta for Work or Horizon
 101 Store⁹ (upon invitation). The system offers the possibility to collect, synchronized, multi-modal data
 102 (gaze, movement, ECG, EEG, voice, subjective reports) for analysis in standard tools (Python, R,
 103 MATLAB, etc.) to support diverse analyses, including cross-modal investigations correlating
 104 different behavioural streams.

105

⁶ <https://unity.com/> currently version 2022.3, and migration to Unity 6 is planned

⁷ <https://firebase.google.com/>

⁸ For example: platform.openai.com/docs/guides/realtime, <https://ai.google.dev/gemini-api/docs/live>

⁹ <https://work.meta.com/>, <https://horizon.meta.com/>

106

107 3. Use Cases

108 The Kiin system is being used in academic research for fundamental human behaviour studies, in the
109 areas of psychological and physiological therapy as well as for corporate staff training and research:

- 110 • **Domestic Violence Rehab** The system is being used by the Generalitat of Catalonia to
111 augment the rehabilitation of domestic violence offenders. We offer various experiences one
112 of them underlying this use case was published in (Seinfeld et al. 2018).
- 113 • **Eating Disorder Café scenario:** With Bristol University we are designing a study for the
114 treatment of eating disorders, which includes the eye tracking capabilities of the system.
- 115 • **Self-Conversation Therapy:** The system has been used in various self-conversation studies
116 (Osimo et al. 2015) to help people with depression and eating disorders. The dynamic body
117 resizing functionality was used in (Anastasiadou et al. 2024) to improve self-esteem in
118 participants with issues of severe obesity. In (Zisquit et al. 2025) it is used for enhanced
119 interpersonal emotion regulation.
- 120 • **EEG Co-presence Study:** With Maastricht University (MU) we have designed a study that
121 exploits the system to measure effects of being with another person’s avatar or a computer-
122 controlled one, leveraging multi-user networking and stimuli presentation and milliseconds
123 EEG synchronization.
- 124 • **Climate Change Game:** With Warsaw University (WU) we co-developed a multi user
125 tragedy of the commons game experience with the aim to raise awareness of the impact of
126 participants’ actions on the environment in a collaborative and competitive setting based on
127 an economics model developed by WU. Demoed at IEEE VR 2025 (Lewandowska et al.
128 2025)
- 129 • **Audio-Haptic Study:** Setup for a study on audio haptic enhancement to evaluate
130 improvement of hearing loss to understanding.
- 131 • **RL-Driven Protest Simulation:** In collaboration with the Arctic University of Norway we
132 migrated historical protest scenes to the system to then use the Python client for real-time RL
133 agent integration with the objective to have the participants join the protest in a peaceful
134 manner.
- 135 • **LLM Agent Interaction:** Directly use integrated low-latency AI agents and environment
136 modification features.

137 4. Discussion & Conclusion

138 The Kiin System offers an integrated, powerful platform for research and training in XR on
139 accessible hardware. It is highly integrated, offering dynamic embodiment, low-latency AI with
140 environmental control, Python extensibility. Ethical considerations regarding embodiment effects, AI
141 influence, and data privacy are paramount. Future work includes increasing concurrency, broadening
142 hardware support, adding built-in analysis tools, simplifying authoring interfaces and self-
143 deployments. The system significantly lowers the barrier for complex longitudinal immersive studies

144 by integrating key functionalities it opens up new avenues for understanding and improving human
145 behaviour. Its use cases ranging from governments over corporate training, as well as research
146 institutions demonstrates its value for immediate and the immense potential for future impact.

147 **5. Conflict of Interest**

148 BS is a co-founder of Virtual Bodyworks (also known as Kiin.tech)

149 **6. Author Contributions**

150 BS coordinated the development of the system and wrote the paper. EC, MZ, RG, CA, JM and JF
151 made major contributions to the system, avatars, experiences and ongoing and completed studies.

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212

Poster Abstracts 2A: Room “Rector Ramón Martín Mateo”

Building Sustainably on Mars: A Pedagogical Experience with Artificial Intelligence and Immersive Web Environments

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6 **Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Sustainability, Immersive Web Environments, Vocational**
7 **Education, Living on Mars.**

8 **Abstract**

9 This summary presents the development of a project by tenth year vocational school students as part
10 of the Artificial Intelligence and Sustainability (IAS) project, promoted by the University of Minho
11 (UM). The IAS project aims to stimulate the pre-university public towards scientific research,
12 creating an environment for sharing ideas, experiences and activities between UM, primary and
13 secondary schools, local authorities and R&D companies in this subject area^{1,2}.

14 Secondary school students can interact with UM lecturers and researchers^{1,2}, who propose challenges
15 inspired by the theme of Artificial Intelligence and Sustainability¹. The project culminates with the
16 public presentation of the work, in the form of oral communication or poster, at a conference held at
17 UM.

18 The 10th year students of the Multimedia and Electronics, Automation and Computers vocational
19 courses chose, from a list of suggested challenges, to work on the theme "Is it possible to build a
20 house on Mars? How would you build it?"

21 The students, divided into groups of up to five, began the research phase on the planet Mars,
22 exploring the websites of NASA and the European Space Agency. This research was complemented
23 using generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools, such as ChatGPT, which helped them interpret and
24 cross-reference the information gathered.

25 The research focused on several key questions such as: 'how to obtain water?', 'how to produce
26 energy?', 'how to ensure that you can breathe on Mars?'. Also, on issues related to thermal
27 insulation, protection against radiation and dust storms, water reuse and sanitation systems and the
28 selection of materials suitable for construction³ in an environment like Mars.

¹ <https://www.uminho.pt/PT/siga-a-uminho/Paginas/Detalhe-do-evento.aspx?Codigo=61817>, accessed on 18/3/2025

² <https://www.uminho.pt/PT/siga-a-uminho/Paginas/Detalhe-do-evento.aspx?Codigo=63720>, accessed on 18/3/2025

³ <https://noticias.up.pt/fcup/humanos-em-marte-trabalho-pioneiro-da-fcup-analisou-exposicao-a-radiacao/>, accessed on 18/3/2025

29 Some of the solutions they presented for building sustainable and cheap houses on Mars include:

- 30 - Use of resistant, light and durable materials, since Mars' gravity is lower than Earth's;
- 31 - Solar energy production, using solar panels and storage systems to power electric heaters;
- 32 - Water collection by extracting and purifying the ice present in the Martian subsoil;
- 33 - Underground construction, using 3D printers
- 34 - Efficient recycling and energy management systems.

35 They began by sketching out their ideas on paper, using pencils and markers. Then, with the support
36 of AI tools (text to image and text to 3D models) they ‘visualized’ their proposals. This phase of
37 constant iteration and interaction with the AI tools made it possible to generate the images included
38 in the posters. At the same time, the Multimedia students created the graphic identity of their
39 projects, developing logos and slogans for their companies’ building houses on Mars. Some groups,
40 especially those on the Multimedia course, chose to create their own illustrations. The posters were
41 developed using Photoshop or platforms such as Canva.

42 This project enabled the students to deepen their knowledge of science, the environment and
43 technology and allowed them to develop digital skills, where the use of AI was relevant as a means
44 of creative production and a huge help for the research they carried out.

45 It should also be noted that this work will serve as a conceptual and visual basis for the next phase of
46 the project, the development of immersive web environments, where ideas for homes on Mars will be
47 represented in online spaces.

48 For construction and exploration, students can use different tools and platforms, depending on the
49 objectives and degree of complexity desired:

50 Using 3D modelling tools such as Blender, Tinkercad or SketchUp, or text-to-3D AI tools, students
51 can build idealized houses.

52 Using platforms such as Anitya, Spatial, FrameVR or CoSpaces Edu, which allow these models to be
53 inserted into immersive environments that can be explored in virtual reality and via the browser.

54 If a greater degree of complexity and realism is required, development engines such as Unity or
55 Unreal Engine can be used.

56 These approaches promote engaging, collaborative educational experiences in line with the
57 metaverse concept, reinforcing the link between technology, active learning, creativity and
58 sustainability

59 This transposition from paper to digital space, where students create immersive educational web
60 environments based on AI and sustainability reinforces active learning, stimulates creativity and
61 technological literacy.

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Ethnography in the Metaverse

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ABSTRACT

As Metaverse platforms evolve, they offer new opportunities to study social behavior. We explore some aspects of conducting ethnographic studies in the Metaverse, highlighting both potential and limitations, while proposing key considerations for future research.

Keywords: Metaverse, Ethnography, Social VR, Virtual Reality, HCI

1 INTRODUCTION

The study of social behavior and user experience in virtual environments have always been of interest in various disciplinary fields. With the recent technological advancements in XR, immersive virtual social worlds are emerging giving a new shape to what is defined as the *Metaverse*. These platforms open up new possibilities for social and behavioral studies inside virtual environments. Although many anthropological methods can be utilized for such studies, potential improvements and discussion points come up when considering details regarding these methods and how we can adapt them in the Metaverse.

In this work we look upon ethnographic methods utilized to document behaviors directly “in the wild”, where it happens, as opposed for instance to observe them in a controlled lab experiments. Conducting ethnography in the Metaverse could be useful to understand the social and cultural behavior of its users. However, various obstacles are to be addressed to enable such studies. In this paper, we discuss the conduct of ethnographic studies inside social VR platforms, shedding light on the promising potential while highlighting possible emerging conflicts.

2 RELATED WORK

The term *Metaverse* was first introduced in 1992 by Neal Stephenson in the novel “Snow Crash”, to describe a 3D space where people are represented by avatars and can interact with each other through these avatars. Different definitions of the Metaverse have emerged in relation to both the advancements in immersive technology and the development of commercial actors. In our work, we consider the Metaverse as mainly based on eXtended Reality (XR, regrouping AR and VR technologies) and avatars, in persistent online 3D worlds, as proposed in a recent review Park and Kim (2022).

2.1 Ethnography in virtual worlds

Anthropological work in virtual worlds can be traced back to the late 1990s, when definitions of *Virtual Ethnography* (Hine, 2000), and *Netnography* (Kozinets, 1998) were introduced, both defining methods to study and observe the behavior of users, communities and cultures present in virtual spaces. These methods were then utilized by anthropologists to study social behavior on various platforms that allowed users to

interact with each others and with the world using their own avatar, as well as to possess their own virtual spaces (e.g., a virtual environment that represented their house) and objects. *World of Warcraft* (Ducheneaut and Moore, 2004; Ducheneaut et al., 2006; Nardi, 2010) or *Second Life* (Boellstorff, 2015) are examples of such platforms. Ethnographic studies relied on the observation of members of these virtual worlds, looking into the their daily activities, their interactions, their communication. Ethnographers joined the users, participated with them in what they did in order to better understand their culture.

2.2 Ethnography in the Metaverse

In its current state, the Metaverse can be defined as a set of persistent platforms such as *VRChat*, *RecRooms*, *Meta Horizon Worlds*, *BanterVR* and many others. These platforms allow users to communicate, interact, and engage in various activities while embodying avatars of their choice. They are available for free to a wide range of users of different background, age, gender or culture, and many integrate accessibility features that allow the participation of users with different impairments, enabling them to interact with others with minimum obstacles. They also allow their users to build their own worlds and allow others to join in, which serves as a motivation to create worlds related to things they are passionate about, attracting other users that share the same passion. As a consequence, various various communities have daily activities on social VR platforms.

Users in the Metaverse are engaging in collaborative and social interactions that both differ from real-world interactions, and have far more richness and depth than what could be observed within previous platforms such as second life. For instance, immersive interactions between avatars and with the environment are embodied, potentially leading to new and complex social behaviors. Studying these behaviors is of interest for social and human-computer interaction researchers, who could clearly get a better understanding of how these users and groups function and interact by conducting their studies “from within”, like for any human group and activities. Yet, in opposition to what happened for non-immersive platforms (Netnography), ethnographic studies in the Metaverse are still scarce, even if some early proposals can be found. For instance, (Maloney and Freeman, 2020) explored the social activities that users found meaningful and valuable in the social VR; (Williamson et al., 2021) focused on studying proxemics during social interactions inside Mozilla Hub, and (Kolesnichenko et al., 2019) conducted interviews inside social VR platforms with designers and professionals of the Metaverse, identifying affordances that enhanced embodiment of the users.

3 CARRYING-OUT ETHNOGRAPHY IN THE METAVERSE

Ethnography in the Metaverse is still limited, and in this section we discuss several requirements associated to data collection and legal issues. An important remark is that despite the fact that many current social VR platforms also allow their users to join with traditional 2D screens and input methods such as mouse and keyboard, our focus is on *ethnographers being in immersive VR*, who can study VR and non-VR users alike.

3.1 Data collection

First, let us consider data collection, which is critical in ethnographic studies, and can take several forms and aims, such as general observations about the surrounding environment or population, descriptions of specific events, experiences recollected by participants, personal notes of the ethnographer, etc.

3.1.1 Recording Data

Recording can serve to document something a participant said during an interview, a gesture they did, the way an action was carried out, a routine of a certain community, etc. There is a lot of flexibility with what to record and how to record it. For instance, the ethnographer can record their first person point-of-view (POV), but also place several virtual cameras or microphones inside the environment to capture other POVs. We can even imagine drone-like cameras following participants as they move around. However, questions remain about how to analyze these recordings. For example, how to find specific moments of interest for the study, and how tools can be built to help the researchers. Such tools can be available on Metaverse platforms that facilitate recording data and synchronizing several viewpoints or data sources to analyze it more easily later on. These artifacts can be controlled by the platform itself, but also by the researchers. Most importantly, these tools should be compatible across platforms to provide a unified method of acquiring the data. Another type of data that could be recorded are logs of the actions of chosen participants, or the state of all, or part of, the environment at certain moments, not as video but as structured data. The use of virtual logging tools to capture events, interactions and the state of the environment will provide more information over the course of the study. This could allow to identify the action or activity done by the participants, and will provide more information about the environment surrounding the participant, such as count and position other participants or virtual objects.

3.1.2 Taking notes

Note taking is a central component of ethnographic studies, and immersive technologies may enable various ways to take notes, some of which may improve on more traditional methods but still have their limitations. Voice recording can be used to verbally record observations or interpretations in real-time. Taking written notes may be difficult in VR, as virtual writing is complicated if one does not have access to a real keyboard, or to a dedicated pen and a surface to write on in reality. Selecting among predefined observation categories may be something that is more easy to do in VR. A particularity of VR is that notes could be placed around the virtual environment to connect the observations and the virtual spaces where they occurred, allowing to revisit them later. Notes could also be combined with other recordings. For example, having the notes synchronized based on timestamps with a video recording would facilitates revisiting specific moments and recalling observations from it. Moreover, collaborative notes are possible for studies that involve several ethnographers, which could be synchronized between the researchers, or passed virtually between for easier collaboration.

3.2 Legal issues

Second, some legal considerations have to be taken into account.

3.2.1 User data privacy and applicable laws

Since ethnographic studies in the Metaverse may involve users from different countries, each subjected to varying data protection laws, then a question quickly arises: which legal framework should apply? Should it be based on the researcher's location, the user's, the platform's, or even that of the virtual world itself? Would there exist something as French soil in the Metaverse? Moreover, every Metaverse platform has its own Terms of Service and Privacy Policy, but it is now unclear if they define what kind of data can be collected by researchers, how user behavior can be observed, and whether research activities like interviews, recordings, or behavioral tracking are allowed.

3.2.2 Participant consent

Ethical and legal reasons make it mandatory to get the consent of the participants in a study, but another issue is the way the consent can be obtained. If we imagine a scenario where the experimenter has to ask for participants' consent to collect data in the Metaverse —e.g., to record an interview— there are many possibilities regarding how to request and obtain it. For example, the experimenter can orally communicate the necessary information and ask for the participant's consent. The experimenter could also have access to a virtual object such as a screen or a tablet that displays the consent form for the participant to read. Obtaining effective consent from the user can also take various forms. A simple oral consent could be video recorded, or virtual objects could be used, for instance a virtual pen to sign a form, or an object that is interacted with to confirm and record a signature. All these methods may depend not only on the platform but also on ethical obligations related to research and laws but also on specific virtual environments within a given platform, introducing variability in the way consent is obtained from different participants to the same study.

4 CONCLUSION

Ethnography in virtual worlds has always existed in some form, but the emergence of the Metaverse opens new possibilities for studying social behavior and emerging cultures within social immersive virtual environments. In this paper, we proposed several key topics related to aspects of ethnographic studies, that are up for discussion.

Knowing these challenges, we aim to use ethnography to deepen our understanding of how users navigate the Metaverse in groups. However, we are continuously evaluating our methods from the perspective of regulations and policies when it comes to users' data. We aim to observe groups explore environments and interact with them, during which we will try to apply some of the approaches we discussed above, especially to what data we will collect and how.

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Development and Evaluation of a Virtual Reality Training System for Precision Agriculture

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ABSTRACT

This work introduces a Virtual Reality (VR) training system for precision agriculture, offering a cost-effective and flexible alternative to traditional training methods. The system integrates NeRF-based reality capture (via Luma AI) with Unreal Engine and Oculus Quest to create immersive training scenarios. User evaluations indicate high engagement and usability, although some participants experienced motion sickness during mobile VR tasks. These results underscore the potential of VR in agricultural training, while highlighting the importance of motion-adaptive environments for an optimal user experience.

Keywords: Virtual Reality, Training System, Precision Agriculture, Unreal Engine, Neural Radiance Fields, User Evaluation

1 INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector is undergoing rapid technological transformation, incorporating automation and robotics to enhance productivity. However, the deployment of these technologies is hindered by a lack of trained personnel and the high costs associated with traditional training methods. Virtual Reality (VR) has emerged as a promising solution, enabling immersive, flexible, and cost-effective training experiences.

This paper presents a VR-based training system for precision agriculture that leverages synthetic and real-world models, integrated through Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) Mildenhall et al. (2021) and Unreal Engine. Our primary contribution lies in demonstrating the feasibility and effectiveness of VR in agricultural training, addressing challenges related to usability and engagement.

2 IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

2.1 System Architecture

The architecture of the proposed training system is presented in Fig. 1. The core component utilizes LUMA AI's NeRF technology to build 3D models of real objects (Fig. 2a). The models of agricultural machines are taken directly from manufacturer databases. Interaction within the VR environment was enabled through hand-tracking and controller-based manipulation.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the proposed system.

Figure 2. Example model obtained by applying NeRF-based 3D reconstruction (a) used in the VR training scenario (b,c). Model of Universal Robot UR5e (d) and a tractor (e) used in scenarios II and III.

2.2 Training Scenarios

The system was verified in three sequential training scenarios:

- 1.Introduction to VR where users learn basic environment navigation (Fig. 2b) and object manipulation (Fig. 2c).
- 2.Robotics training where users operate a virtual robotic arm (Universal Robot UR5) to perform simulated farming tasks, such as fruit harvesting.
- 3.Operating Tractor where users drive a tractor in a VR environment, assessing the impact of prolonged VR exposure on comfort and motion sickness.

2.3 User Evaluation

To assess the effectiveness of the system, participants completed a questionnaire adapted from the Virtual Reality Neuroscience Questionnaire (VRNQ, Kourtesis et al. (2019)) and Igroup Presence Questionnaire (IPQ, Tran et al. (2024)). The questions in the questionnaire are divided into three groups and evaluate the perceived realism, usability, and physiological effects of VR exposure:

- First and second questions asked the respondents about their past experience with playing games and using Virtual Reality sets.
- Third, Fourth and Fifth questions concerned the immersion and subjective experience of the users when it came to scenarios.
- Sixth, Seventh and Eighth questions asked about the ease of use and were the assignments understandable.

Data analysis indicated a positive reception, with high levels of immersion and moderate discomfort in the simulated vehicle operation scenario.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The results confirm the potential of VR-based training in agriculture, providing a safe and immersive environment for skill acquisition. The modular design of the proposed system allows for adaptation to

Figure 3. Response percentages to questions on a Likert Scale.

different types of agricultural machinery, and user feedback highlights the importance of optimizing comfort and minimizing motion sickness.

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A VR Platform for Home Neurorehabilitation with Remote Supervision

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a virtual reality (VR) system for home-based neurological rehabilitation, developed for the Meta Quest platform. It integrates a Unity-based VR application for therapeutic exercises with a .NET desktop tool for remote monitoring and scenario adaptation. Connected via MQTT, the system enables real-time supervision by healthcare professionals, supporting personalized therapy at a distance. A functional prototype was evaluated through simulated rehabilitation sessions.

Keywords: VR System Architecture, Neurorehabilitation, Remote Monitoring, Human–Computer Interaction, Unity, MQTT

1 INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Neurological incidents such as strokes frequently result in upper limb motor dysfunction, reducing patient autonomy and quality of life. Virtual reality (VR) has recently gained traction as a tool for motor rehabilitation, offering immersive, interactive, and task-specific training that promotes neuroplasticity and accelerates recovery (Bui et al., 2021; Herrera et al., 2023). These systems also allow for adaptive task difficulty and provide engaging, game-like experiences that can improve patient adherence (Lee et al., 2020).

This project aims to design and implement a VR-based rehabilitation system with a focus on software robustness, usability, and clinical integration. The system specifically targets upper limb motor dysfunction, which is often a consequence of neurological events such as strokes. By focusing on upper extremity rehabilitation, the system aims to facilitate the recovery of fine and gross motor skills essential for daily activities. The proposed system leverages hand tracking for intuitive interaction, supports customizable therapy scenarios, and includes remote access features for clinicians to manage and monitor sessions. A key motivation behind this work is enabling at-home rehabilitation, reducing the need for frequent clinical visits. Home-based rehabilitation systems are particularly valuable for patients with limited mobility, those residing in rural or underserved areas, or individuals facing transportation barriers. By enabling therapy in a familiar environment, the system lowers healthcare costs, and encourages consistent engagement with therapeutic routines. This design approach aligns with the increasing trend toward decentralized, patient-centered care models (Sinha, 2024).

2 ARCHITECTURE AND IMPLEMENTATION

The system comprises two key components: a VR application designed for the Meta Quest headset and a desktop application built using the .NET framework. The VR application (Fig. 1A) was developed in Unity,

chosen for its flexibility, integrated physics engine, and compatibility with VR SDKs. It supports immersive scenarios where patients perform object manipulation tasks aimed at improving motor skills. Key features of the VR application include: (i) bare hand-tracking-based interaction using Meta XR All-in-One SDK and Hand Physics Toolkit (González, n/a); (ii) configurable rehabilitation environments (e.g., tables and shelves) built from modular 3D shapes; (iii) scenario management through a structured stage-object model; (iv) visual/audio task instructions and real-time performance metrics.

Figure 1. Data and control flow in the VR application (A), an example scene as seen in the desktop app (B), and an alternative scene setup with more objects for manipulation (C).

The therapeutic exercises implemented in the system are designed to be flexible and configurable, either through an external control application or directly within the VR interface. Each exercise typically involves relocating virtual objects to designated targets, mimicking goal-directed motor tasks common in upper limb rehabilitation. The objects used in these tasks are defined by external 3D models, allowing customization without modifying the underlying code. Target locations can be indicated by semi-transparent "ghost shapes" or through other visual cues, such as color coding, enabling the integration of both motor and cognitive components. This flexibility supports a range of task types and difficulty levels, making the system adaptable to varying rehabilitation needs.

The desktop application (Fig. 1B,C) serves as a control centre for clinicians. It allows for real-time monitoring of sessions via streamed visual data, editing of scenarios and environmental parameters, configuration and analysis of performance metrics. Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT), a lightweight publish-subscribe network protocol commonly used for IoT applications due to its efficiency and low bandwidth usage (Radwan and Alves-Foss, 2024), is employed for transmitting data between the two applications, ensuring lightweight and responsive data exchange. This allows for dynamic adaptation of therapy scenarios during sessions and consistent data synchronization.

3 RESULTS

The developed system was evaluated through simulated rehabilitation sessions (Borowski and Rewekant, 2024). The VR application successfully guided users (healthy students acting as simulated patients) through a series of customized motor tasks, such as relocating objects to designated targets within virtual environments (Fig. 2). Hand tracking demonstrated sufficient accuracy for natural interaction, while the integrated physics-based simulation contributed to a realistic and engaging experience.

The desktop interface allowed supervisors to customize therapy scenarios and monitor patient progress remotely, with performance metrics such as task or particular movement completion time and object

Figure 2. Setting parameters inside the VR app (A), task setup with three objects and their target locations, shown as semi-transparent shapes (B), and the final state for two objects moved by the patient (C).

placement accuracy logged and visualized through interactive charts. The system demonstrated strong stability and modular architecture, supporting its suitability for future clinical deployment and remote use.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation confirms that VR with off-the-shelf headgears originally targeted to entertainment market can be effectively leveraged to create flexible, interactive rehabilitation environments suitable for home-based therapy. The integration of remote supervision and data tracking tools enhances its value for decentralized care, enabling supervisors to guide and adapt therapy without requiring in-person sessions. Future work will focus on clinical validation, improving real-time feedback for patients, and implementing adaptive difficulty algorithms to further personalize rehabilitation in a home setting.

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VR-generated illusion as a tool for limbs neurorehabilitation during hyperacute phase of ischemic stroke

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ABSTRACT

Virtual Reality (VR) has been shown to enhance motor rehabilitation in post-stroke patients after they embody a virtual avatar. Virtual reality-generated illusions can facilitate functional recovery within one week after the onset of a stroke. We present our proposed solution that applies AR and VR in the rehabilitation of stroke patients. We also present issues related to the monitoring of people undergoing rehabilitation. To determine the tolerance of patients to the new rehabilitation technique, we conducted a survey and measurement of selected parameters of vital signs. The evaluation of the patients involved in the program was performed at baseline and after 7 days of training. The effectiveness of VR rehabilitation was measured using the National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS). We observed excellent tolerance and safety for VR training in stroke patients.

Keywords: Neurorehabilitation, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, Post-stroke Patients

1 INTRODUCTION

Ischemic stroke leads to motor deficits, which capture mainly the attention of clinicians and researchers. However, post-stroke sensory deficits often receive less exploration, primarily due to the contrast between apparent motor dysfunction and more subtle sensory impairments. Furthermore, during the hyperacute phase of ischemic stroke, assessing and differentiating neglect, hemisensory deficits, and hemianopsia can be challenging. Factors such as aphasia (language disorder) and disturbances in consciousness hinder the assessment of neglect and hemisensory deficits using the NIHSS (National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale).

In the pre-recanalization phase, clinical evaluations are more limited due to time constraints. However, in the post-recanalization phase, a thorough assessment of sensory modalities is essential for planning effective neurorehabilitation. The International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF), established by the World Health Organization in 2001, provides a standardized language and framework for describing health and health-related conditions, including proprioceptive functions (b260), touch functions

(b265), and sensory functions related to temperature (b270), vibration (b2701), pressure (b2702), and noxious stimuli (b2703), as well as other related areas (b2708 - b2709).

Alternative sensorimotor pathways that involve secondary motor areas can help facilitate motor control. Ischemic stroke can damage structures involved in motor control, such as primary somatosensory areas and the thalamus, along with other subcortical structures. Consequently, the functional recovery of post-stroke patients may be delayed and challenging. In these cases, tailored neurorehabilitation should incorporate activities aimed at somatosensory stimulation to enhance stereognosis, proprioception, and the ability to discriminate and localize sensations. Combining sensory and motor techniques can improve recovery from limb dysfunction. One traditional and practical approach is mirror therapy, which has been developed for motor rehabilitation in post-stroke patients (1). This therapy creates a visual illusion by allowing the patient to watch the reflection of the unaffected limb in a mirror. As the patient moves the unaffected limb, the reflection creates an image of the affected limb, stimulating interhemispheric communication and activating the brain regions responsible for controlling movement in the paralyzed limb.

Kinaesthetic perceptual illusion through visual stimulation **Figure 1.** Mirror therapy (KINVIS) is a neurorehabilitation protocol in which a person at rest experiences the sensation of a body part moving or the desire to move that part while watching a video depicting the same movement. KINVIS has the potential to induce changes in the motor output system of the brain, as evidenced by the increased bioelectric activity in the affected hemisphere around the sensorimotor area following KINVIS. The advent of emerging technologies, such as Metaverse (2), finds application in the healthcare sector when feasible (3). Virtual Reality (VR) also presents opportunities to create immersive illusions that can aid in the neurorehabilitation of stroke patients. The limb illusion generated by VR has been shown to enhance motor rehabilitation in post-stroke patients after they embody a virtual avatar. This approach stimulates interregional and interhemispheric communication, thereby improving movement control in a manner akin to mirror therapy. VR scenarios can be tailored according to the range and type of neurological deficits experienced after a stroke. Additionally, the effectiveness of VR illusions can be amplified through the use of haptic feedback or tendon vibration via transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), such as in the wrist. By combining visual and proprioceptive stimuli, a conducive environment is created for the multisystemic activation of brain areas involved in movement control. At the Institute of Neurological Disorders at the Poznan University of Medical Sciences, we implement virtual reality illusions with haptics during the hyperacute phase of ischemic stroke. Our observations indicate a positive impact on motor recovery, including a reduction in tremors and the alleviation of neglect syndrome. However, we have also observed limitations in patients with Parkinson's disease, who exhibited increased dyskinesias during VR training. We attribute this phenomenon to impaired visual perception and the compromised multisensory integration characteristic of Parkinson's disease.

2 VIRTUAL REHABILITATION SYSTEM

It is well known that the rehabilitation process for neurological diseases is long and after a period of hospitalization, the patient must perform various, often tedious, exercises at home. Some of these exercises can be performed in virtual reality. Performing these exercises in virtual reality helps to make them more attractive, and thus more effective (the patient is more likely to perform the exercises in a well-designed

Figure 2. Illustration of the proposed system implementation

and attractive virtual reality). Of course, this assumes that the motor requirements appropriate to the set of exercises are met. The use of technology and virtual reality enables the dissemination of neurorehabilitation, allowing such goals as physical and cognitive restoration, enrichment of rehabilitation techniques, increased effectiveness; wider access to society, and teleneurorehabilitation. The system we have developed uses virtual reality, but we also use augmented reality (AR) technology. AR technology has been implemented in the “smart mirror” device we made. We use it for a personalized interface with the system user. The patient approaches the mirror, is recognized, and then a dialogue begins which aims to offer the patient appropriate rehabilitation exercises. A set of these exercises is selected from a catalog developed in advance by doctors and physiotherapists. This set is dedicated/personalized for the patient. The illustration of the proposed system is shown in Fig.2.

2.1 Smart Mirror - Personalized Interface

The Smart Mirror allows the patient to be identified by facial recognition, and then there is a personalized dialogue with the patient. Upon recognition of the patient, as mentioned earlier, the system proposes to the patient a set of exercises dedicated to him. The proposal is not only personalized for the patient, but also takes into account additional information such as the time of exercise, current weather conditions (weather forecast), the patient’s mood, etc. The substantive scope of the system software is consulted with neurologists and neurorehabilitation specialists and implemented in the system accordingly. The system runs on a Raspberry Pi platform. However, the platform communicates with a more powerful computer that runs the main application. It is a web application implemented in the Django environment. Face recognition is implemented using the PyTorch and OpenCV libraries. The required data are stored in an SQL database (in our case, MariaDB). The facial recognition function in Smart Mirror is powered by algorithms based on artificial intelligence that can recognize faces and compare them with faces in the system database. The virtual rehabilitation system will propose the most appropriate and/or expected virtual interaction with the recognized person.

3 CONCLUSION

Neurorehabilitation, supported with simple tools for everyday activities and advanced technology, opens possibilities to improve motor training and cognitive functions and enables the treatment of crippling

symptoms such as neglect syndrome. VR-based therapy can provide a positive learning experience and be engaging and motivating. Enhancing typical exercises performed in a real environment, with virtual reality, individuals recovering from strokes can engage in practicing self-care tasks within an environment that is typically unfeasible to recreate within a hospital setting. Illusions generated by VR can activate “mirror neurons” and “re-programme” neuronal control of motor functions. Further expansion of the palette of exercises available in virtual reality will reach homes of patients (e.g. elderly persons) and will allow telerehabilitation. Telerehabilitation trainings can be developed and supported by the implementation of human–computer interfaces (HCI). VR systems are currently used in everyday practice in the Stroke Unit of the University Hospital in Poznan. Stroke patients are mainly older people who are only occasionally familiar with computer technology. However, unexpectedly, their tolerance to VR is excellent. We noticed an excellent tolerance for VR training in stroke patients. Stable blood pressure and heart rate remain crucial for the clinical safety of procedures used during the hyperacute phase of ischemic stroke, and that was a case in our trial. Interestingly, some symptoms, such as intension tremor, that are present in real-world training disappeared in VR training. NIHSS after VR training was reduced in average from 4.797 to 2.155 as presented in Fig.3. Interestingly, some symptoms, such as intension tremor, that are present in real-world training disappeared in VR training. Access to rehabilitation centers is limited, and many patients face challenges in staying motivated to follow rehabilitation programs. Our project directly addresses these challenges by using AI-driven telerehabilitation, which offers personalized, remote rehabilitation plans that adapt to each patient’s progress, improving patient outcomes and increasing access to care for those affected by neurological disorders.

Figure 3. NIHSS before and after VR trainings

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Poster Abstracts 2B: Room “Vicente Gimeno Sendra”

The Convergence of Artificial Intelligence and the Metaverse in Orthopedic Healthcare: Emerging Applications and Research Directions

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7 **Keywords:** artificial intelligence, metaverse, orthopedics, virtual reality, digital twins, surgical
8 simulation, immersive healthcare

9 **Abstract**

10 **Introduction:** Artificial intelligence (AI) and metaverse technologies have each made significant
11 strides independently, laying the groundwork for their transformative convergence in healthcare. AI
12 has become integral to modern medicine, powering applications ranging from diagnostic imaging and
13 predictive analytics to personalized treatment recommendations and workflow automation. Recent
14 breakthroughs include AI-assisted cancer treatment planning, early detection of neurological
15 disorders through speech and movement analysis, and the integration of wearable devices for
16 proactive health monitoring.

17 Concurrently, the metaverse has evolved from a conceptual virtual environment to a sophisticated,
18 immersive ecosystem. Advances in extended reality (XR) have enabled hyper-realistic simulations,
19 real-time interactions, and seamless integration of digital and physical experiences. Robust metaverse
20 infrastructures will make these environments more accessible and capable of supporting complex,
21 data-driven healthcare applications.

22 The convergence of AI and the metaverse in orthopedic healthcare is now enabling new models of
23 clinical care, education, and patient engagement by combining intelligent data analysis with
24 immersive, interactive environments. Together, these rapidly advancing technologies have the
25 potential to revolutionize clinical care, surgical training, and patient engagement by enabling more
26 intelligent, immersive, and personalized experiences. This poster will discuss these emerging
27 applications and research directions.

28 **Clinical training and education:** AI-powered simulations within metaverse platforms are
29 revolutionizing surgical education. These systems provide:

- 30 • *Personalized feedback:* AI algorithms analyze trainees' performance in real time, offering
31 individualized guidance on technique, efficiency, and safety.

32 • *Objective skill assessment*: Automated metrics track progress, benchmark skills against expert
33 standards, and identify areas for improvement, ensuring rigorous and unbiased evaluation.

34 • *Adaptive scenario progression*: Training modules dynamically adjust case complexity based
35 on the learner's proficiency, ensuring continuous challenge and growth.

36 Virtual patients—realistic, AI-driven avatars, powered by natural language processing and behavioral
37 modeling—offer safe, immersive opportunities for students and professionals. These include:

38 • *Clinical decision-making*: Learners navigate evolving clinical scenarios, making diagnostic
39 and therapeutic choices with immediate AI-generated feedback on outcomes.

40 • *Empathy and communication*: Virtual patients simulate diverse personalities and emotional
41 responses, allowing trainees to refine bedside manner, deliver difficult news, and build
42 rapport in a safe environment.

43 • *Interprofessional collaboration*: AI-powered avatars can represent multidisciplinary team
44 members, fostering teamwork and communication skills essential for modern orthopedic
45 practice.

46 Our lab is exploring this approach by training AI models to drive verbal responses of virtual
47 therapists and patients in VR, creating realistic practice environments for clinical skill development.

48 **Enhancing patient care and decision-making**: Predictive visualization tools, underpinned by AI,
49 are enhancing patient care in several ways:

50 • *Preoperative planning*: Surgeons can interact with 3D models of patient anatomy, simulate
51 interventions, and anticipate complications, leading to more precise and personalized surgical
52 strategies.

53 • *Shared decision-making*: Immersive visualizations help patients understand their conditions
54 and treatment options, facilitating informed consent and collaborative care planning.

55 • *Patient understanding*: By visualizing outcomes and risks in an interactive format, patients
56 gain clearer insights into their care journey, improving satisfaction and adherence.

57 Smart digital twins—AI-enhanced, self-updating models of individual patients—integrate real-time
58 clinical, sensor, and imaging data to support continuous monitoring, outcome prediction, and tailored
59 rehabilitation programs.

60 In addition, our research has demonstrated viability of using metaverse technologies with patients by
61 conducting patient focus groups using lookalike avatars with real-time tracking, significantly
62 enhancing patient engagement and communication through a genuine sense of presence, whilst still
63 enabling participation regardless of mobility constraints or physical limitations. [1,2]

64 **Embedded AI in immersive healthcare**: Within immersive clinical settings, AI can be embedded
65 directly into virtual spaces, offering

66 • *Real-time workflow support*: Intelligent virtual agents guide clinicians through protocols, flag
67 potential errors, and streamline documentation during virtual rounds or consultations.

68 • *Clinical recommendations*: Embedded AI systems analyze patient data on-the-fly, suggesting
69 diagnostic or therapeutic actions based on the latest evidence and guidelines.

- 70 • *Facilitated interaction*: AI-driven avatars act as patient surrogates, interpreters, or
71 administrative assistants, enhancing communication and efficiency during remote or
72 multidisciplinary consultations.

73 Examples include AI agents that moderate virtual case discussions, provide instant access to patient
74 histories, or simulate complex patient behaviors for training and assessment purposes [3]. Building
75 on our success with AI-driven avatars in rehabilitation settings, we are adapting these technologies
76 for a broad range of conditions, creating more natural and responsive virtual clinical interactions.

77 **Research frontiers and innovation areas:** Emerging research at the intersection of AI and the
78 metaverse is rapidly expanding. Areas of innovation include multimodal AI that integrates spatial,
79 visual, and linguistic data, allowing for more comprehensive and integrated analysis; embodied AI
80 agents capable of navigating and interacting within virtual environments; and synthetic data
81 generation to enhance training and testing; adaptive interfaces that can adjust virtual content in
82 response to users' cognitive or emotional states, and biometric feedback systems that can tailor
83 therapy in real time. Such advances can potentially revolutionize personalized digital health.

84 **Challenges and Future Outlook:** Despite these advances, significant challenges remain, including:

- 85 • *Data privacy and security*: The integration of sensitive health data in immersive environments
86 raises concerns about confidentiality and unauthorized access, necessitating robust encryption
87 and blockchain solutions.
- 88 • *Clinical validation*: Rigorous research is required to validate the effectiveness and safety of
89 AI-driven metaverse tools, ensuring they meet clinical standards and improve outcomes.
- 90 • *Equitable access*: High costs and technological requirements risk exacerbating healthcare
91 disparities, highlighting the need for inclusive design and policy interventions.
- 92 • *Regulation and oversight*: Clear regulatory frameworks must be developed to govern the use
93 of AI and metaverse technologies, balancing innovation with patient safety and ethical
94 considerations.

95 Nevertheless, the ongoing convergence of AI and the metaverse is poised to unlock new frontiers in
96 orthopedic healthcare, transforming how clinicians learn, plan, and deliver care, and how patients
97 experience their orthopedic journey. Our ongoing research aims to address these challenges while
98 building on our successful implementations in patient engagement with VR and the metaverse and
99 AI-powered clinical interactions.

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Embodied AI and Multisensory VR for Skill Acquisition and Rehabilitation in the Metaverse

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Figure 1. Co-Embodiment Systems: Learners share avatar control with real or AI teachers. *Top left:* Joint control with a real teacher (50% each). *Bottom left:* Shared control with an AI teacher, whose real-time movements are generated based on learner input and a Tai Chi motion capture library. **AI Gesture Recognition Flow:** Observation probability, Bayesian filtering, and normalization select the best matching expert gesture. **Gesture Matching Criteria:** Ensures correct direction and shape, allows flexibility in speed, and rejects major mismatches.

2 Dance-based motor learning requires precise coordination, body awareness, and continuous feedback.
 3 Although VR has shown promise for supporting various dance practices, including Tai Chi (Tian et al.,
 4 2024), no studies have explored the co-embodiment of first-person AI-supported skills for such skills.
 5 Previous research shows that shared control with a real teacher improves learning (Kodama et al., 2023),
 6 but the role of AI remains underexplored. In this work, we developed a co-embodiment system where users
 7 and a real or AI teacher share control of a virtual avatar, with movements weighted equally, using Tai Chi
 8 movements as a demonstrative case of dance-based motor skills. The system uses motion capture to track
 9 the user's input, comparing it to a pre-recorded Tai Chi expert dataset. Using a gesture recognition model
 10 (Bevilacqua et al., 2009), an AI teacher predicts ideal postures and provides corrective feedback in real
 11 time. This adaptive approach delivers personalized, continuous guidance that allows participants to view
 12 their optimized Tai Chi movements from a first-person perspective as their own body in real time. We
 13 explore whether AI-driven shared agency can support procedural learning as effectively as co-embodiment
 14 with a human teacher (see Figure 1 for key innovations).

15 Although most co-embodiment research focuses on visual interaction, effective motor learning and
 16 rehabilitation depend on multisensory engagement. Our system integrates haptic feedback, auditory cues,
 17 and gaze control to improve body awareness and motor performance Sigrist et al. (2013).

18 Haptic feedback is the key to somatosensory control in Tai Chi, classical dance, yoga, and hip hop,
19 which require precise activation of the coccyx, spine, scapula, limbs, and neural extremities. Many dance
20 techniques initiate movement from the torso, progressively activating each vertebral segment, from the
21 tailbone upward or from the scapula downward, to achieve fluid and expressive motion through precise
22 neuromuscular engagement Haas (2017). Beginners often struggle with precisely engaging these deep
23 postural muscles, highlighting the need for increased somatosensory awareness. To support this, various
24 haptic technologies have been explored, such as vibration for localized signals and EMS for deeper muscle
25 activation (Cho et al., 2023). These systems improve proprioception and support muscle isolation essential
26 for training and rehabilitation. Our ongoing study investigates which haptic approaches best support
27 multisensory engagement for embodied motor learning.

28 Our system also incorporates other sensory inputs such as breathing (vital for core stability and focus
29 (Jerath et al., 2006)), eye tracking (balance, postural alignment, expressive clarity) in order to promote
30 holistic body awareness and supports dance-based rehabilitation, consistent with the principles of dance
31 movement therapy Payne et al. (1992).

32 In summary, our research explores how AI-driven co-embodiment and multisensory VR systems can
33 enhance motor skill learning and support rehabilitation. By enabling shared control of a virtual body with
34 an AI teacher, our system offers first-person adaptive guidance for dance-based training. Tai Chi serves as
35 a key example of shared agency and embodied feedback. Furthermore, integrating haptic, auditory, and
36 visual cues improves body awareness, breath regulation, and gaze control, which are essential for effective
37 embodied interaction. These findings demonstrate how virtual reality and AI can promote sustainable
38 personal development, with potential health, education, and wider metaverse applications.

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Disability Centred Design and Interactive Machine Learning: A Co-creative Methodology for a more Accessible Metaverse

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2 ABSTRACT

3 The metaverse promise is a shared place of connection where we can meet for transformative
4 and mundane digital experiences, which could create new worlds without the ableist structures
5 and systems we live in. However, the technology underpinning the metaverse is still extremely
6 inaccessible to many disabled users (Gerling and Spiel, 2021). Without centering disabled
7 experience and making it a key design concern within the metaverse we are upholding, reinforcing
8 and creating new structures of ableism. To create a truly equitable disabled creators and
9 researchers need to be part of the designing interaction. In this flashtalk I will explore a
10 methodology for participatory research and interaction design using Interactive Machine Learning
11 (IML) tool, InteractML to create new ways of interacting in the metaverse. This work was done in
12 collaboration with associate dancers from Candoco dance company.

13 **Keywords:** Metaverse, Accessibility, Disability, Machine Learning, Interactive

1 TALK

14 In navigating an ableist technology, it is common practice in disabled communities to “hack” technology
15 and the environments, designing new ways of interacting that are designed specifically for your body-mind
16 (Perry, 2024). Crip technoscience calls for research and practice in “knowing-making” (Hamraie, 2017)
17 that centers the skills, wisdom and hacks of disabled people, that position disabled people as “experts
18 and designers in everyday life” (Hamraie and Fritsch, 2019). In designing and creating interactions in the
19 metaverse disabled people should be integral as part of that design process. Disabled communities have
20 already established this practice in the metaverse, such as mods in VRChat¹.

21 Unlike traditional machine learning pipelines, IML engages users iteratively in the training and refining of
22 AI models (Bernardo and Grierson, 2017). IML enables users to have control and develop an understanding
23 of the machine learning system using small datasets which are completely transparent to users. This
24 subverts current power dynamics in AI putting the user in full control of where the data comes from and
25 where it is going (Vigliensoni et al., 2022). InteractML integrates an IML system for designing movement
26 interaction with game engines Unity and Unreal (Hilton et al., 2021; Plant et al., 2020, 2021). Using

¹ Dale 2022 <https://access-54.ability.uk/2022/09/09/vrchat-screwed-over-disabled-players-but-the-devs-are-trying-to-fix-it/> [Accessed 16th April 2025]

27 InteractML users can record examples of their poses, gestures or movements, so the system can recognise
28 these movements and the user can connect these to outputs. It uses a node-based visual scripting language
29 requiring minimal programming and democratising access to using IML. Using InteractML the AI becomes
30 a collaborator, where disabled creators can teach the system their way of moving. This gives users creative
31 agency, where in the core of this creative process with AI there is consent, transparency, and co-authorship.

32 In collaboration with disabled dancers Kat Hawkins, Xan Dye, Paulina Porwollik, Ted Wilkinson and
33 Dermot Farrell we embarked on a participatory design process exploring how to co-create accessibility
34 to inherently inaccessible technologies used in the metaverse VR and MOCAP. We sought to create
35 personalised interactions using these technologies which were designed with and for the dancer researchers
36 for performance and personal expression. InteractML was used as the tool to use the knowledge, skills and
37 practice of the dancer-researchers and the power of IML.

- 38 • What does a disability centred design process involve with IML?
- 39 • How can care and trauma-informed practice be embedded in a process with IML?
- 40 • How can you empower disabled dancer-researchers in the process with IML?

41 There cannot be a Metaverse for Good without disabled creators, researchers and audiences being leaders
42 in how it is shaped. By embedding accessible mechanisms for design such as InteractML which utilise the
43 power of transparent small data AI we can start to imagine how we can create a more accessible metaverse
44 which truly reimagines how we interact.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

45 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
46 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

47 Clarice Hilton conceptualisation, investigation, methodology, administration, software, writing original
48 draft. Rebecca Fiebrink supervision. Marco Gillies supervision, writing review and editing

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Extended reality technologies for behavioral therapy and cognitive training for people with intellectual disability

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ABSTRACT

The development of eXtended Reality (XR) technologies is allowing the improvement of traditional psychological methods for behavioral therapy, cognitive stimulation, and training Freeman et al. (2017). In particular, XR technologies offer the possibility to create secure and controlled settings where the users can interact with simulated environments without requiring to be physically present in them, and therapists can completely monitor and adjust the progress as needed Schiza et al. (2019). In particular, when dealing with people with Intellectual Disability (ID), the evoking possibilities that the creation of XR environments provide can help to alleviate their difficulties with abstract thinking, imagination or transfer of skills to real life scenarios Dagnan and Jahoda (2006).

Taking this into account, the works presented here aim at exploring the use of XR technologies in behavioral therapy and cognitive training with people with ID. These works stem from the project Includverso 5G¹, which aims at improving the quality of life of people with ID through immersive experiences benefiting from the interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaboration among Nokia, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and the Fundación Juan XXIII. Specifically, among other use cases, we developed two approaches for: 1) immersive behavioral therapy for individuals with fear of stairs and 2) immersive cognitive training to support job integration of people with ID.

In relation to the use of XR for behavioral therapy, we carried out a longitudinal study during six months with nine users of the Fundación Juan XXIII with bathmophobia (fear of going up and/or down stairs,) Goyena et al. (2025b). The proposed method was based on integrating XR technology in the classical systematic desensitization technique. The whole process (i.e., design, development, and evaluation of the method) was performed in close collaboration with psychologists. This included the selection of appropriate immersive stimuli representing

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¹ <http://www.includverso-5g.es/>

relaxing and feared stimuli (360-degree videos and virtual scenarios) and the development of an application for the therapists to control and monitor the sessions, integrated with a tool for the users to visualize the stimuli and provide feedback about their state Cortés et al. (2024). This feedback was obtained through questionnaires (simplified and adapted from classical ones Mott et al. (2019)) that appear in the virtual environment, and also from non-invasive biosensors providing physiological data, such as heart rate, electro-dermal activity, electromyography, etc. After the therapy sessions, all participants were able to go up and down real stairs that they were not able to face before², showing the benefits of the immersive therapy in overcoming their fears and in improving their inclusion and quality of life.

For cognitive training, a second application has been developed to train attention skills for individuals with ID with the goal of supporting their transition into the workforce Goyena et al. (2025a)³. In particular, two serious games simulating real-life tasks were developed, related to jobs that the individuals of the *Fundación Juan XXIII* are trained to perform. So, two primary scenarios have been created: a cafeteria and a supermarket. In the cafeteria scenario, the tasks to be performed by the users include collecting dirty dishes and serving customer orders. In the supermarket scenario, users are tasked with restocking products and processing customer orders. Different levels of difficulty were implemented for each task, allowing the users to progress and improve their skills. The application includes a module that allows real-time control and monitoring of the sessions by the therapists. The developed system also allows the collection of physiological data through non-invasive sensors, including heart rate, eye movement, etc. Another longitudinal study with nine users with ID from the *Fundación Juan XXIII* is currently being performed and the preliminary results highlight the potential of XR technologies in cognitive training and job placement for people with ID.

Future work will focus on the extension of these approaches to multi-user scenarios (including avatars based on artificial intelligence agents) and to other phobias and training scenarios.

Keywords: extended reality, accessibility, intellectual disability, behavioral therapy, cognitive training, user assessment.

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**KEYNOTES:
BRIEF ABSTRACTS**

The Neuroscience of self-consciousness: Basic research, clinical applications, and contemplative practice

Professor Olaf Blanke, Bertarelli Chair in Cognitive Neuroprosthetics, Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Switzerland

Recent work has targeted self-consciousness by investigating a minimal form of self-consciousness that is based on the multisensory perception of exteroceptive and interoceptive signals. This minimal form is called bodily self-consciousness (BSC) and has been studied in cognitive psychology, neuroscience, and in medicine, through extensive use of virtual and mixed reality (XR). Highlighting a series of studies investigating two fundamental aspects of BSC, referred to as self-location and self-identification with an individual's body, I show that BSC is based on torso-centered signals in a distributed cortical network, centered in temporo-parietal cortex. Such a torso-centered BSC system, by coupling exteroceptive and interoceptive signals, is fundamental for self-consciousness, leading to conscious mental states that are experienced as if by a unitary and embodied subject. In a second part of my presentation, I will highlight recent work that explores links between BSC (self-location, the first-person perspective, sense of agency) and so-called extended or narrative self-consciousness, in particular spatial navigation and episodic autobiographical memory, making again use of XR technology. I will present data showing that changes in BSC during encoding impact (1) spatial navigation performance and grid-cell like activity in entorhinal cortex and are of relevance (2) in episodic autobiographical memory, mediated by hippocampal activity coupled with BSC regions. These data link key subjective components of BSC with spatial navigation and the subjective reliving of personal events from one's past. In a final part of my talk, I will describe a new XR platform that allows to integrate altered states of BSC in two contemplative practices, self-compassion meditation and meditation practice targeting deconstruction of self-experience.

When Virtual Patients Meet Virtual Therapists: Harnessing LLMs and VR for Mental Health

Professor Doron Friedman, Sammy Ofer School of Communications, Reichman University, Israel.

Had I told you ten or twenty years ago that my lab was developing virtual therapists to treat virtual patients, it might have sounded like satire. Today, however, such systems lie at the forefront of applied AI research. In this talk, I present a series of studies at the intersection of large language models (LLMs), virtual humans, and extended reality (XR). Motivated by the global shortage of mental health professionals, our work explores scalable AI-driven solutions—from training resilience skills in caregivers to deploying fully automated therapists within immersive VR environments.

A central challenge is evaluating the quality of AI-generated therapeutic interactions. We demonstrate that commonly used metrics like MAUVE are inadequate for this domain. Instead, we introduce a novel evaluation method using simulated virtual patients who complete validated psychometric questionnaires designed for real patients. This approach yields high reliability and construct validity.

Building on this framework, we show how virtual therapists can self-improve using our evaluation metric as an oracle—via Direct Preference Optimization (DPO) and a new tree-based search method. Finally, we illustrate the potential of these technologies in VR: from structured role-play with virtual patients to AI-assisted self-reflection using embodied avatars. Together, these developments signal a shift toward scalable, interactive, and empirically grounded AI systems for mental health support and training.

Designing AI and VR Tools to Think With

Professor Yvonne Rogers, UCLIC, Computer Science Department, University College London, UK.

There is much potential for adding GenAI in its various guises to the Metaverse to empower people in a diversity of ways. But how can we ensure that the tools and immersive spaces we build are engaging and effective? Furthermore, how can we prevent ChatGPT and the like taking over our lives so that they simply end up doing the tasks we currently do more quickly and with less effort? One approach is to consider how to design AI with VR to deliberately require us to make more effort in order that we can experience a greater sense of achievement. To this end, I have been developing software tools that slow us down rather than speeding us up. To guide this research I have developed the 'To SEE' framework that proposes augmenting human minds with LLMs to Scaffold, Extend and Externalise our activities with the goal of engendering reflection. In particular, one line of research we have been pursuing has shown how combining VR tools with chatGPT and voice-enabled prompts can enhance wellbeing. By enabling people to externalise their thoughts through this fusion of technologies is proving to be an effective strategy for working through and overcoming troubled minds.

Virtual Humans

Professor Frank Steinicke, Department of Informatics, Hamburg University, Germany.

This talk explores the emerging field of Virtual Humans, highlighting how Extended Reality (XR) technologies and Artificial Intelligence (AI) are converging to create highly sophisticated, lifelike intelligent virtual agents (IVAs). We will examine the transformative potential of these IVAs across domains such as education, healthcare, and entertainment, as well as the associated risks related to ethical considerations, privacy, and societal impact. Drawing on insights from the EU PRESENCE project (<https://presence-xr.eu/>), which aims to advance the development and deployment of immersive virtual agents, the talk will also discuss future perspectives and the critical challenges that need to be addressed to harness the full capabilities of this rapidly evolving technology.

Virtual Worlds and Society: A Science for Policy Perspective

Dr Miguel Barreda Angeles, Scientific Researcher at Joint Research Center, European Commission.

This Keynote introduces the project VirtueS: Virtual Worlds and Society, currently underway at the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. The initiative seeks to explore the role virtual worlds will play in the EU over the coming years and to assess their potential effects on individuals and society as a whole. The presentation highlights key EU policy developments in this area, with a particular emphasis on the importance of understanding how emerging virtual environments may influence user wellbeing. It shares preliminary findings from a scoping review of the relevant literature and outlines forthcoming research steps, aimed at generating early insights to inform future policy actions that safeguard European values.

Clinical and well-being applications of the Metaverse

Professor Maria V. Sanchez-Vives (1) Institute of Biomedical Research August Pi i Sunyer, Barcelona, Spain, (2) ICREA, Barcelona, Spain

The illusion of presence that is generated in virtual environments and embodiment of virtual bodies based in sensorimotor correlations [1, 2] results, along with brain adaptability to new bodies and virtual worlds, in numerous applications [3], including those in physical and mental health. Here I will discuss clinical and well-being applications of the Metaverse in healthcare, focusing on four key areas: Clinical Applications of VR in Pain and Rehabilitation: Virtual reality (VR) within the Metaverse is demonstrating significant benefits for pain management and rehabilitation. Studies have shown VR interventions can reduce pain [4], improve range of motion [5], and enhance functional outcomes in conditions such as chronic low back and neck pain, with high patient safety and acceptance. These immersive environments can offer personalized, engaging experiences that increase adherence and motivation in rehabilitation programs. For reviews see [6, 7].

Metaverse for Patients and Focus Groups: The Metaverse enables innovative models for patient engagement, such as virtual focus groups. These shared virtual spaces allow patients, clinicians, and researchers to interact as avatars, facilitating user-centered design, remote participation, and rich patient feedback. Pilot studies indicate that Metaverse-based focus groups are well-received and may improve healthcare delivery by integrating patient perspectives into the development of new therapies and technologies [8].

Metaverse to Reduce Gender Discrimination: By providing avatars and using them for changing perspective, the Metaverse can help mitigate biases linked to gender, appearance, or other personal characteristics. This digital environments can be used for training into reducing discrimination and promoting inclusivity in both clinical, work and social contexts. The European research project META-TOO (A transfer of knowledge and technology for investigating gender-based inappropriate social interactions in the Metaverse; <https://meta-too.eu/>) investigates strategies to reduce these interactions in virtual worlds.

Metaverse to Reduce Gender Violence: The immersive and controlled nature of Metaverse platforms offers new avenues for education, support, and intervention aimed at preventing gender-based violence. Virtual environments can be used as a tool for rehabilitation of conduct of aggressors of intimate partner violence and other violent

behaviours [9, 10]. This may allow to reduce gender violence in ways not possible in traditional settings [11].

Collectively, these applications highlight the transformative potential of the Metaverse to enhance clinical outcomes, promote patient-centered care, and advance equity and well-being in healthcare.

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Ethical Issues in the Metaverse

Professor Patrick Haggard, Institute of Cognitive Neuroscience, UCL, UK.

Ideally, the metaverse would be a better place than real life, or at least no worse. In practice, people often behave less ethically in the metaverse than in real life. The reasons for this are often not directly related to the metaverse, but to authentication and identity: people generally behave worse when their identity is concealable or concealed. A distinctive feature of the metaverse is the multisensory immersion in a virtual environment. In the virtual environment, digital touch systems can interact directly with the user's body. This raises special ethical issues, because the stimuli act directly on the user's body, opening up the possibility of unwanted or unpleasant touch delivered by a metaverse system. A key concept for considering the ethics of such systems is the concept of *sensory autonomy*. Healthy adult individuals are assumed to have a right to choose the sensory inputs (sound, sight, touch etc.) that they want, so

they should not receive any unwanted stimulation during Metaverse interactions, just as in interactions in real life. This principle requires an obvious stop switch for all digital touch applications, and a system for ensuring that immersive tactile interaction is always subject to continuing ongoing consent.

